

**Search for the Cosmic Self: A Comparative Study of Keats's
and Ghani Khan's Poetry through the Perspectives of
Ibn Arabi and Kant**

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**Qurtuba University of Science and Information Technology
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THESIS SUBMISSION CERTIFICATE BY SUPERVISOR

This is to certify that the thesis submitted by student Atiqullah, ID # 19963, meets the standard required for its acceptance by the Department of English (Linguistics & Literature), Qurtuba University of Science and Information Technology, Peshawar, for the award of the degree of PhD.

I recommend that the thesis be accepted for the award of the PhD degree.

Supervisor: Assoc. Professor Dr. Abdul Hamid Khan

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Author's Declaration

I solemnly declare that the research work presented in the thesis titled “Search for the Cosmic Self: A Comparative Study of Keats’s and Ghani Khan’s Poetry through the Perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant” is entirely my work, with no significant contribution from any other person. I understand the zero-tolerance policy of the HEC as well as that of this University towards plagiarism. Therefore, I, as the author of the above-titled thesis, declare that no portion of my thesis has been plagiarised, and any material used as a reference is cited correctly. It is further declared that I have developed this thesis through my efforts under the guidance of my supervisor. No portion of the work presented in this thesis has been submitted in support of any other degree or qualification from any university in the country or abroad. Even if my statement is found to be incorrect at any stage, including after I have received my degree, the University and HEC reserve the right to withdraw my degree.

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This thesis is a testament to the collective support and encouragement I have received, and I am truly grateful.

Dedication

To my beloved family, for their unwavering love, endless patience, and unstinted support throughout this journey.

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Abstract

This comparative study examines the concept of a cosmic self in the poetry of John Keats and the Pashto poetry of Abdul Ghani Khan through the philosophical perspectives of Muhyi ud-din Ibn Arabi and Immanuel Kant. Despite stemming from different traditions, Ibn Arabi and Kant converge on the fundamentals of the cosmic self. In Ibn Arabi's mystical philosophy, the cosmic self revolves around the Unity of Being, where the individual self is bound in its essence to the Divine within the multiple cosmos (*Akbarian* mysticism). In Kant's transcendental idealism, the cosmic self can be inferred as a dimension of the noumenal realm connecting "the starry heavens above" and "the moral law within" the individual self. Keats's and Khan's poetry was selected in particular for this comparative study because their poetry thematically displays the existential questions of dissolution and regeneration of the self. This study follows Zpetenek's model of comparative literature and employs the triangulation method for data validation. It systematically analyses Keats's *Lamia*, *Endymion*, *Poems 1817* and *Poems 1820*, alongside the available English translation of Khan's 141 poems by Sahibzada Imtiaz titled *The Pilgrim of Beauty*. Structured into seven chapters, the research analyses Keats's and Khan's poetry sequentially, focusing on selfhood as "I" and as the cosmic self in light of the conceptual framework developed from Ibn Arabi's and Kant's philosophies through convergence and divergence, highlighting the cross-cultural and universal significance of the concept of the cosmic self. Chapter Seven synthesises the findings and offers theoretical implications and recommendations for future research. This study demonstrates that humans, regardless of their spatiotemporal and cultural circumstances, have a universal longing for a cosmic self that exists on an intermediary level as a connecting link. Keats and Khan symbolise their belief in a universal kinship transcending the constraints of time and space, uniting humanity through the accentuation of the allusions from the past as well as through the depiction of winged and airy phenomena, such as birds and angels.

Chapter One

Prelude

I am a withered flower,
And a garden desolate,
Melody of tears, grief,
Freezing sighs of a nightingale;

.....

I'm a silent melody,
And a tune forgotten, lost;
Youth frittered away in grief,
Come! Intoxication brings,
Moreover, my senses put to flight!
For my pain, the balm, become
Bring for me the brimming cup!

(Sahibzada, 2014, pp. 40–41).

1.1. Introduction

This introductory chapter outlines the concept of cosmic self. It has been a significant dimension of the philosophical inquiries across the intellectual traditions of the East and West. This chapter briefly lays down the interpretative framework, which draws on the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant, for analysing the cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's poetry. The chapter is divided into several sections, beginning with a brief background of the study and concluding with a glossary of key terms that the study will frequently reference during the analysis. The study contributes to the comparative literature by offering a unique analysis of the self as a cosmic reality.

1.2. Background of Study

Comparative literature encompasses and fortifies world literature. It operates on the principles of self-recognition by transcending geographical boundaries and secures an immersion in world

literature. This study aims to secure recognition for the literature of the other, which is located at the margins. That is why Zepetnek (1998) declares the goal of comparative literature to be “cross-linguistic, trans-cultural, trans-national, interdisciplinary, and cross-temporal” (p. 13). A literary text is the self-extension of the creator; therefore, the universal application of Eurocentric conventions to every text is as serious a crime as decapitating the very self that is behind its creation (Maxwell & Miller, 2014).

The self holds a status of macro within the microcosm in mysticism and philosophy. It symbolically unites the cosmos, the egoistic self and the divinely infinite (Nasr, 2007). This intrinsic world within the individual becomes equal in significance and magnitude to the external universe. Usually, a poetic genre is the most potent means of expressing the cosmic self. Rilke (2017) also meant the same when he said, “the only journey is the one within” (p. 35). Spontaneity and naturalness characterise the poetic composition for self-expression. A cosmically significant self, with its describable and indescribable, intelligible and unintelligible aspirations, can select poetry for its articulation.

This study takes a comprehensive approach. It delves deeply into the concept of the cosmic self in the poetic works of Keats and Khan. It employs a comparative model based on Zepetnek’s Systemic and Empirical Approach to literature. This model underscores its trans-cultural universalism. It bridges the gap between the dominant and the marginal literature (Zepetnek, 1998).

This study explores Keats’s and Khan’s poetry about the concept of the cosmic self. It uses a combined mystical and philosophical framework from Ibn Arabi and Kant. The theoretical underpinning for this research, developed comparatively by interweaving Ibn Arabi’s mysticism and Kant’s transcendental idealism, acknowledges the enduring principles regarding the self and its cosmic association. The research data comprises collation and analysis through triangulating the thematic and content analysis for objectivity and

authenticity. The study remained focused and delimited to Keats's poems, as collected in *Keats' Poetry: 4 Books: The Poetry of John Keats, including Lamia, Endymion, Poems 1817, and Poems 1820* and Khan's poems, translated from *Pashto* into English by Sahibzada, titled *The Pilgrim of Beauty* (Keats, 2012; Sahibzada, 2014). The poetic compositions and other works by Keats and Khan were also consulted during the data analysis for further validation.

The study was organised into seven chapters. The concept of the cosmic self is introduced in the first three chapters, which provide an overview of the previous relevant and current literature and establish the theoretical and methodological foundations. The succeeding chapters present data analysis in sequence for the exploration of different dimensions of the cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's poetry through the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant, as well as its cross-cultural and universal significance. The study culminates in Chapter Seven, which synthesises the results and gives recommendations.

1.2.1. Self—An Unresolved Riddle in Philosophy and Mysticism

The concept of cosmic self offers a challenge due to its abstract and ambiguous status in comparative literature (Dimkov, 2020). There is an intrinsic convergence within the Eastern philosophical and mystical thought regarding the concept of the cosmic self. However, it is generally absent from the Western intellectual tradition due to its widely divergent foundations in existential proclivities.

The classical philosophy was anchored to a teleological end. Socrates was a proponent of personal growth and self-understanding, who was followed by Plato with the concept of the self being immortal and illuminating. Aristotle made the self hylomorphic (comprising matter and form) and attributed to it the objective of attaining virtue and eudemonia or human flourishing (Altman, 2017; Moore, 2015; Simpson, 2001). Later, with the dawn of Christianity, Saint Augustine made the self rational and immortal, considering humanity enduring an

“existential riddle,” but Saint Aquinas divided the self into internal and external, the intentional and the phenomenal (Berry, 2017, pp. 87–106; Japola, 2002).

With the advent of modern philosophy, the concept of self underwent a significant shift. Descartes proclaimed a perpetual state of flux between mind and being, but Locke linked it empirically with the mind (Azeri, 2011; Chamberlain, 2020). Spinoza made the finite mind a repository of the essence, but for Hume, the self was an ideal. This concept was further developed by Berkeley, who supported the spirit-idea dualism (Azeri, 2018; Bettcher, 2008; Hubner, 2015). Kant’s successor, Hegel, made self-recognition contingent upon dialectics facilitated by the other, whereas Husserl’s self was experienced through direct intuition, playing a structuring role (Russon, 2011; Rudolf & Marbach, 1993).

In the East, religious scriptures, such as Hinduism, affixed the concept of the self (*atman*) to eternity. It became the essence in the *Upanishads* and cosmic in the *Vedantic* teachings. Buddhism denied the concept of eternity to the self (Andrej, 2016). In the eastern part of the Islamic world, *Avicenna*, with a background in metaphysics, divided the self into essence and existence. In contrast, on the western shores of Spain, *Averroes* identified existence with Being and truth (Belo, 2009). Another Muslim philosopher, *Al-Ghazali*, divided the self into spiritual essence and materially visible behaviour (Atesci, 2019). In the rationalist philosophy of the Islamic world, the *Mutazilites* rejected determinism and endowed the self with free will, a concept that the *Asharites* attributed to the divine (Taskheer, 2017; Toosi, 2020).

1.2.2. Ibn Arabi and Kant

Embracing the ethos of comparative literature that fosters cross-cultural and interdisciplinary dialogue, this study takes a mystical and philosophical framework. It engages in a dialectical exploration, juxtaposing the philosophies of Ibn Arabi and Kant with the poetry of Keats and Khan. This is unified by the concept of the ubiquitous cosmic self, through a comparative approach of Zepetnek (2003).

In the ontological framework of Ibn Arabi, the self is the fusion of body and spirit, with humans serving as an *isthmus* station (Corbin, 2013). This body-spirit coalescence into a single, cosmic self is an epiphany (sudden realisation), drawing on the analogy between synthesis and antithesis, as inspired by the *Quran and the Concept of Al-Furqan* (Arif, 2002). These different stations leave the seeker with the open option of finding self in the visible and in the invisible, or the imaginal world. In the Kantian epistemological framework, the self exists as material and as immaterial. However, it is the immaterial self that synthesises understanding with perception in a transcendental experience of apperception. It is thus the noumenal self and the phenomenal self. The noumenal is the essence (ineffable) and beyond comprehension, yet it also defines the actual character (Fushihara, 1987). Kant, however, did not explicitly expand on the concept of the cosmic self.

1.2.3. Quest for the Cosmic Self in the Poetic Texts of Keats and Khan

Like Goethe's *Weltliteratur*, transcending geographical boundaries, Keats and Khan also explore the concept of the cosmic self. Keats's longing for cosmic selfhood is palpable in the epitaph on his grave, which reads, "Here lies one whose name was writ in water" (Keats, 2005, p. xxxii). Similarly, Khan's poetry is characterised by a quest for "humanism," "the search for truth," and "self-realisation," echoing a similar yearning for the cosmic self (Sahibzada, 2014, p. xxi).

It is noticeable that Keats's protagonists often dissolve into oblivion towards the closure of his major poems. This recession is found in the following instances from Keats (2012):

- "They vanish'd far away!" (Endymion, line 1011).
- "no pulse, or breath they found" (Lamia, lines 309–310).
- "And so she pined, and so she died forlorn" (Isabella, or The Pot of Basil, LXIII).
- "they are gone: ay, ages long ago" (The Eve of St. Agnes, XLII).
- "Fled is that music:—Do I wake or sleep?" (Ode to a Nightingale, lines 79–80).

- “The red-breast whistles from a garden-croft; / And gathering swallows twitter in the skies...” (Ode to Autumn, lines 29–30).
- “plung’d all noiseless into the deep night” (Hyperion, lines 349–350).
- “She dwells with Beauty—Beauty that must die / ...at his lips / Bidding adieu...” (Ode to Melancholy, lines 21–22).

Khan’s poem “*Tapos ka Jawab*” (Question or Answer) also expresses the same dilemma of dissolution and regeneration. It emphasises this through a comparison with pails of water on a Persian wheel (Sahibzada, 2014):

Music wailing its death?	<i>Daa saaz khpal marg na karree saandi</i>
Or fire burning bright?	<i>Ka yau ur dey chi baleegi</i>
.....
Is it drawing-pails of water	<i>Mangooti ka da arat dee</i>
On a Persian water-wheel –	<i>Sa dakeegi sa tasheegi</i>

(pp. 124–127).

Khan (2014) repeats the same existential question in another poem, “*Yau Khub da Shaaair da Saba da Ranrra*” (A Dream of a Poet). Here, life is compared with a caravan of nomads that just stops over for a short duration at one point and then moves on:

What was it that’s gone?	<i>Daa sa woo chi tir shoo,</i>
.....	<i>Daa sa woo chi raaghla</i>
A caravan moving,	<i>Da sa qaafila, daa da chaa qaafila?</i>
But whose, and of what?
.....
Was this just a dream?	<i>Daa staa wu yau khub ka qisa wa zamaa</i>
Or the tale of my love?
.....
Was it beauty transcendent?	<i>Ghazab wu, rahmat wu ka noor ka ranrra?</i>
Or heavenly light?	

(pp. 214–215).

Keats's longing to become one with the cosmic self is manifested by his use of first and second person pronouns. The "I" flies towards "thee" on "the wingless wings of Poesy." It is "thee" which is an entity in the noumenal realm beyond the physical apprehension and can be accessed only through an experience in the ineffable realm (Keats, 2012, p. 293). This image of the wing reemerges in another of Keats's poems, where great spirits of the earth can transcend the limitations of space and time only on the back of the "Archangel's wing" (p. 201). Absent these channels of poetry and wings, Keats's life would come to an abrupt end like a water drop that is absorbed in the ocean without even bringing a negligible change to the magnitude of the ocean. Keats writes "Stop and consider! life is but a day; / A fragile dew-drop on its perilous way / From a tree's summit..." (p. 208).

Khan's poetry also has many instances that reflect his philosophy of the cosmic self and the nature of life. He establishes a connection between human existence and the essence (noumenal and spiritual realms) by comparing his beloved wife, despite being in "human form," to "a poet's dream," *Persian* beauty, and an honourable *Afghan* (Sahibzada, 2014, p. 5). Khan often recounts Keats when he recounts the temporality of life, which is "for a few days only, / And will soon be over, spent" (Sahibzada, 2014, pp. 268–269).

There is a limited number of comparative studies on Keats's and Khan's poetry. These aim to address other dimensions in their work without making significant contributions to the existing literature on both (Bacha, 2010; Khan et al., 2020). The self as a subjective element has been analysed in Keats's and Khan's poetry. However, the concept of cosmic self remains a dimension in Keats's and Khan's poetry that has been unexplored particularly in the mystical and philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. The study aims to explore this by

combining Ibn Arabi's mystical philosophy and Kant's transcendental idealism in a single framework.

1.3. Statement of the Problem

Self holds a special significance in Keats's and Khan's poetry. While some other aspects related to subjectivity have been the subject of comparative studies, the specific concept of the self and its cosmic connection within a mystical or philosophical context needs particular analysis. The study aims to fill this gap by developing a conceptual framework that draws on the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant, and applies it to the poetry of Keats and Khan for data analysis. It makes a significant contribution to literary research in comparative studies by combining four entirely different literary and intellectual traditions of the East and West.

1.4. Research Objectives

The study focuses on Keats's and Khan's poetry. They develop a concept of selfhood that transcends conventional interpretations. It regards the self as so much cosmically significant that it echoes both in the tradition of *Akbarian* mysticism and Kantian transcendental idealism. Ibn Arabi and Kant consider poetry as a vehicle for universal self-realisation. This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To comparatively explore the attributes of self and its cosmic association in Keats's and Khan's poetry from the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.
- To analyse areas of convergence and divergence in Keats's and Khan's poetry regarding the concept of the cosmic self from the mystical and philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.
- To comparatively evaluate the transcultural and universal significance of the concept of the cosmic self in the poetry of Keats and Khan, drawing on the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.

1.5. Research Questions

To achieve the objectives, the study is designed to explore the following questions:

- What are the attributes of the self and its cosmic association in Keats's and Khan's poetry, as viewed from the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant?
- How do Keats and Khan converge and diverge in their poetry regarding the concept of the cosmic self from the mystical and philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant?
- Why does the concept of cosmic self reflect a trans-cultural and universal dimension across divergent literary traditions represented by the poetic articulation of Keats and Khan?

1.6. Rationale of the Study

Few comparative studies existed to inquire particularly into the concept of self in the poetry of Keats and Khan. However, this concept needs to be explored trans-culturally, trans-nationally, trans-linguistically and cross-temporally in the works of Keats and Khan, with particular reference to the concept of cosmic self as presented by Ibn Arabi and Kant. These two philosophers were selected for their significant contributions to understanding the self and its cosmic connection. Their ideas thus provide a rich theoretical framework for this study.

This research serves as a bridge between the literary and intellectual heritage of the East and West, drawing on literature, mysticism and philosophy to provide evidence that humans are intrinsically cosmic and universal.

1.7. Delimitations of the Study

- The study is limited to the poetic works of the Romantic poet Keats and the Pashto poet Khan, leaving out other Romantic or *Sufi* poets except where required for comparative or contextual references.
- The study focuses on the concept of the cosmic self, which is a metaphysical and philosophical idea connecting the self with the universe and divine essence. Other

themes in Keats's and Khan's poetry have been discussed to see if they interact with the concept of the cosmic self.

- The analysis is based upon the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant by developing a conceptual framework from their concept of self and its cosmic association for interpreting Keats's and Khan's poetry. The self, as it is understood in psychology, is outside the scope of this study.
- The study focuses on Keats's poetic compositions, included in *The Poetry of John Keats: Lamia, Endymion, Poems 1817, and Poems 1820*. Similar delimitation is also exercised regarding Khan's poetry by including an English translation of Sahibzada for his book *The Pilgrim of Beauty* (Keats, 2012; Sahibzada, 2014). Sahibzada's book is acknowledged as an authentic and reliable English translation of Khan's poetry.
- Contextual requirements of historical and biographical significance are considered; however, those are not the primary focus. The primary focus is rather the philosophical and mystical portrayal of the cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's poetry.

1.8. Significance of the Study

The concept of cosmic self had never been explored in Keats's and Khan's poetry through the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant before this study. This study provides an exploration into a unique dimension in Keats's and Khan's poetry, through the development of a conceptual framework regarding the cosmic self in the *Akbarian* and Kantian perspectives. It also establishes a bridge between the Eastern and Western literary, philosophical and mystical traditions. The study serves as a point of redefinition of the selfhood in its cosmic significance. The study would add manifold to the academic richness of the comparative literature.

1.9. Literature Review

Comparative literature is not produced within a defined national boundary. It transcends these, leading Goethe to label it world literature (Jay, 2001; Sahin, 2016). Aristotle's *Poetics* rightly

takes credit for being the first piece of comparative literature on account of its different translations. However, in modern times, it was the Spanish Jesuit Juan Andrés who formally launched comparative literature on the Western continent. However, the Eastern continent of Asia did not trail behind, as its rich literature also gained access to Europe through translated works, such as *The Thousand and One Nights*, and earned respect from giants of their age, including Goethe (Dominguez et al., 2015; Goethe, 1850; Knipp, 1874).

In the contemporary world, comparative literature has fully matured into an “inter-disciplinary, cross-cultural [and] trans-national” discipline. It has wrested itself free from the dominance of the European languages and canon with comprehensively evolved theories, approaches and methodologies of its own (Behdad & Thomas, 2014, p. 1; Damrosch, 2003; Dominguez et al., 2015; Manqoush, 2014; Spivak, 2003).

Comparative literature offers a common ground of interplay to poetry, philosophy and mysticism. Almost every second philosopher, mystic or poet has contributed in some measure to the repository of comparative literature. For instance, Hugo Meltzl, a philosopher, took over the chair of being the first editor of the pioneering *Journal of Comparative and World Literature* (Damrosch, 2006). There always exists a universally acknowledged dimension that unites all world literature through a single point of contact. Hegel emphasises imagination in the world of arts, whereas Russell focuses on emotion in mysticism and philosophy (Domínguez et al., 2015; Kottman & Squire, 2018; Russell, 1921). Another point of contact that invites the interest of comparatists is the mystical search for unity between the individual and the absolute, thus binding all humanity into a universal existence (Hart, 2003). Similarly, language and poetry are other common possessions of humankind, even if spoken and produced in different forms (Guillen, 1993).

Poetic compositions with mystically transcendental and imaginative themes, such as the quest for ultimate truth, “cosmic consciousness,” and “sagacity,” carry the attributes of cosmic

significance (Spurgeon, 1913, pp. 2–7). This mystically cosmic connection in the poetic compositions is established differently, such as through asceticism in the East and through immanence in the West. Saint Augustine meant the same through his advice “Interrogate thyself, O man, and make of thyself a step to the things that be above thee” (Underhill, 1913, p. ix). Keats’s “Endymion” (2012) describes the same through:

Feel these things? – that moment we have stepped

Into a sort of oneness, and our state

Is like a floating spirit’s... (Book I, lines 796–798).

Among the existing literary genres, poetry is uniquely well-suited to serve as a vehicle for exploring answers to ontological and epistemological questions, such as the relationship between matter and spirit, or the development of understanding and perception (Davies, 2004; Pettinger, 1999).

A brief overview in the following reveals that some literature is available on Keats’s and Khan’s poetry. However, there exists no study in the domain of the comparative study that has analysed Keats’s and Khan’s poetry for directly exploring cosmic association of the self or even bare self in some mystical and philosophical perspectives or even in the mystical and philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.

Keats made poetry overcome internal schism through creativity that stems from the individual self and culminates in conscious realisation (Roberts, 1993). Despite his internal divisions and external challenges, Keats’s desire to escape from the material world would ultimately find enduring peace in the physical world (Haque & Rahman, 2013). This oscillation and binary fission between the material and immaterial could also be attributed to his interest in the ancient Indian philosophy, which he had read through an English translation (Dash, 2014). Other instances of this inner division are reflected in the interplay of pleasure and pain, as well as beauty and ugliness in his works (Nicholas, 2019; Sarkar & Munshi, 2019). Keats’s

attachment to the physical world was so strong that he remained essentially a phenomenologist, rejecting Platonism and turning towards external nature (Ahad, 2020; Hussain, 2022; LO, 2022; Nicholas, 2019).

Keats and other Eastern poets have also been studied comparatively, revealing several cross-cultural, cross-linguistic and thematic affinities between them. For instance, the 9th-century Chinese poet Li He, in the Far East, was as Romantic in his themes and political aspirations as 19th-century Keats (Yuan, 1996). The Eastern poetic tradition of worshipping the beloved in a master-slave relationship was shared by Keats and Ottoman court poets within the framework of Hegelian philosophy (Ozkan, 2021). A similar connection existed between the 16th-century *Sufi* poet of the Punjab, Shah Hussain and Keats concerning the emergent evolution of self in Morgan's and Gafni's framework (Fatima, 2011).

Within the Western continent, many poets paralleled Keats in their philosophical approach to life. For example, both Keats and Shelley transformed themselves into sites of conflicting fictions within the Nietzschean framework (Sandy, 1998). A continuous process of transformation and self-development unfolded in Keats and Coleridge, drawing on the Schlegelian and Hegelian philosophical perspectives (Ngiewih, 2021). Poetry became a medium for gaining self-awareness and recognition in the works of Keats, Byron and Shelley (Westwood, 2017). Keats, Coleridge and Shelley even shared mystical predispositions in their yearning to attain oneness with the divine through self-annihilation (Beyad & Vafa, 2021). Keats, Shelley and Eliot had no fixed image associated with the concept of truth (Tyner, 2022). An intertextual study of Coleridge and Keats concludes that both poets are bound by language, social and cultural norms, despite variations in geographical location and time (Shah & Gul, 2021). Keats and Coleridge were two contemporaries bound together by linguistic, cultural and social norms (Omid, 2022).

In the *Pashto* literary tradition, one finds the earliest example of mystical poetry in *Khair-ul-Bayan*. Bayazid wrote to disseminate his philosophy of the Unity of Being, but was vehemently opposed by *Darveeza Baba* (Shah, 2020; Yaqubi, 2020). The mystical philosophy of Bayazid's Unity of Being is paralleled by Hamza Shinwari's philosophy in the contemporary world (Dinakhel & Bakhshali, 2022).

Pashto poet Khan was a modernist. His anti-structuralism dissuaded him from unthinkingly bowing down to dogma and religious autocracy by the religious clerics (Awan & Ali, 2014; Munir, 2018). Their shallowness could only be content with living in the material world of space and time, which Khan found to be simply symbols of impermanence (Sardaraz & Nusrat, 2019). Acknowledging the transitoriness of the physical world, Khan emerged as a mystic in the modern sense, seeking the meanings of actual existence and the relationship with the divine (Ahmed et al., 2021). Having no illusions about religious doctrines, Khan, like Plato, also believed that the human soul is immortal and is a part of duality that links humanity and love to the immortal soul (Zakir & Ramzan, 2022). Khan often emerges as a Platonist who deliberates on the immortality of the human soul and the mortality of the human body without succumbing to pessimism and nihilism (Safa & Sahand, 2022). Wordsworth and Khan, though belonging to different countries and times, shared a common affinity for pantheism, a love of harmony and empathetic feelings for the sufferings of humanity (Rehman & Ahmad, 2016). A thematic affinity also exists between the East and West, as evident in the approaches towards life and death in the poetry of Khan and Emily Dickinson, inviting a deeper exploration of these parallels (Mehnaz et al., 2022). Keats and Khan shared several characteristics, including their approach towards suffering, love of nature, beauty and musicality, with some differences, such as Keats was sensuous, while Khan was unambiguous (Bacha, 2010). Khan's poetry was as rich as that of any Western poet, such as Keats, in themes of love, beauty and nature (Khan et al., 2020).

Despite the rich Chinese literature that Goethe (1850) believed to be a common heritage of humanity, a noticeable gap remains in the literature. Specifically, there is a lack of direct analyses of specific literary works from the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant, particularly in the context of comparative studies between the *Sufi* tradition of the Unity of Being in the East and American transcendentalism (Awad, 2018; Coates, 2002; Elahi et al., 2022; Jahromi & Amjad, 2023; Khan et al., 2023; Myerson, 2000).

1.10. Theoretical Framework

This thesis is an exploration of the self as part of a cosmic system that operates at multiple levels. It is based on the concepts of self in the mystical philosophy of Ibn Arabi and the Transcendental Idealism of Kant. The parallels in several arguments and theses between Ibn Arabi and Kant serve as the theoretical foundation of this work.

In the *Akbarian* ontology, the self is the combination of body and spirit that occupies an intermediary position between the spiritual and physical worlds (Corbin, 2013). There is no body-spirit duality between the materially physical and immaterially spiritual self, as described in the analogy of the Quran, which embodies both synthesis and antithesis within one (Arif, 2002). Ibn Arabi's division of the world into the seen, unseen and imaginative also follows the same principle.

The Kantian epistemology is founded upon the principle of dualism. The self exists in the sensory realm of phenomena and the supra-sensory realm of noumena. The phenomenal self is part of the intelligible world and the noumenal self of the transcendently ineffable world (Fushihara, 1987). Humans are sure to suffer from a transcendental illusion (being deceived by reason to go beyond the limits). Kant calls it using reason mistakenly beyond the limits of experience (Kant, 1998).

Ibn Arabi's concept of self becomes cosmic through linking it to the cosmic whole. It becomes part of the ultimate reality that can assume all the attributes of physical, psychic,

spiritual and absolute (Chittick, 1989, 1998; Corbin, 2013). Kant did not acknowledge the self as being cosmic. However, he tied the self to the physical (phenomenal) on the *a priori* presumption (noumenal), with the physical existence being subject to the law of causation. The moral being, though, is subject to freedom only (Kant, 1996). It is this cosmic attribute of transcendental idealism that represents objects in the phenomenal world through concepts in the mind, known as *a priori* (Durant, 1933). Ibn Arabi and Kant begin from the sensory realm, but Kant stops there, fearing transcendental illusion, whereas Ibn Arabi continues to explore the realms of spirits and mystery (Arif, 2002; Marinay, 2015). Both Ibn Arabi and Kant attribute sublime qualities to humans. Humans exercise free choice (Ibn Arabi and Kant), possessing self-willed freedom and autonomy for achieving their ends (Kant, 1997; Rakhmat, 2022).

1.11. Methodology

This comparative study on Keats's and Khan's poetry from a mystical and philosophical perspective is qualitative and interpretative. It draws on the hermeneutic and phenomenological traditions to explore poetry as a medium for philosophical self-exploration and its cosmic associations. Following Zepetnek's model (1998), data from Keats's and Khan's poetry is thematically analysed for the concept of cosmic self in the following steps:

- Identifying the self in Khan's poetry, followed by a thematic and content analysis of different dimensions of the cosmic self in his poetry from the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.
- Juxtaposing Keats's and Khan's poetic compositions to analyse convergences and divergences in the concept of the cosmic self from the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.
- Evaluating Keats's and Khan's poetry for trans-cultural and universal significance.

1.12. Method

The study employs a qualitative research methodology. It is deemed appropriate for this research, as it facilitates a rich interpretative analysis of poetic texts (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). Being a study in poetic literature with philosophical and mystical undercurrents, the study stresses the exploration of the subjective and symbolic dimensions of the text (Creswell, 2014). This qualitative research also employs a flexible approach to incorporating cross-culturally philosophical themes (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

1.13. Organisation of the Study

It has been divided into the following seven chapters:

Chapter One: Prelude

Chapter Two: Critical Appraisal of the Related Literature

Chapter Three: Theoretical and Methodological Paradigm

Chapter Four: The Whispering Cosmos in Keats's Verse

Chapter Five: Khan's Interweaving of "I" with the Cosmic Whole

Chapter Six: Keats and Khan: Unveiling Unity in Diversity

Chapter Seven: Postlude: A Wandering Keats from a far-off Place like Wretched Khan

1.14. Glossary of Important Terms

- **Akbarian:** The mystical school and legacy of Ibn Arabi (Unity of Being) is known as the *Akbarian* system of philosophy.
- **American Transcendentalism and Kantian Transcendental Idealism:** American Transcendentalism is more spiritual, focusing on accessing the immaterial realm by transcending the material. In contrast, Kantian Transcendental Idealism is a more philosophical approach, emphasising the shaping of the phenomenal realm through human perception and inner categories.
- **Annihilation (*Fana*):** It is a *Sufi* concept that stands for dissolution and effacement of the self or ego into the divine or the beloved.
- **Cosmic Self:** It encompasses the earthly and heavenly aspects, transcending the individual and uniting all existence into one whole. It is known as *atman* in the Indian philosophy, *One* in Pythagorean or Neoplatonic philosophies, Perfect Human in Ibn Arabi's philosophy, and Genius and Superman in Kant and Nietzsche, respectively.
- **Dualism:** It argues that reality exists separately and distinctly on two levels, such as mind and body, noumena and phenomena, good and evil.
- **Essence and Existence:** Essence is the source or nature of an entity or what constitutes its *ipseity* and innermost attributes. Existence is the physical appearance or the whatness (*quiddity*) of an object. Ibn Arabi calls essence *Huwiyya* (roughly Kant's noumena) and existence *Mahiyya* (Kant's phenomena).
- **Immanence and Transcendence:** Immanence refers to the within-ness of the divine in the spatiotemporal world, whereas transcendence denotes the without-ness of the divine beyond spatiotemporal existence.
- **Isthmus (*Barzakh*):** It is a Greek term for a narrow strip of land connecting two larger landmasses. It is translated as *Barzakh* in the *Sufi* tradition, which means an

intermediary state between two different states, such as the life between death and resurrection.

- **Noumenal Reality:** In transcendental idealism, it refers to the reality that exists in itself and is beyond human understanding, as it transcends the limitations and categories of spatiotemporal existence.
- **Perfect Human (*Al Insan-ul Kamil*):** It is the ideal human who carries the attributes of the divine and stands as an *isthmus (barzakh)* between the two realms of the finite and infinite, material and immaterial, essence and existence. In Kant's philosophy, the concept of artistic genius in the *Critique of Judgement* also creates harmony in imagination and understanding.
- **Phenomenal Reality:** In Kant's system, it is the reality as it appears to us within our knowable experience, shaped by our perception.
- **Realms of Ibn Arabi:** Kant divides reality into noumenal and phenomenal, whereas Ibn Arabi divides it into five named as 1) the divine realm *Al-Hahoot*, 2) the divine names *Al-Lahoot*, 3) the realm of power *Al-Jabaroot*, 4) the realm of sovereignty *Al-Malakoot*, and 5) the human realm *Al-Nasoot*.
- **Sublime:** In Kant's philosophy of Judgement, it overpowers our sensory perception and imaginative capacity, evoking a sense of awe, but at the same time compelling us to acknowledge the power of reason over thinking about the infinite as well as our sense of human dignity.
- **Subsistence (*Baqa*):** It is also a *Sufi* concept that holds of eternal existence in the divine after annihilation through regeneration.
- **Synthesis:** It forms part of pure reason in Kant's philosophy and is the ability of the mind to combine different human faculties, such as experience and concepts, understanding and perception. Its roughly equivalent is Ibn Arabi's unity, though

stemming from a different tradition of mysticism, where the synthesis occurs between the human and the divine. In Kant, synthesis is epistemological, and in Ibn Arabi, unity is ontological.

- **Teleology:** It is derived from the Greek *telos*, which means end or purpose. It looks at the actions from the perspectives of goals and purpose.
- **Theomorphic:** It refers to some entity taking the form of the divine.
- **Theophany:** It is the manifestation of the divine in tangibly visible form.
- **Transcendental Idealism:** According to Kant, human experiences of the physical world (phenomenal reality) are structured by human perception, which is facilitated by twelve innate categories, organised into four groups: quantity, quality, relation and modality. This tradition of philosophy is also Kantian philosophy.
- **Unity of Being:** This concept is expressed in nearly the same terms by ancient Brahmanic schools, Eastern *Sufis* such as Ibn Arabi and modern monist or phenomenological philosophies, which hold that reality is fundamentally one, with all existence being interconnected as a single whole.

CHAPTER TWO

Critical Appraisal of the Related Literature

I died as a mineral and became a plant,

I died as a plant and rose to an animal,

I died as animal and I was man.

Why should I fear? When was I less by dying?

(Rumi, trans. Nicholson, 1995).

2.1. Introduction

This chapter lays the foundation for the study by situating it within the historical, geographical and intellectual contexts. It focuses on exploring the cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's poetry from the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. The chapter also gives a historical overview of the development of the concept of self in the light of the ancient and modern philosophical and mystical traditions. This chapter thus builds the conceptual and philosophical foundations of the cosmic self by analysing the following main areas:

- Cosmic Self as Grounded in Thematic Affinity with Comparative Literature
- An Overview of the Cosmic Self in Mysticism and Philosophies
- Selfhood and Its Cosmic Significance in the Eastern and Western Philosophies
- Ibn Arabi and the Emerging Concept of Cosmic Self from the Unity of Being
- Kant's Transcendental Idealism and the Emerging Concept of the Cosmic Self
- Thematic Development of the Self in the Comparative Studies on Keats and Khan
- Keats's Poetic Assertion of the Phenomenal World
- Thematically Emerging Self in Khan's Poetry
- Poetry as a Source of Articulating the Metaphysics of the Self
- Key findings
- Conclusion

2.2. Cosmic Self as Grounded in Thematic Affinity with Comparative Literature

Comparative literature develops a relationship between cultures, languages and disciplines. It is also known as world literature because it transcends temporal and spatial boundaries. An ancient work such as Aristotle's *Poetics* can also be presented as part of comparative literature due to its cross-cultural and cross-linguistic impact and be credited as the first product of Comparative literature. In the modern world, comparative literature developed in a religious environment, pioneered by a Spanish Jesuit, Juan Andrés (1740-1817), whose work might also have influenced Henry Hallam (1777-1859) of England. Despite its comparative obscurity, Asia also produced masterpieces in comparative literature that gained access to Europe through translations, foremost among those being *The Thousand and One Nights* (Dominguez et al., 2015; Goethe, 1850; Jay, 2001; Knipp, 1874; Sahin, 2016; Zepetnek, 2003).

Comparative literature has now assumed the status of a fully matured and independent discipline. It follows an interdisciplinary, cross-cultural and trans-national approach. The breadth of its scale lies outside the influence of the Eurocentric languages with its independent theories, approaches and methodologies (Behdad & Thomas, 2014; Damrosch, 2003; Domínguez et al., 2015; Manqoush, 2014; Spivak, 2003).

Comparative literature provides a common ground to poetry, philosophy and mysticism through its interdisciplinarity. It is evident even in the practitioners of these disciplines. For instance, Meltzl (1848-1908), despite being a philosopher, became the first ever editor of a purely literary magazine *Journal of Comparative and World Literature*. It also appears that the interdisciplinarity provided by the comparative literature between different disciplines does not rest solely in structural and technical terms but also on a much deeper level in the imagination as it is for Hegel or in the emotions as it is for Russell who applies it to connect philosophy and mysticism (Damrosch, 2006; Domínguez et al., 2015; Kottman & Squire, 2018; Russell, 1921; Stace, 1961).

Comparative literature proceeds metaphorically in the mystical tradition of the search for union between the individual and the universal, transcending geographical barriers, temporal divisions and religious differences. It thus collates the individual with the universal and so shares a common vision of humanity bound into universal existence. Similarly, the object of literature remains the same; its manifestations, though, take different forms and languages. For example, poetry is a common possession of all humanity, and its manifestation in different genres is explicable (Hart, 2003; Domínguez et al., 2015; Goethe, 1850; Guillén, 1993).

2.3. An Overview of the Cosmic Self in Mysticism and Philosophies

The self, being intrinsically associated with cosmos, has always been at the forefront of the mystical and philosophical traditions. It has also been interpreted variably since ancient times. It is either being one with the divine, a quintessential part of the cosmic and universal order or a consciousness that transcends the physical and holds the whole cosmos within itself.

In the *Vedantic* literature, the *Atman*, or the inner self, is part of the Brahman, or the universal and cosmic consciousness, reflecting the unity and non-duality of the self. The cosmic self thus transcends the individual self and becomes part of the universal self. In the classical period, Heraclitus defined the soul as *logos* that inheres in the universe. Plato made the ideal form as the frame behind all creation, while Plotinus, pioneering a mystical vision, had the soul constantly moving towards attaining oneness with the *One* that transcended all existence (Plotinus, 1991; Radhakrishnan & Moore, 1967)

During the Middle Ages, when theology and cosmology were fused, Ibn Arabi developed the mystical philosophy of *Wahdat al-Wujud* (Unity of Being) that emphasised uncovering the truly cosmic nature of self by attaining oneness with the divine through self-annihilation and subsistence. The Christian mystic Eckhart pioneered the concept of the ground of the soul, which postulated that the core self is the divine essence. Jewish Kabbalist tradition holds the

soul to be a part of a cosmic whole that continuously reveals itself through creation (Chittick, 1989; McGinn, 2001; Scholem, 1974).

Due to its emphasis on humanism and individualism, the Renaissance revived the interest in the human self by equating it with a microcosmos holding the whole macrocosmos within. Ficino and Bruno portrayed the self as representative of cosmic order, which it brings through unity with the divine. During the Enlightenment, when the German Idealistic philosophy had many followers, the self was considered responsible for structuring knowledge and moral law. Kant was not a mystic, but his concept of numenal or transcendental self, in addition to his concept of transcendental freedom, reflected a cosmically significant self that was responsible for universal structure. Kantian philosophy was later expanded and elaborated by his contemporaries and successors like Fichte, Schelling and Hegel. Hegel rather centred his philosophy upon the concept of the Absolute Spirit that holds the individual self as a quintessential moment of realisation (Hegel, 1977; Kant, 1998; Yates, 1964).

With the developments in psychology during the contemporary era, Jung gave a cosmic dimension to the self through his theory of archetypes when he proposed that the self is not merely personal but also transpersonal and symbolic of the divine. Emerson considered the “Universal Being” living inside him. According to Maharshi cosmic self can be realised through transcending the ego in order to realise a boundless consciousness which is actually cosmos (Emerson, 1983, p. 10; Jung, 1977; Maharshi, 2000).

2.4. Selfhood and Its Cosmic Significance in the Eastern and Western Philosophies

As was noticed in the previous section, the concept of self and its cosmic association has always sparked profound philosophical debates in the past, stimulating intellectual curiosity and exploration. Those debates centred on different preferences in the Eastern and Western traditions. The West subjected itself to reason, autonomy and transcendental idealism; while the East focused more on its mystical unity with all existence as part of a cosmic whole. It sees

the self as an *isthmus* between the empirical and metaphysical realms. Plato and Aristotle transformed the concept of the self from physical to ideal, with the human form being a prison where the self always keeps yearning to reunite with the ideal. The Neoplatonists like Plotinus and Saint Augustine argued that the self moves towards unity with the One through a process of dissolution. These profound philosophical ideas are also noticeable in Keats's and Khan's poetry, which seeks answers to the existential questions about the essence and existence (Chittick, 1998; Cooper, 1997; Crowther, 1993; Hadot, 1995; Lear, 1988; Matthews, 2002).

As noticed, the roots of the self and its cosmic association are mysterious. It unites the cosmos, the individual self and the divinely infinite. So, it becomes a magnification of the individual self to merge it with all the creation and the divine essence. The ascetic and mystic traditions across the East and West reflect this experience. Most of the mystics practise poetry because of its transcendental and philosophical nature to realise the cosmic self. Generally, in Eastern mysticism, the individual self becomes cosmic through annihilation, but in the Western tradition, it becomes cosmic through existing universally in nature (Nasr, 2007; Spurgeon, 1913; Underhill, 1913).

This element of ineffability associated with the self is also the focal point of the ancient Eastern philosophies. These view the self as part of a cosmic whole or divine existing both on the internal and external levels. The Hindu scriptures negated the individual self as illusory and rather named it *Brahman*, which it defined as a cosmically universal truth. The self could secure freedom from individual identity through the practice of *ahimsa* and *moksha*, which were defined as non-violence and liberation from the cycle of birth, death and rebirth, respectively. The Buddhist scriptures completely denied the existence of any self at all or its association with any concept like immortality. These scriptures extolled annihilation. At times, Keats's and Khan's poetry also reflects this theme of annihilation. In China, the Dao philosophy resolved this conflict between self and no-self through placing it along a continuum. The Daoist poetry

also abounds with imagery that portrays themes of cosmic connection, nature and no-self (Ames & Hall, 2003; Deutsch, 1988; Harvey, 2015; Ivanhoe, 2002; Shankara, 1978; Suzuki, 1956).

European tradition also does not escape the debate about the self. In the Classical period of European philosophy, Socrates, Plato and Aristotle presented the self as dual due to the combination of matter and form. But with the advent of Christianity, Saint Augustine and Aquinas make the self rational, existential and metaphysical. In modern philosophies, Descartes and Locke defined the self as subject to change and empiricism. Spinoza transformed the self into a universal essence, and Hume made it a reflective repository. Berkeley and Hegel made the self dual, with Husserl focusing on intuition and phenomenon (Altman, 2017; Azeri, 2011 & 2018; Berry, 2017; Bettcher, 2008; Chamberlain, 2020; Hubner, 2015; Japola, 2002; Moore, 2015; Rudolf & Marbach, 1993; Russon, 2011; Simpson, 2001).

The situation in the Islamic world is somewhat different. Here, the self is divided into essence and existence, both being derived from the Divine and the truth. It is a free spirit that derives its strength from the ultimate reality. The Self originates from the Divine but then develops into the subjective “*I*” that always recognises the Absolute. For example, Iqbal gives a genuine concept of the self, which is cosmic because it develops from the individual to the transpersonal realms (Belo, 2009; Qasim & Zeb, 2015; Taskheer, 2017; Toosi, 2020).

2.5. Ibn Arabi and the Emerging Concept of Cosmic Self from the Unity of Being

Ibn Arabi's mystical system of the Unity of Being considers essence and existence as one and united into the cosmic self. The cosmic self, as envisioned by Ibn Arabi, is achieved by effacing and transcending the individual self into unity and synthesis with a higher reality, facilitated through the use of mystical or philosophical scaffolding. The material images symbolically reflect the divine who persistently exists as essence in the individual and in the cosmic (Chittick, 1998; Chodkiewicz, 1993; Murata, 1992; Nasr, 2007; Sells, 1996).

Humanity is led into conflict by the self-other dichotomy. Ibn Arabi, however, reconciled those divisions by advocating for a dialectical relationship between religions, thereby dissolving insurmountable barriers through love, mercy and harmony. His understanding of complex metaphysical concepts was entirely structured. Humans have the potential to acquire proper knowledge through self-actualisation rather than through blind imitation. Humans also have the potential to achieve a cosmic state of the Becoming, understand the distinction between truth and falsehood and attain perfection (Ali, 2020; Chittick, retrieved August 2, 2019; Shah, 2021).

The following sections highlight different aspects of Ibn Arabi's school of the Unity of Being with special reference to the emerging concept of cosmic self:

2.5.1. Oneness and Annihilation

The Christian and Islamic mystical traditions appear to have come under the influence of Neoplatonism, especially with reference to divine creativity and the soul's ultimate return to the divine from which it came. Ibn Arabi's concept of the Unity of Being emphasises its humanistic dimensions. Actual existence belongs solely to the Divine Essence, whereas created beings possess existence only in a metaphorical sense. This realisation is enough to promote a sense of humility and mutual connection that transcends religious and doctrinal boundaries. In this respect, Ibn Arabi and Spinoza sound so similar despite hailing from different traditions and times in their proposed monism, which considers the divine and the physical world as facets of a single reality. Ibn Arabi propounded the concept of a perfect human who is defined by Mulla Sadra as the vicegerent of the divine, possessing infinite spiritual and intellectual potential. This perfect human with cosmic potential is also found within a little milder manner in Kant's ideal human who holds a rational and moral standpoint (Alsamaani, 2017; Elahi, et al., 2022; Hakim, n. d.; Kamal, 2017; Zarrabi, 2020).

Being a *Sufi* himself, Ibn Arabi's philosophy overlaps ethnic, religious and national boundaries, arguing for universal mercy without prejudice to any other belief. It transcends all forms, attributing the essence to the ultimate reality and integrating mysticism with metaphysics, emphasising the unity of creation. All creation reflects the attributes of one or the other of the Divine Names, but a Perfect Human like the Prophet embodies all the Divine Names in his person (Chodkiewicz, 1993; Derin, 2009; Nurhayati, 2020; Sa'dudin, 2020).

2.5.2. Love and Beauty

Love for the divine and humanity finds common expressions in Christianity, Islam and Hinduism. Similarly, the divine represents ultimate beauty with worldly beauty as only its manifestation. True love always leads to annihilation because the real object of all love is the divine. Since beauty inspires love, therefore, it has all the potential to result in annihilation. Ibn Arabi's treatise *The Meccan Revelations* also declares worldly beauties as mere imperfect manifestations of divine beauty. Ibn Arabi's worldview was based on an all-encompassing love, rejecting schism, fright or violence. Divine created all creation out of love. Ibn Arabi even embraced those who were his opponents and permitted those in his company, because divine love and compassion supersede exclusivity and arbitrariness. This theme finds parallels in the 19th-century Romantic poet Wordsworth, who shares philosophical and mystical inclinations with Ibn Arabi regarding considering a single life force and nature being infused with spiritual presence. Spinoza and Ibn Arabi, as discussed in the previous section, hold beauty as pivotal to understanding the divine and perfect truth, transcending temporal and spatial boundaries (Beyad & Vafa, 2021; Cavus, 2019; Chodkiewicz, 1993; Wainwright, 2020; Zarrani, n.d.).

2.5.3. Essence and Existence

The essence of a person is driven by individuality and identity, whereas existence relates to the visible attributes or acts of walking and eating. This holds a fundamental position in Ibn Arabi's system. According to him, the essence of the divine is unknowable and ineffable on account of

the veil that hides it forever, but existence belongs to Him due to self-disclosure. All creation is a mere manifestation of existence, which in reality belongs to the actual Being. Existence keeps unfolding continuously. Ibn Arabi brings two visible phenomena of dark and light for essence and existence, respectively. Every individual displays unique pre-eternal attributes that exist in divine knowledge before being manifested in the world, as reflected in the Quranic verse that states all human souls exist in the Divine before their earthly existence as vicegerents. Ibn Arabi's concept contrasts with the Aristotelian and Avicennan concepts of essence and existence, as it connects all existence back to the Divine Essence. The 21st-century Hollywood film *Inception* also mirrors the same philosophy, highlighting the nature of reality, perception and existence, showcasing life as an illusion and a dream-like experience. There was also a strong connection between the Buddhist and Ibn Arabi's concept of essence and existence, holding all things existing conditionally through divine (Izutsu, 1983; Kars & Bahrani, 2022; Lawson, 2016; Ogunnaike, 2013; Quran, 7:172; Shahzad, 2012).

2.5.4. Immaterial vs Materialism

Ibn Arabi considers both the material and immaterial self as one and the same. It shares a relation both with the divine and the worldly. The visible and physical self rests as a material self in the physical realm. The immaterial self is the true self, which emanates from the divine and displays divine attributes. The more a self gets lost in the denser physical world, the greater it loses connection with the true immaterial self. A mystic always looks for annihilation of this material self in order to win oneness with the true immaterial self. The Perfect Human serves as an *isthmus* or intercession between the material and immaterial as combined into one (Addas, 1993; Chittick, 1989).

Ibn Arabi demonstrated the Unity of Being through the application of material phenomena, such as the sun, moon, stars, earth and sky being symbols of the divine manifestation. These symbols suggest a relationship between the material existence of the

creatures and the absolute creator. It reflects that a dynamic relationship exists between the divine presence and manifestation in creation (Buana, 2017).

2.5.5. Freedom and Autonomy

Freedom and autonomy of self in Ibn Arabi's philosophy are derived from the Unity of Being. Ibn Arabi strives for a free and autonomous self in the metaphysical and spiritual sense rather than in the political one. Being mystic, he recommends self-securing freedom through surrender. Freedom is a divine attribute that is vouchsafed to humans. Individual autonomy rests not in getting disconnected from the divine but in remaining connected all the time. A cosmic self has the potential to experience gnosis by winning freedom from worldly desires and binding itself with the divine. This cosmic self, which Ibn Arabi calls the Perfect Human, serves as a channel through which all the divine commands flow towards the material realm. Ibn Arabi's self exercises tremendous potential for self-affirmation, despite considering the world an illusion, and actively engages with it. Ibn Arabi's self attains immortality and freedom through connectivity and paradoxically giving in to the will of the divine. Another example of this freedom through attaining oneness and relinquishing one's freedom is that of Rumi, whose philosophy finds parallels in American transcendentalism (Chittick, 1989; Hussain, 2021; Khan, 2021).

Sufism also suggests the experience of annihilation and subsistence as a means to attain permanence. This portrays a relationship between the seeker and the sought, where the seeker gains awareness through a transformation of identity. Everything is willed by the divine, but even then, humans are not denied free will. Moreover, humans, being manifestations of the divine, retain their independence and are responsible for their actions. Ibn Arabi's Perfect Human represents a complete realisation of divine attributes while maintaining personal responsibility that fosters a sense of moral duty. Humans often avoid accepting divine

predestination and acknowledge their role in shaping their destinies. (Bugti & Khan, 2019; Diyab, 2000; Izutsu, 1983; Yaqubi, 2020).

2.6. Kant's Transcendental Idealism and the Emerging Concept of the Cosmic Self

Kant makes the human mind so active and powerful that it constructs and shapes reality for itself. Kant does not explicitly allude to the cosmic self in his philosophy, but it can be inferred as a self that holds both the empirical or phenomenal as well as transcendental or noumenal existence. It is fundamentally composed of freedom, autonomy and rational balance. It brings harmony through the juxtaposition of the phenomenal and noumenal, which Kant symbolically represents through his famous quote from the *Critique of Practical Reason* about the heaven above and the moral law within. Kantian sublime also awakens the cosmic self in humans when they confront anything that defies normal human capacities through its vastness and grandeur. On such occasions, reason asserts its superiority, whereas the imagination fails to comprehend. Thus cosmic self is the one that can think beyond and assert its superiority despite being small and insignificant (Allison, 2004; Crowther, 1993; Guyer, 2006; Kant, 1997; Scruton, 2001; Stillinger, 1971).

Kant's view of the self is dualistic. His empirical self is subject to the inner sense perceptions, and the transcendental self is dependent on apperception that serves to organise experience. The self synthesises actively but receives inner perceptions passively. This self is consciousness, possesses knowledge and holds an appearance while at the same time unifying all the experiences. Despite human cognition being limited to the phenomena Kantian self is intrinsically related to the noumenal self. Thus, it lives in appearances in the physical realm but transcends that for the ineffably noumenal realm. On the contrary, Descartes rejects the inner duality of the self. In Cartesian terms self is a unified and fixed thinking substance. The contemporary philosophers find it difficult to come to an agreement about Kantian noumena and phenomena as either being two different dimensions of the same entity or two independent

entities. It gets further complicated when the self as a thing-in-itself is considered as unknowable, but at the same time self-as-it-appears is knowable. Notwithstanding all these conflicts self is a complex reality with dual aspects. The Kantian self structures experience. It develops a link between the noumenal and phenomenal realism. It is through the sublime that the self transcends limitations and realises its true potential. This process can be compared with Nietzschean notion of becoming, where creativity takes place through the Dionysian principle of chaos, but in the case of Kant, it takes place through the Apollonian order of reason and morality. Self thus undergoes a constant development through synthesis of unity and fragmentation, reason and feeling, appearance and transcendence (Kitcher, 2021; Bonaccini, 1998; Dietmar, 2021; Kant, 1997; Kaplama, 2016; Kreines, n.d.; Marshall, 2013).

The following sections highlight different aspects of Kant's philosophy of transcendental idealism with special reference to the emerging concept of cosmic self:

2.6.1. Oneness and Annihilation

In *Sufi* literature, self-annihilation is extolled as a channel to achieve oneness with the divine. Being proponents of self-annihilation, the *Sufis* reject racial boundaries, transcending social and religious barriers. Thus, it looks for unity in diversity. In the Islamic tradition, Rumi recounts the experiences of attaining oneness through negation and dissolution of the self. In modern times, this can be paralleled with most of the poets of the Romantic period. However, Kant organises the self into a rational and autonomous capacity with moral agency. Despite acknowledging the self being not only transcendental but also empirical and pragmatic, Kant makes the self independent within a system of moral and rational laws. Oneness for Kant is not in the spiritual or the mystical sense but in the unity of consciousness and the synthesis between reason and nature. Although the effect of the sublime leads to moral and aesthetic annihilation yet he rejects annihilation of the self in the ontological or mystical sense. Freedom does not rest in surrender but in the use of rational will. *Sufism* and Kantian philosophy agree on

achieving higher unity through transcendence. In mysticism, self-dissolution results in oneness, but in the transcendental idealism of Kant, it is achieved through the unity of reason and the pursuit of moral law. Rumi's philosophy sounds similar to Kantian unification of the manifold. Despite rejecting the mystical notion of annihilation, Kant holds the self as finite but free-moving towards an ideal moral community. Both the Kantian and mystical philosophies thus make the self as overpowering its identity either through reason or through mystical love to attain a greater harmony (Beyad & Vafa, 2021; Frierson, 2013; Green, 2006; Insole, 2020; Kant, 1997, 1998, 2000).

2.6.2. Love and Beauty

There is a strong connection in love, self and beauty with emphasis on emotion and imagination in Romanticism as a response to the rationalism of the Enlightenment. Beauty was acknowledged as a medium to the spiritual and transcendent experience towards the infinite. German Romantics like Schlegel and Schelling made beauty a universal truth that helped gain a connection to the infinite. Similarly, the Romantics made love an ideal and transcendent experience that linked aesthetics with moral influence. Kant, however, adapts a more critical approach towards love and its impact upon the self. Having been generated in the faculties of understanding and imagination, aesthetic judgment is accepted universally. Love is either a practical being driven by duty and respect or a pathological being directed towards sensory pleasure. A beautiful object attracts because of its form and balance, but an object carrying the sublime generates awe and moral uprightness. The Kantian concept of the self is active agent that gives meaning to the world through rational reflection and moral autonomy. However, Kant deviates from the Romantics by considering respect, not love, as the basis of ethical relationships. Despite moving from different perspectives, the Romantics as well as Kant elevate the self through experiences of love and beauty. Romanticism extols an intuitive and emotional self by bringing down barriers between the physical and spiritual worlds through the

sublime and love. Kant lets these experiences filter through a rational and moral medium. The Kantian self applies aesthetic judgment as a means of interpretation by bringing together emotion and cognition. The self then transcends the merely empirical. Thus, both Romantics and Kant consider beauty as a means towards a higher understanding of the self and world through emotions and through reflection, respectively (Forster & Steiner, 2020; Kant, 1996, 2000, 2011, 2012; Rinne, 2018; Rockmore, 2013).

2.6.3. Essence and Existence

Philosophers in the Classical tradition generally label existence as an attribute of essence. This becomes obvious in the case of the theological and rationalist philosophies. Essence and existence are concentrated into the Divine essence. Existence is considered synonymous in attributes with the concept of a being. This question of essence and existence was commonly held by both the Eastern and Western traditions. Even Eastern mysticism and American Transcendentalism viewed the self as a manifestation of the divine, like Emerson, Thoreau and Whitman, who treated existence as grounded in essence. As a religious experience, transcendence is seen as an encounter with divine reality that affirms the essential self. On the contrary, Kant, being a dualist, separates essence from existence and proposes that existence is not a predicate. It is not derivable from any essence, may it be divine because it must be verified empirically, not deduced *a priori*. This concept is influenced by the Kantian dualism where reality is either phenomena (anything that appears and is knowable) or noumena (thing-in-itself or unknowable). So is the self, which is divided between the empirical self (conditioned and observable) and the transcendental self (the necessary condition for experience but not directly knowable). Sometimes the mind suffers from transcendental illusion when it tries to overreach and misconstrue concepts of reason for metaphysical realities. According to Kant, essence and existence will always remain distinct, with any claim of having attained ontological unity with the divine as completely preposterous and baseless.

Although Kant is a dualist yet his concept of transcendental freedom reconciles essence and existence through moral autonomy. The self may have restrictions epistemologically, but it is morally free and self-legislating, which Kant places in his rational faculties instead of in mystical intuition like the Romantics. Hegel, immediately after Kant, rejected his dualism and rather proposed a dialectical unity between thought and being. Despite Kant's rejection of metaphysical claims regarding essence, when he affirms moral agency he acknowledges the existence of an autonomous and rational self which serves as a guide towards what is and what ought to be (Du Toit, 2011; Grier, 2001; Kant, 1997/1998/ 2012; Najmabadi et al., 2020; Stang, 2015; Sutanto, 2017).

2.6.4. Material vs Immaterial

Traditionally, the self is conceived in material terms. It carries a physical existence like a body, experiences pain and pleasure in a psychological sense and displays an observable behaviour. Self is thus wrapped in time and space, registering perceptions and sensory experiences. In this sense, the self is a biological mechanism and phenomenal awareness. Kant, too, considers the empirical self (or inner sense) as linked to mental and psychological states experienced by the body. Such a self experiencing sensory perceptions from the external world cannot be a single entity but fragmented like manifold impressions from the outside. As opposed to this, Kant proposes a self that is transcendental, immaterial, unified, and *a priori*, making experience possible within itself, such as "I think." Being a transcendental self, it is immaterial in the noumenal realm and is governed by the rational moral law that structures experiences. Despite drawing distinct boundaries between the material and the immaterial self, Kant does not segregate them entirely on ethical and moral grounds. For Kant, the material self is the manifestation of the immaterial self in the world of appearance. The immaterial self unifies and structures the fragmented material self. Kant thus develops this connection between the material and immaterial by giving freedom and moral autonomy to the immaterial self, but

accepting the material self being surrounded by social existence. Kant thus makes a complete human through this duality of the material and immaterial (Allison, 2004; Kant, 1996, 1998).

2.6.5. Freedom and Autonomy

In the Kantian moral system, freedom is associated with moral autonomy. True freedom is not to choose arbitrarily but to be independent in legislating moral law out of free will. It is responsible for promoting harmony and balance in the world if humans subject themselves to the moral statutes. Freedom is thus the second name for rational self-governance. Kant, though, hesitates in defining freedom as a single overarching concept. For him, freedom can be divided into different types such as logical, practical, transcendental and freedom of choice. Each plays different roles peculiar to itself. Autonomy is thus not as simple as generally understood. The concept of logical freedom rejects determinism in cognition; practical freedom is responsible for rational moral thinking; transcendental freedom drives action beyond causal relation (a metaphysical necessity for moral responsibility), and freedom of choice guards against heteronomy to be driven by inclinations rather than duty. Moral responsibility is supervised by transcendental freedom, whereas practical freedom drives autonomous action. Ultimately, Kant recommends freedom that is holistic, rational, self-legislating and accountable. In the Kantian republic human self is autonomous not because it is independent but because it is bound by a universal moral law (Fricke, 2005; Insole, 2020; Kant, 1997, 1998, 2000).

2.7. Thematic Development of the Self in the Comparative Studies on Keats and Khan

Romanticism is a cross-cultural and cross-linguistic movement, as evidenced by a comparative study between the 9th-century Chinese poet Li He and Keats (Yuan, 1996). A comparative analysis, which triangulates data to follow Ficino's and Hegel's theories of recognition, concludes that the poetry of the Ottoman court poets and Keats portrays a master-slave relationship between the lover and the beloved (Ozkan, 2021). Applying Zpetenek's model, which builds upon Morgan's and Gafni's theories of the emerging evolutionary self, Fatima

(2011) identifies similar mystical strains in the 16th-century Punjabi poet Shah Hussain and Keats.

Comparative studies on Keats and other Western poets also suggest a close link between them. For instance, the self emerges to be a place of Nietzsche's conflicting fictions in the poetry of Keats and Shelley (Sandy, 1998). Textual analysis reveals that both Coleridge and Keats are idealists whose becoming occurs through continuous transformation and self-development, as informed by the philosophies of Schlegel and Hegel (Ngiewih, 2021). Romantic poets such as Byron, Shelley and Keats use poetry as a medium for cultivating self-awareness and balancing their aspirations and ambitions (Westwood, 2017). A poet's imagery also reflects attitude towards life, as Keats appears through his imagery as a poet in search of peace, yet accepting the realities of life, living in the same world (Doyle, 2021). Coleridge, Keats and Shelley are Habermasian and Davidsonian who believe truth to be more absolute than the ideal. Another comparative study, applying Northrop Frye's Anagogic Theory, concludes that Coleridge, Keats and Shelley are mystics, as they attain oneness with the divine through self-annihilation (Beyad & Vafa, 2021). Tyner (2022) explores the iconoclastic and iconophilic concepts of poetry and concludes Keats, Shelley and Eliot are apophatic (related to negative theology, what God is not), whose idea of truth does not carry any image.

A comparative study by Rehman and Ahmad (2016) concludes that Wordsworth and Khan, though belonging to different countries and times, share similar effects, including a love of harmony and empathetic feelings for the sufferings of humanity, which are characteristics of pantheism. An intertextual study of Coleridge and Keats concludes that both poets are bound by linguistic, social and cultural norms, despite variations in geographical location and time (Shah, 2021). Another comparative study, applying Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis model, between Emily Dickinson and Khan, concludes that both view death not as the end of life (Mehnaz & Durrani, 2022).

A comparative study on Keats and Khan reveals many similarities between the two, including their struggles in life, love for nature and beauty and a musicality that runs through their poetry, with minor differences by characterising Keats as sensuous, while Khan as straightforward (Bacha, 2010). Another study from a postcolonial perspective concludes that Eastern literature is as rich as Western literature, and literary figures like Keats and Khan explore similar themes of beauty, love and nature, despite cultural and temporal barriers between them (Khan & Arshad, 2020). A comparative study by Khan (2025) examines the similarities in Keats's and Khan's poetry, using visual imagery to transcend and escape the physical world, thereby engaging with the philosophical themes. Keats's imagery, however, romanticises eternity in beauty but examines the transitoriness of life within the mystic tradition.

2.8. Keats's Poetic Assertion of the Phenomenal World

Poetry holds a healing power. It resolves inner conflicts and promotes a sense of peace in the physical world. There are binary divisions in his poetry, particularly about themes such as pleasure and pain, life and death, permanence and impermanence. Keats lived in the physical or phenomenal world, which was fundamental to him. He found beauty in the ugliness, pleasure in pain and permanence in transitoriness, much like his character Psyche. The Platonic idealism, which posits that reality is twice removed, was unacceptable to him, and instead, he turned towards the actual realities of life (Ahad, 2020; Dash, 2014; Haque & Rahman, 2013; Nicholas, 2019; Roberts, 1993; Sarkar & Munshi, 2019).

Keats's poetry expresses the complexities of life. He did not reject life with all its beauties, pleasures and pains, but accepted them as the primary foundation for poetic expression. Keats's poetry is the expression of a collective consciousness that denies the Cartesian or Lacanian mind-body separation (Gunday, 2022; Hore, 2022; Hussain, 2022; Khan et al., 2023; LO, 2022; Ngiewih, 2021; Stroe, 2021).

2.8.1. Transformation and Temporality in Keats

Keats considered beauty as the most truthful attribute of the self; therefore, the self is an inseparable dimension that reveals the aesthetic experience. Beauty helps the self gain access to the infinite. It is not limited to a fixed station but constantly faces aesthetic experiences. This yearning for the infinite leads the self to be dissolved in nature, art and the cosmos as a means of transcending the mundane. Keats cannot shut himself off from the external world and its social upheavals, including the political developments of his time. However, he acknowledges the significance of inner perceptions in exploring the mysteries of the supra-sensory realm. Thus, he removes the barriers between the individual self and the cosmos. The self that Keats develops is paradoxically fluid, with associations that spanned over the physical and metaphysical realms. The self undergoes constant flux, highlighting its transitoriness and temporality. This simultaneous interconnectivity of the self with death and beauty develops into a metaphysical state of the self that achieves union with aesthetic and cosmic realities (Abrams, 1971; Motion, 1997; Shaw, 2006; Vendler, 1983; Watson et al., 2014).

2.8.2. Keats's Transcendental Imagination and Aesthetic Self

The Romantic poets exalted imagination to the level of a creative and divine faculty, enabling the self to transcend time and space. For instance, Coleridge constructed the secondary imagination as a building block upon the primary, always working with perceptual reality as it exists. Keats's imagination accepted self-effacement but rejected self-assertion, and so remained in a state of suspension between finitude and the infinite. Keats's poetry acknowledged the limitations of the human self and sought to gain access to the sublime and cosmically eternal. His negative capability, characterised by a state of being in uncertainties, mysteries and doubts without reaching after fact and reason, supported his trust in the art and poetry to help him transcend from the known to the unknown. Keats's selfhood thus rested upon annihilation and negation rather than affirmation. Consequently, he dissolved into a

masterpiece of art, such as the “Ode on a Grecian Urn,” in an attempt to attain eternity. Keats was a mystic in his poetry. His aesthetic self reconciled with its limitations despite access to the infinite. Connection with beauty thus requires achieving self-annihilation. This search for self is also reflected in comparative literature, which focuses on discovering the true self in marginal literature, making it significant to compare their positions within world literature. Comparative studies have been undertaken in the works of Keats and Eastern poets, such as Li He, whose works reveal cross-cultural, cross-linguistic and thematic affinities (Abrams, 1953; Bate, 1963; Coleridge, 1817; Keats, 1817; Ozkan, 2021; Vendler, 1983; Yuan, 1996).

A comparison between 16th-century Punjabi poet Shah Hussain and Keats reveals that both share the concept of an evolving and emergent self in their poetry. Comparative studies suggest that the affinity between Keats and Shelley also extends to the self as a site of conflicting fictions within the philosophical perspective of Nietzsche. There is also evidence that Coleridge and Keats are regarded as idealists whose Becoming occurs through continuous transformation and self-development, influenced by the philosophies of Schlegel and Hegel. Byron, Shelley and Keats used poetry as a medium for self-consciousness, balancing aspirations and ambitions. The poet’s attitude towards life is disclosed through imagery. Keats’s imagery reveals that he sought peace but also accepted the realities of life. Philosophically, Coleridge, Keats and Shelley are associated with Habermasian and Davidsonian perspectives, which hold that truth is more absolute than the ideal. As far as the iconoclastic and iconophilic concepts of poetry are concerned, Keats, Shelley and Eliot are apophatic whose idea of truth lacks any image (Beyad & Vafa, 2021; Doyle, 2021; Fatima, 2011; Ngiewih, 2021; Sandy, 1998; Tyner, 2022; Westwood, 2017).

2.8.3. Creativity and Imagination in Keats’s Poetry

Keats blended imagination and the creative self with a greater focus on nature, mysticism and self-discovery. In Keats’s idea of life, nature is a source of inspiration that explores the dualities

of existence and transforms reality through emotion and inspiration. Keats's "Ode to a Nightingale," and Shelley's "To a Skylark," symbolise the bird with natural beauty, leading to delight, optimism and transcendence. For Keats, poetry was both a passive reflection and an active force that transformed reality, making the self an essential source of meaning and transcendence. Keats worshipped beauty and reinforced his Romantic ideal of imagination as a means of self-expression. His poetry embodied imagination as a boundless journey, where creativity merged the self and the world, transcending moral, political or social functions. His poetry demonstrated the creative self as dissolved into beauty, making art an end in itself rather than a means to some external purpose (Antunes, 1976; Abrams, 1953; AL-Rifaie, 2021; Callan, 1960; Gunday, 2022; Ibrahim, 2020).

2.8.4. Quest for Wholeness in Keats

Keats's poetry displayed a sense of oneness through philosophical and mystical themes. His poetry portrayed a journey within the self for achieving self-realisation and collective consciousness. Keats demonstrated a living experience by offering an introspective yet sensory engagement with existence. In the Jungian perspective, Keats's poetry fosters harmony and synthesis between conscious and unconscious elements, following a path similar to mysticism that unites the finite self with the infinite. The psychological reading from a Jungian perspective reflects Keats's poetry as navigating the human consciousness. Negative Capability enabled Keats to reconcile the tension between aesthetics and ethics. Negative Capability is an exercise in mysticism that embraces uncertainty and contradictions through the synthesis of the opposing elements. Keats's "Endymion" reflects the mystical tradition of sacrificing individuality for a greater unity. Endymion's mystical designs are characterised by a melancholic nature that yearns for the ineffably infinite. Keats's poetry demonstrated a mystical quest for oneness that dissolved dualities between the self and the other, thought and

feeling, reason and emotion (Albayrak, 2022; Bari, 2012; Khan et al., 2020; Nazir & Hasan, 2019; Russell, 1945; Syeda, 2011).

2.8.5. Exploring Contradictory Relationships in Keats's Poetry

Keats explored answers to philosophical and existential questions through the depiction of themes related to love and beauty. His concept of love was not materialistic, as in the contemporary era. He saw a universal force in it through the portrayal of longing and passion. It was not static or eternal but transitory and associated with life, centred upon human longing, fulfilment and even inevitable loss. This made Keats's poetry a powerful and complex force, as it explored the contradictory relationship between pain, imagination, beauty and self-discovery. Moreover, love is interwoven with imagination, which helps us escape from harsh realities. Both Keats and Khan were lovers of beauty and nature, acknowledging its transient but eternal attributes. Keats's aestheticism influenced perceptions of love, drawing on Platonic and Kantian perspectives. Love is a means of understanding reality through beauty. Keats's "Ode on a Grecian Urn" focuses upon the theme of eternal beauty and truth. Beauty is strictly personal because it is constructed by the mind. Keats's poetry treated love and beauty as intertwined with imagination, truth and eternity, making it a central element of his poetic philosophy (Ahmad et al., n.d.; Asiatidou, 2020; Estevez, 2019; Gashti, 2020; Haque & Rahman, 2013; Jiang & Dong, n.d.; Naqi et al, 2017; Ozkan, 2021; Song, 2019; Vendler, 1983).

2.8.6. Dualities of Life in Keats's Poetry

Keats highlighted the dualities of life through the juxtaposition of imagination and reality, beauty and mortality, pain and pleasure. It is art and human experience that are instrumental in Keats's unveiling a deeper understanding of life and its permanence or impermanence. This duality is reflected in the depiction of the relationship between essence and existence, as well as in his oscillation to embrace reality or to escape to the world of beauty and imagination. However, he ultimately reconciled with accepting the wholeness of life. Keats's use of

mythology was aimed at seeking order and wholeness, a trait he derived from Hellenistic philosophy. He proceeded to unearth reality with the help of myth, art and beauty to establish a link between the past and the present. Despite his acceptance of life's impermanence, he stopped short of offering any solution. He presented an interplay of paradoxes, irony and acceptance triggered by his personal experiences of suffering and loss. Keats's poetry thus accentuates the themes of nothingness, transformation, duality and self-recognition. Keats willingly embraced uncertainty, suffering and change as integral parts of human existence. Existence was perceived as a process rather than a fixed state, where nothingness, transformation and paradoxical dualities shaped the human experience (Al-Abbood, 2015; Al-Jumaili, 2020; Guven & Erdogan, 2021; Mukherjee, 2021; Naqi et al., 2017; Nicholls, 2019; Nijibayashi, 2022; Sengupta, n.d.; Teke, 2006; Westwood, 2017; White, 2010).

2.8.7. Keats's Inclination towards a Life of Sensations

The sensory and material world provided Keats with the themes that underscored his belief in dualism and the transitory nature of existence. His poetry bridged the gap between empirical realism and imaginative transcendence, positioning him among the Romantic dualists and Hellenic sensualists. This interest in sensory experiences, as well as the auditory and pictorial projection of images to express mortality and beauty, was manifested through his odes. Despite his leaning towards empirical idealism, Keats's poetry was a precursor to the Romantic dualism, characterised by the coexistence of beauty and mortality. Negative capability helped in accepting this dualism. Romantic poetry is generally defined by its sensuality. Keats sought the immaterial through escape from the material world and through aligning aesthetic, philosophical and spiritual experiences with the material world. Keats, however, could not escape the material, cultural, spiritual and intellectual thought of his time. He laid down his preferences for material existence himself through a longing for a life of sensation rather than of abstract contemplation. He equally emphasised a need to balance earthly pleasures and pains

with a more profound spiritual yearning. His poetry also showed a movement from the sensory experiences towards supra-sensory realms, making his poetry both grounded in reality and the metaphysical. That reflected his artistic quest for life's paradoxes (Alsaeed, n.d.; Cavell, 1988; Dash, 2014; Doyle, 2021; Fermanis, 2009; Hussain, 2022; Lo, 2023; Paul, 2022; Sha, 2014; Teke, 2021; Zheng, 2014).

2.8.8. Desire for Rebellion and Autonomy

Autonomy, rebellion, transformation and longing are defining characteristics of the Romantic poets. Being labelled as a Cockney himself, Keats, like Brontë, raised a rebellion against religious and social persecution, making literature a means of expressing personal and intellectual autonomy. This rebellion and longing to control are symbolically represented by the act of gaze in "Lamia," through enchantment. Keats was a strong proponent of change and reform. He always longed to maintain a balance between an optimistic outlook on transformation and reconciliation. Keats often employed phallic symbols in his poetry that explored themes of freedom, desire and power. Freedom was depicted as a dynamically evolving process, rather than being fixed to one spot. Sometimes, he challenges social norms through sexual innuendos that reflect his freedom. Freedom by escape, as reflected through the image of a bower, also demonstrates a connotative sense of freedom, showing escape into nature (Aryan, n.d.; Chen, 2019; Karadas, 2020; Kitson, 2008; Marks, 2022; Sandy, 1998; Seffers, 1993; Yuan, 1996).

2.9. Thematically Emerging Self in Khan's Poetry

Mystical themes were common in Pashto poetry, particularly during the Mughal era, when the Pashto-speaking regions of India were referred to as Khorasan. The work of Bayazid, titled *Khair-ul-Bayan*, written during that time, advocated for the Unity of Being as pioneered by Ibn Arabi. Darveeza criticised his teachings. These mystical themes also echo in Khan, whose intrinsically rebellious nature employed dissolution as a means to explore higher truths by

combining paradoxes with modernist scepticism. He considered the human self as a manifestation of the divine self. Khan was a philosopher who explored time through various connotations, including impermanence and the concept of being. Following no particular mystical ideology, he explored the meanings of actual existence and the relationship with the divine. Khan, like Plato, held the human soul to be immortal and a part of duality that links humanity and love to the immortal soul. His themes included death and existentialism, but he was not a pessimist or nihilist and instead accepted the pleasures of life (Ahmed et al., 2021; Awan & Ali, 2014; Dinakhel & Bakhshali, 2022; Farhad, 2011; Munir, 2018; Omid, 2022; Safa & Sahand, 2022; Sardaraz & Nusrat, 2019; Shah, 2020; Yaqubi, 2020; Zakir & Ramzan, 2022).

As stated earlier, mystical and ascetic traditions had caught the attention of Khan, who focused on the unity of being and rejected religious institutions and dogmatic ideologies. His portrayal of the self was based on both autonomy and subordination, which created a paradoxical state between the individual and the transcendent self. Wordsworth and Khan, despite having contrasting temporal and spatial conditions, shared a pantheism, love of harmony and empathy for humanity's sufferings. Both poets were associated with a literary movement that highlighted social and cultural norms, despite variations in their locations and periods. Dickinson and Khan both found death as a source of relief, but Khan found mystery as a source of solace and comfort for himself (Farid, 2008; Mehnaz & Durrani, 2022; Rehman & Ahmad, 2016; Shah, 2021).

2.9.1. Mystical Strains in Khan's Poetry

Philosophies of existentialism and *Sufism* were blended in Khan's poetry, making pleasure and pain inseparable dimensions of life. Khan denied any nihilistic approach towards life and instead established a spiritual connection with the divine while celebrating the pleasures of life. His poetry displays a mystical subsistence in the divine, where the soul, despite remaining

aware of physical existence, becomes part of the divine. The metaphysical dimension has been present in the Pashto poetry since the Mughal era. Notable *Sufi* traditions, such as the Chishti, Qadri, Naqshbandi and Roshania, found their place in Pashto literature that contributed to its development through the promotion of self-reflection, discipline and mystical expression. Khan shared many characteristics of mystical strains even with the English poets like Wordsworth and Keats. Wordsworth and Khan displayed pantheism in their poetry, finding the divine in every blade of grass. This conviction of the divine, being manifest in nature and beauty, made Khan a *Sufi* who found in nature not only beauty but also a source of spiritual awakening and environmental consciousness. Another Romantic poet, Coleridge, also had an affinity with Khan. Coleridge's "Kubla Khan" and Khan's "My Palace" are mystical poems that evoke dream-like experiences. Khan was more humanistic, unlike Coleridge, who focused on the divine, human emotions and the beauty of existence. Khan thus gave a unique and personal touch to mysticism through his peculiar handling of love, fate and beauty (Ahmed et al., 2021; Iqbal, 2022; Omid, 2022; Rehman & Ahmad, 2016; Safa & Sahand, 2022; Shah & Gul, 2021).

Khan repudiated materialist tendencies and accepted the *Sufi* ideal of seeking a higher spiritual truth. He also shared his concept of paradise, which emphasises beauty, creativity and the human experience as divine. Khan emphasised the creation of a world of imagination more in alignment with the *Sufi* ideals, where the seeker transcends worldly concerns to attain spiritual truth. Khan was closely linked to Rumi and Hafiz because, like them, he also emphasised the spiritual journey that passes through hardships (Akbar, 2016, 1975; Nabil, n.d.).

2.9.2. Aesthetic Love and Universal Connection

Khan admired beauty and nature as sources of inspiration and transcendence. His poetic compositions blend aesthetic and mystical perspectives on love and beauty. Love and beauty,

as reflected through images such as flowers, birds, landscapes and colours, often inspire a sense of mystical connection between the self and the universe. These elements of beauty and art helped him secure escape and transcendence from the painful realities of life. Khan highlighted the dual dimensions of beauty and love that resonated with the *Sufi* notion of harmony between worldly and spiritual life. Thus, his concept of love and beauty was both existential and mystical, which seemed to have been influenced by *Sufism* and its understanding of rigid doctrinaires. Khan's unconditional love for the divine was deeply rooted in Ibn Arabi's concept of the Unity of Being. Khan's approach to beauty parallels the Kantian sublime as well, making beauty a subjective and existential experience of self-realisation. Khan's poetry offers a bridge between the Eastern and Western philosophical traditions. Instead of being carried away by physical aesthetics, he focuses on the spiritual aspect of love, beauty and life. Khan's philosophy of life was a collage of Iqbal's visionary ideals, Khayyam's existential musings and Keats's Romantic love for beauty and imagination. It underwent phases of evolution from childhood experiences to the life spent in the West, and then ultimately came under Tagore's influence. One of his poetic compilations, *Palwashey*, reflects this love for the divine as a central and profoundly emotional theme (Babar, 2005; Bacha, 2010; Hanif, 2022; Raj Wali, 2013; Zubair, 2019).

2.9.3. The Paradox of Death in Khan's Poetry

While analysing the essence-existence duality in Khan's and Dickinson's poetry, death stands out as an inseparable reality highlighted through numerous symbols. Both Dickinson and Khan acknowledged the paradoxical nature of death, recognising it as transformative and transcendent, yet a destructive reality. These themes were closely interwoven into his concept of life and death, carrying deeper meanings and associations with the Pashtun culture. Drawing on Plato's theory, he also posits that the soul is immortal, which transcends material existence. Khan's acceptance of existence on the dual planes is reflected through his juxtaposition of

human life with the permanence of the soul and through his acceptance of physical experience. He criticises material attachments but favours a mystical approach where the soul journeys towards beauty and truth (Sardaraz & Nusrat, 2019).

2.9.4. Realistic and Mystical Perspective on Existence in Khan's Poetry

Khan's poetry explores the philosophical and ethical dichotomy of good and evil through a lens of realism, materiality and immateriality. Khan's approach to human nature was grounded in realism, encompassing various ethical categories, including meta-ethics, normative ethics and applied ethics. His poems portray contrasts, emphasising the coexistence of opposites, and align with the existentialist and *Sufi* traditions. Khan interpreted materialism as a source of blind dogmatism, evil, power struggles and societal corruption. Good and evil are represented as fluctuating and evolving from a traditional religious morality into a humanistic and mystical perspective. Khan countered the commonly held moral binaries by accepting both a realist and mystical perspective for understanding the material and immaterial. He blends realism and mysticism with the desire to transcend the material world for the immaterial, which symbolises freedom, creativity and peace. His poetry often aligns with the *Sufi* framework by bringing a balance between beauty and dreams (Ali et al., 2023).

2.9.5. Rooted in Nationalist Culture

Khan's poetry reflects a yearning for freedom. For instance, his free verse showcases his commitment to intellectual and artistic freedom. Being representatives of dogma and pedantry, Khan openly criticises religious clerics. Khan extolled liberty at every level, from the artistic to the ideological and encouraged raising questions. He projects himself as an anti-colonialist and anti-imperialist. Khan takes pride in the Oriental literature, which he considers as universal and profound as any other literature in the world. His poetry presents a universality that transcends geographical boundaries. He would draw inspiration from the traditional Pashtun

culture of resistance towards any form of subjugation and blind obedience (Awan & Ali, 2014; Khan, 2020; Sultana, 2021).

2.10. Poetry as a Source of Articulating the Metaphysics of the Self

Poetry, as an art form, plays a pivotal role in understanding oneself and one's existential state. Heidegger emphasised the role of poetry as a metaphysical inquiry that unveils the mystery of the self or being. Poetry utilises language to comprehend the self and its existential state by shaping one's ontology. Poets like Holderlin and Rilke elevated the self from the temporal and spatial to the transcendental by rendering it instrumental in connecting the individual with the cosmos. This process was facilitated by the poetry's ability to use language for understanding the self and its existential state, inspiring a deep appreciation for the art form (Derrida, 1992; Gadamer, 1989; Heidegger, 1971).

It is the language that enables both poetry and philosophy to express transcendental, metaphysical and existential questions. Philosophers approach answering existential inquiries about the self through philosophical propositions, while poets adopt a subjective and intuitive path. Metaphysical realities are conveyed through the figurative tools of paradox and symbolism in poetry and philosophy. Despite being a follower of the Platonic school, Plotinus disagreed with Plato's criticism of poetry as responsible for distorting the natural truth and therefore charging poets with banishment. The Romantic poets equated the quest for self with pilgrimage, focusing on divine love. This concept of poetry and the quest for the self as a pilgrimage within oneself is also reiterated by Schimmel, concerning Rumi and Hafiz. Romantic poetry also explored metaphysical themes, thereby setting the self free from the constraints of time and space to gain access to the infinite through intuition. Like the Romantic poets, some notable philosophers, such as Nietzsche, Heidegger and Sartre, also considered poetry as an engagement with metaphysical questions about the self constructed by language

(Abrams, 1971; Derrida, 1992; Hadot, 1995; Heidegger, 1971; Republic, Book X; Schimmel, 1975).

2.11. Key Findings

The chapter undertook a thorough analysis of the previous literature on various dimensions of the self, with particular emphasis on the philosophical frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant as well as of Keats's and Khan's poetry. The following points emerged:

- Considerable scholarship on Keats and Khan touches on the self; however, it is treated as part of a subjective element that gives imaginative and emotional expression rather than conducting a focused philosophical or literary inquiry into the concept of selfhood as a central theme with cosmic significance.
- As is obvious from the previous literature, this study fills the gap by undertaking research on the self as a conceptual core of inquiry through a structured theory about its cosmic significance in the philosophical and mystical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.
- Both the Eastern and Western mystical and philosophical traditions have developed an interest in exploring the self and its cosmic connection. It is either a dual entity with distinctly separate material and immaterial dimensions or a single entity with the same essence that encompasses both the material and immaterial aspects.
- It appears that Keats and Khan do not display a consistently regular approach towards self but envision a self that is fluid and oscillating between the physical and spiritual.
- Kant's transcendental idealism and Ibn Arabi's *Wahdat al-Wujud* (Unity of Being) operate in entirely distinct perspectives. Sometimes these two frameworks appear complementary to each other in acknowledging how the self perceives, constructs, and structures a cosmos of its own.

- Love, beauty and aesthetic experience are means to transcendence between the material and the immaterial, essence and existence. Impermanence is an inseparable aspect of pleasure and pain.
- Scholarship on Keats highlights his affinity with Kantian aesthetics and the sublime, but he largely remains underexplored in a framework that combines both the *Akbarian* and Kantian perspectives.
- Khan fuses mystical and philosophical themes in his poetry. He also questions the rigid structures of materialism and parochial authority obstructing the realisation of a cosmic self.
- Scholarship on Ibn Arabi's influence on poetry suggests that his thought profoundly shaped mystical poetry; however, its direct relevance to Romantic poetry, as well as to Keats and Khan, has remained largely unexplored, particularly in terms of the self and its cosmic significance.
- Kant's philosophy emphasises on construction of the self through perception and imagination that rests in the ineffable noumenal world, along with beauty and the sublime.
- While existing cross-cultural literary studies connect Wordsworth to Rumi or Shelley to Eastern mysticism, the focus of this research is on the underexplored Keats's and Khan's poetry in the mystical and philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.

2.12. Conclusion

The literature review highlighted an interdisciplinary nature to this study. It reflected how Keats's and Khan's poetic vision of the cosmic self engages with mystical and philosophical perspectives. The overview of the existing scholarship also revealed a gap in the research on selfhood in Keats's and Khan's poetry, particularly viewed from the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. By establishing literary, mystical, philosophical and comparative

foundations of this study in the light of previous work, this study now proceeds to lay down the theoretical and methodological underpinnings of this research.

CHAPTER THREE

Theoretical and Methodological Paradigm

You are not other than the universe, nor is the universe other than you (Chittick, 1989, p. 79).

Two things fill the mind with ever-new and increasing admiration and awe, the more often and the more steadily we reflect upon them: the starry heavens above me and the moral law within me (Kant, 1788/2015, p. 129).

3.1. Introduction

Having reviewed the literature, this chapter outlines the theoretical and methodological framework for exploring the concept of the cosmic self in the poetic works of Keats and Khan. It integrates some common aspects of Ibn Arabi's mystical framework with Kant's transcendental idealism in a comparative approach to analyse and interpret selfhood and its cosmic association in Keats's and Khan's poetry. This chapter approaches the subject under two main headings:

- Theoretical foundation for the conceptualisation of the research
- Methodological Framework, which covers the research design and method for data analysis.

3.2. Theoretical Foundation and Its Justification

This study operates in a comparative philosophical framework. It combines Ibn Arabi's mystical philosophy of Unity of Being and the transcendental idealism of Kant to explore the construction of the cosmic self. Despite operating in and basing their philosophical thoughts on entirely different traditions of the East and the West, Ibn Arabi and Kant often develop supporting insights into different forms of reality with their transcendental and cosmic dimensions related to the selfhood, such as freedom and autonomy, love and beauty, essence and existence, material and immaterial, oneness and annihilation. Ibn Arabi's Unity of Being makes all existence a manifestation of the Divine essence, which demands self-annihilation to

realise its true potential (Chittick, 1989; Corbin, 2013). On the other hand, Kant, despite having been groomed in a pietist environment by his mother, is secular and rationalist, proposing a self that exists both as a noumenal self and a phenomenal self, separately looking for moral autonomy (Kant, 1788/1996; Allison, 1990). Ibn Arabi, by his mystical inclination and Kant, by his philosophical propensity, acknowledge the limits of rational knowledge. They believe in a higher and noumenal (immaterial) reality that can be accessed only through a mystical experience (Ibn Arabi) or through transcendental reasoning (Kant). Combining Ibn Arabi's metaphysical and Kant's rational framework, based on imagination and moral ideals respectively, helps explore comprehensively the dual-aspect model of the self from the visibly physical (phenomenal) and invisibly spiritual (noumenal) dimensions. The cosmic self is operationalised through the aspects of freedom, love, beauty, and existence, etc, for ontological and epistemological inquiry into Keats's and Khan's poetry. This pluralistic exploration through integration of the two divergent frameworks accepts the self as a suitable site of both the physical and spiritual inquiry (Coates, 2005; Dagli, 2016).

The study is grounded in Ibn Arabi's mystical ontology of the Unity of Being and its dimensions, particularly about the concept of the cosmic self. It is also based upon Kant's transcendental idealism and its corresponding dimensions. This study situates the cosmic self within a comparative research framework.

The cosmic self is a mystical and philosophical examination having empirical and transcendental connotations. The self appears to be a dynamic and active entity that exists at many levels. It can gain access to the knowable and unknowable realms through different means by using mystical or philosophical processes. This section lays down the theoretical foundations of the cosmic self through the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Immanuel Kant.

- **Ontology of the Self – Multilevel Existence:** Ibn Arabi's concept of self is multi-layered and cosmic in a true sense. It is human as well as divine, moving through a

hierarchical path from the physical to the spiritual. These hierarchies of the realms are named as the physical, psychic, angelic, spiritual and the Absolute (Chittick, 1998/1989; Corbin, 2013). These levels represent ontological presence and the self displaying different divine names along the path from physical to the spiritual realm. Kant divides the working of the self into two levels, which he calls the phenomenal self (empirical and shaped by sensory data structured by the mind) and the noumenal self (existing beyond the realm of sensory experience and accessible only through moral reason) (Kant, 1998). Kant's transcendental idealism shapes physical experiences through *a priori* categories within the self (Durant, 1933).

- **Time and the Self:** Although Ibn Arabi and Kant have different concepts of time but they associate these with self-awareness and perception. According to Ibn Arabi, time is divided into different layers, which are as follows:
 - Divine time transcending the constraints of physical time and is in the metaphysical realm (called by Ibn Arabi as *Dahr* in Arabic)
 - Cosmological time, which is concerned with the uncovering of experiences in the universe (known as *Zaman* in Arabic)
 - Atomic time is related to the indivisible moment (called *Waqt* in Arabic)

These multi-layered aspects of time help in understanding the status of the human self in the cosmos. However, Kant considers time *a priori* and intuitive, which helps in the structuring of sensations. Time is intuitive because it does not exist independently; rather envelops the external data into a comprehensible form (Bowering, 1992; Kant, 1998; Mohlaroyim, 2025).

- **The Role of the Self:** There is also apparent agreement between Ibn Arabi and Kant on the question of ethical considerations and self-will. Ibn Arabi makes humans exercise free will and vicegerents of the Divine, while making choices for selecting a choice

(Rakhmat, 2022). Kant rejects using the human self as a means towards achieving some end and must be respected so much that it is considered an end in itself. This is central to Kant's moral philosophy, upholding the dignity of the human self (Kant, 1997).

- **Epistemology of the Self and Cosmos:** Both Ibn Arabi and Kant begin with the common point of the physical realm in their epistemologies, but then follow different paths to arrive at the culminating point. The physical world of sensory perceptions does carry significance for Kant, but those are structured by the faculties of understanding and reason. Kant, though, accepts the limitations of human reason, which cannot go beyond the physical realm to the unknowable noumenal realm (Kant, 1998). On the contrary, Ibn Arabi makes mystical knowledge responsible for uncovering the spiritual truths otherwise inaccessible to ordinary perception. However, Ibn Arabi does not reject reason and revelation that finally lead to the Absolute (Arif, 2002; Marinay, 2015). Ibn Arabi explicitly and Kant implicitly accept the existence of a creative force behind the universe (Richards, 2010). For instance, Ibn Arabi also argues that it was the command of the divine which brought the whole cosmos into existence (Kamal, 2017; Massimi, 2011).
- **Realms of Existence and the Architecture of the Self:** Ibn Arabi and Kant divide existence into different realms:
 - Kant divides reality into phenomenal and noumenal realms that are significant for understanding moral law and freedom (Kant, 1998). These two realms are defined as follows:
 - ✓ **Phenomenal Realm:** It is the world of appearance and is structured by human cognition, being sensory and physical.

- ✓ **Noumenal Realm:** It is the domain of things-in-themselves existing independently outside human cognition and sensibility (Di Maria, 1999).
- Ibn Arabi explains the following five realms:
 - ✓ *Mulk* or the physical world is obviously the visible and empirical world.
 - ✓ *Alam al-Mithal* or the imaginal and psychic world, which combines the visible and invisible world and can be equated with the isthmus or intermediary world. It also shapes the spiritual forms (Shaqqi, 2022).
 - ✓ *Aalam al-Malakut*, or the angelic realm, is the realm where angels and spiritual forms exist and where Gabriel manifested himself to Mary (Hassanzadeh, 2021).
 - ✓ *Aalam al-Jabrut* or spiritual realm is the world of “eternal archetype” which is immaterial (Matsumoto, 2019, pp. 157–178).
 - ✓ *Mutlaq* or Absolute Presence is the cornerstone of the philosophy of Unity of Being and is considered foundational to spiritual and metaphysical union (Ramlan & Ludovico, 2023).

Ibn Arabi places *Barzakh*, which he calls the intermediate realm or *isthmus*, synthesising the finite and infinite (Ibn Arabi, 1980). Kant avoids getting into speculative metaphysics; however, his concept of the noumenal self serves almost the same purpose as that of Ibn Arabi’s imaginal realm, where metaphysical existence coheres with the physical. It remains outside the rational comprehension, though (Grier, 2014).

- **Sources of Self-Consciousness:** As discussed earlier under epistemology, the sources of self-consciousness, despite originating from different frameworks, are generated from the sensory experiences that help unfold the spiritual realms and knowledge

(Ibrahim, 2020). Kant makes transcendental apperception responsible for the self's ability to unify experience through cognition (Kant, 1998).

Ibn Arabi and Kant give a concept of the true self and its cosmic connection by locating it in the immaterial and noumenal realm (Kant). However, Kant equally accepts a separately existing physical or empirical self that rests in the phenomenal realm. Ibn Arabi, though, has a concept of a single self that exists both in the physical (Kantian phenomenal) or spiritual realms (Kantian noumenal). Ibn Arabi and Kant also conceptualise a self that looks for a synthesis with the greater reality (Ibn Arabi) and with the moral principle (Kant). Kant founds his philosophy on the rational principle, but Ibn Arabi on the spiritual experience of discovering cosmic mysteries through mysticism and divine relationality. Their respective systems provide a rich source of theoretical foundation for exploring the self as material and immaterial, autonomous and free, seeking love and beauty, looking for essence and existence and exploring how to secure annihilation and oneness. The following table combines the mystical framework of Ibn Arabi with the philosophical framework of Kant:

Table 3.1.*Combining Ibn Arabi and Kant in the Conceptual Framework*

Dimension	Ibn Arabi	Kant	Shared Insight
Freedom and Autonomy	True freedom is driven by the divine will, not by the self-ego. Autonomy is the surrender of will (annihilation) to the divine.	Moral freedom comes through rational autonomy with the self acting to fulfil universal moral law instead of being selfish.	External determinism and egoistic will are denied. Freedom is in going beyond the lower self through submission (Ibn Arabi) and through rational self-legislation.
Essence and Existence	It is Divine, whereas the Divine is manifested through existence. Appearances are illusions and not the entire reality.	The essence rests in the thing-in-itself (conceptual, noumenal), which is unknowable, but existence is phenomenal (lived experience), with the true self located beyond empirical appearances.	The true essence rests beyond appearance. Humans can cognise existence only partially.
Love and Beauty	The divine created the universe out of love. Beauty is a manifestation of God's Names. Love and beauty bring harmony and balance through unity.	Reason expresses itself through an aesthetic experience of love and beauty. The pleasure caused by beauty is disinterested, pointing towards universal harmony.	Love and beauty are transcendent, universal, and elevating by setting the self free from egoistic inclination and taking it closer to the Absolute.
Material and Immaterial	The divine and immaterial is manifested through the material world (theophany). The spirit being immaterial rests in the divine.	The material world represents the phenomenal realm, whereas the immaterial is the noumenal. Our moral actions are inspired by the noumenal self.	Reality exists in dual form of the material and immaterial. The human self must unfold the immaterial to attain real significance.
Oneness and Annihilation	It is only through annihilation that the human self finds perfection. The human self thus secures Unity.	The noumenal self is rational and uninspired by material riches. It transcends the noumenally free and universal moral self.	The true self can be accessed through transcendence from the physical self towards a higher reality, the Divine Unity (Ibn Arabi)

3.3. Methodological Framework

Given the philosophical and literary nature of the inquiry, a qualitative research approach was adopted. It follows a comparative literary inquiry through thematic and content analysis to analyse the employment of themes and images associated with selfhood and its cosmic significance in Keats's and Khan's poetry. This triangulation of the methodological framework facilitated an in-depth analysis of data from both Keats's and Khan's poetry, examining their perspectives on the cosmic self from the viewpoints of Ibn Arabi and Kant.

The study, focusing on poetic compositions with philosophical and mystical undercurrents, employed a qualitative research methodology. This approach was deemed the most appropriate as it facilitated a rich and interpretative analysis of poetic texts (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). The study emphasised the exploration of the subjective and symbolic dimensions of the text, a unique aspect that distinguishes it in the field of literary studies (Creswell, 2014). This qualitative research also employed a flexible approach to incorporate cross-cultural philosophical themes (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

3.3.1. Research Design

This study mainly adopts a qualitative approach to make textual analysis of Keats's and Khan's poetry by triangulating thematic and content analysis. The study is aimed at achieving research objectives of identifying cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's poetry through the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi's Unity of Being and Kant's transcendental idealism. The study operates in a comparative framework drawing on the poetic and philosophical output from the East and the West. The findings of this are significant to prove that the poetic articulations of the self have a relationship with the cosmos and the divine.

3.3.2. Data Collection Procedure

The corpus consists of the selected poems by Keats taken from *Keats' Poetry: 4 Books: The Poetry of John Keats, including Lamia, Endymion, Poems 1817, and Poems 1820* and the English translation of Khan's Pashto poetry, *The Pilgrim of Beauty* by Sahibzada Imtiaz. These have been thematically explored for the cosmic self through its different dimensions of freedom and autonomy, love and beauty, essence and existence, material and immaterial, oneness and annihilation. The selection method for data sampling is purposive because it focuses on the poems that explicitly or implicitly explore metaphysical and philosophical dimensions.

3.3.3. Selection Criteria

The selected poems carry metaphysical and philosophical underpinning with particular reference to the cosmic self and its dimensions. The following poems have been included for analysis:

- **Keats:** "Ode to a Nightingale," "Ode on a Grecian Urn," "To Autumn," "Ode on Melancholy," "Ode to Psyche," "Ode on Indolence," "Hyperion," "The Eve of St. Agnes," "Lamia," "Isabella; or, The Pot of Basil."
- **Khan:** "Wali" (Why?), "Shandana," (Shandana) "Da Faridoon da Moor Khat" (Letter from Faridoon's Mother), "Nageen," (Nageen) "Bahram Khan," (Bahram Khan) "Talaash" (Seach), "Badiwa" (The Kite), "Yau Jaam" (A Goblet of Wine), "Zama Mahal" (My Palace), "Jannat aw Duniya" (The World and Heaven), "Laka Wakhli Chi Mashoom" (Like a Child Who Plays), "Ridi Gul" (The Flower) "Suka" (Summit) "Ajaba Falsafa" (Strange Philosophy) "Gugal" (My Bosom) "Dwa Stargi" (Two Eyes) "Shpa Wa Da Sparlee" (It Was a Night in Early Spring) "Sparley" (Spring) "Za Hum Jadugar Yema" (I, too, am a Wizard) "Zama Muhataram Wrur Sardar Ali Khan Amir Jumat Islami Ta" (To My Dear Friend, Sardar Ali Khan Amir Jumat-i-Islami) "Dua" (Prayer) "Mansoor" (Mansoor) "Wakht" (Time) "Chi Adam Khawru Ki Kini" (When Man Mingles with the Earth) "Sail" (Excursion) "Zama Bakht" (My Fate) "Da

Khapiru Shahzagai” (The Fairy Princess) “*Shaheed*” (The Martyr) “*Sawal Jawab Da Levani Aw Mulla*” (Pious Priest and Madman) “*Deodasi*” (Deodasi) “*Ay Zawana*” (Oh Young Man!) “*Sodagar*” (The Merchant) “*Da Bachu Tarana*” (The Children’s Anthem) “*Saki*” (The Cupbearer) “*Masti*” (Ecstasy) “*Taali*” (Swing) “*Tapus ka Jawab*” (Question or Answer...) “*Da Faqiranu Ghazal*” (The Hermit’s Sonnet) “*Zhwand*” (Life) “*Zama Da Bachu Mur*” (The Mother of My Children) “*Saakht*” (Creation) “*Wru*” (Softly) “*Larr Sha*” (Get Away) “*Da Buday Taal*” (The Rainbow) “*Sinda Za Sinda Bahiga*” (Flow Oh River, Flow Along...) “*Da Zhimi Makham*” (A Winter’s Eve) “*Yau Khub Da Shair Da Saba Da Ranrra*” (A Dream of a Poet) “*Qismat*” (Fate) “*Pa Awya Kaala Zhwandoon Ki*” (Of the Three Score Years and Ten) “*Bachay Chi Lui Shee*” (My Child When You Grow Old) “*Janaan*” (Beloved) “*Mina Aw Husan*” (Love and Beauty) “*Saaz Aw Husan*” (Music and Beauty).

- **Corpus Size:** Approximately 53 poems of Khan translated by Sahibzada in *The Pilgrim of Beauty* and 11 major poems by Keats included in *Keats’ Poetry: 4 Books: The Poetry of John Keats, including Lamia, Endymion, Poems 1817, and Poems 1820*.
- **Sampling Technique and Time Span:** It is a criterion-based purposive sampling with a theoretical time span covering Keats’s Romantic period of the early 19th century and Khan’s poetry written during the 20th century.
- **Data Sources:** Data sources are given as under:
 - **Primary Sources:** These include the following:
 - ✓ **Keats:** *Keats’ Poetry: 4 Books: The Poetry of John Keats, including Lamia, Endymion, Poems 1817, and Poems 1820*.
 - ✓ **Khan:** Khan’s translated poetry in English, *The Pilgrim of Beauty. Latoon* (Search) by Hasrat.

- ✓ **Ibn Arabi:** Core text including *The Sufi Path of Knowledge: Ibn al-Arabi's Metaphysics of Imagination*, *The Bezels of Wisdom (Fusus ul-Hikam)* and selected excerpts from *The Meccan Revelations (al-Futuhat al-Makkiyya)*.
- ✓ **Kant:** These include *Critique of Pure Reason*, *Groundwork of the Metaphysics of Morals*, *Critique of Practical Reason* and *Critique of Judgement*, *Critique of Practical Reason* and *Prolegomena to any Future Metaphysics* that guide transcendental idealism and major concepts of Kant's philosophy.
- **Secondary Sources:** These sources include several relevant scholarly contributions that critically analyse the poetic, philosophical and mystical writings of Keats, Khan, Ibn Arabi and Kant with special reference to the self and its significance. These sources also clarify the theoretical background.

3.3.4. Data Analysis Procedure

The study integrates thematic analysis and content analysis to interpret poetic texts concerning the cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's poetry through the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.

3.3.4.1. Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis is considered a helpful method to identify patterns and philosophical themes in both Keats's and Khan's poetry that can facilitate an exploration of the cosmic self (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Triangulation of thematic analysis and content analysis also helped validate and verify data, thus reducing the element of bias and adding to the depth of data collected (Jonsen & Jehn, 2009). Triangulation is like refraction through a glass, encouraging several viewpoints (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). As recommended by Denzin (1989), this research correlated Ibn Arabi, Kant, Keats and Khan. Data analysis was done in the following steps:

- **Familiarisation:** It was done through repeated reading and re-reading.

- **Initial Coding:** It was manually done in table form, covering different dimensions of the cosmic self such as freedom and autonomy, love and beauty, material and immaterial, essence and existence, and oneness and annihilation.
- **Generating Themes:** Each theme was reviewed for its association with Ibn Arabi's and Kant's concept of the cosmic self, as well as the images employed by the poets under the following broad categories, with the relevant poetic example from the data:
 - Freedom and autonomy
 - Love and beauty
 - Essence and existence
 - Material and Immaterial
 - Oneness and Annihilation
 - Finally, the report was produced after interpreting themes in light of Ibn Arabi's concept of Unity of Being and Kant's transcendental idealism to highlight the cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's poetry.

3.3.4.2. Content Analysis

It was employed to identify and categorise images and symbols that construct the poets' vision of the cosmic self (Krippendorff, 2018). The steps include:

- **Unit of Analysis:** Textual Coding was carried out to identify metaphors, symbols, and motifs related to selfhood, infinity, nature, death and transcendence.
- **Thematic Categorisation:** Images and texts were placed thematically into autonomy and freedom, materiality and immateriality and essence and existence, considering them as one or distinct entities.
- **Triangulation with the Thematic Analysis:** The findings of the thematic analysis undertaken previously were paralleled with the content analysis.
- **Frequency and Co-occurrence:** Recurring images were matched to verify findings.

3.3.5. Operationalisation of the Key Concept: Cosmic Self

The cosmic self is intrinsically associated with cosmos, the divine and the transcendent self. It is either being one with the divine, a quintessential part of the cosmic and universal order or a consciousness that transcends the physical and holds the whole cosmos within itself. In order to achieve the objectives of this research, the cosmic self has been operationalised through the following conceptual dimensions:

- **Freedom and Autonomy:** It is liberation from the illusion of autonomous selfhood and surrendering entirely to the Real. Autonomy is also giving will in the will of the divine (Ibn Arabi, 1980, 2015). According to Kant, true freedom is the absence of external pressure called heteronomy and the capacity to act according to one's own rational principles. Autonomy is the capacity to self-legislate moral law (Kant, 1996). Freedom thus has an intelligible source, aimed at moral dignity and transcending selfish desire (Ibn Arabi, 1980; Kant, 1788).
 - **Operationalisation of Freedom and Autonomy:** |It is to be uninfluenced by selfish inclinations, egoistic desires and aligned with the divine will. Rationally legislating for the self and annihilating the self in the divine will to achieve true autonomy. Symbols and images associated with freedom and autonomy in the text highlight ethereality and wind like birds, pieces of art and literature, nature, clouds, death and flight, etc (Chandler, 2005; Roe, 2012).
- **Love and Beauty:** According to Ibn Arabi, love is the force behind creation so that the divine may know itself. Beauty is the efficient cause of love represented in whatever has been created by the divine (Ibrahim, 2022). However, Kant considers love as subordinate to moral duty and rational control. Beauty brings synthesis into imagination and understanding, which has expressed purposelessness without purpose (Kant, 1998).

- **Operationalisation of Love and Beauty:** Actions inspired by moral duty instead of personal fulfilment. Emotions are controlled by reason. Harmony and balance through literature and art reflect beauty and longing for divine unity. Images and symbols of longing, pain, imagination and creativity. Keats uses images like flowers, moon, Spring, clouds, colours, rills and stars, etc (Paris, 2024). Khan also demonstrates the same approach towards love and beauty in his poetry (Babar, 2005).
- **Material and Immaterial:** For Ibn Arabi, material is the sensible, empirical world which is composed of bodies and the visible dimension of reality, but immaterial is spiritual, immutable and invisible true reality. Kant considers material as phenomenal, which is the sensible world and immaterial as noumenal, which is the intelligible and unknowable realm beyond human perception. Kant also calls these realms things-in-themselves (noumenal) and the thing-as-they-appear (Chittick, 1989; Kant, 1998).
 - **Operationalisation of Material and Immaterial:** Material dimension has sensory, physical and concrete imagery such as flowers, scents, etc. Abstract, timeless and intelligible phenomena, such as unheard music, frozen images, and a longing for eternity, represent the immaterial dimension.
- **Essence and Existence:** According to Ibn Arabi, essence is the archetypal form of all creation. True existence belongs solely to the divine, with the existence of created beings as borrowed and contingent. According to Kant, existence is not a predicate that requires empirical evidence for affirmation, whereas essence is a conceptual and rational determination that shows the possibility of a thing (Chittick, 1989; Kant, 1998).
 - **Operationalisation of Material and Immaterial:** Essence is represented by themes and metaphors reflecting ideal forms and archetypes associated with permanence and impermanence. Imagery associated with impermanence and

temporality, like shifting seasons and growing old. These dialectical attributes are the focal points of Essentialism (looking for universal and archetypal in text), New Criticism (exploring internal structure) and Phenomenology in literature (emphasising physical and sensory experience).

- **Oeness and Annihilation:** According to Ibn Arabi, everything exists within the divine as manifestation, whereas oneness is produced through the annihilation of the self and ego (Chittick, 1994). Sometimes, the philosophical frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant converge on the cosmic self as a dimension of the ineffably spiritual, higher and noumenal reality, which holds unity in diversity for Ibn Arabi or in the categories of understanding for Kant (Chittick, 1989; Kant, 1781/1998). Kant believes in epistemological unity and oneness through transcendence and cognition. However, Kant ignores self-annihilation and rather affirms the self through autonomy and rational moral principle, unlike the mystical notion of Ibn Arabi.
- **Operationalisation of Oeness and Annihilation:** Images like ocean, mirror, metaphors and images of dissolution and merging self into that of the beloved or divine, such as in a mystic experience. Death and disappearance are the recurring motifs. However, Kant does not let the self annihilate but asserts itself as an autonomous entity.

3.3.6. Coding for Thematic and Content Analysis

The study followed a manual coding system for both the thematic analysis and content analysis. For this purpose, textual data was broken down into meaningful units and categorised under larger philosophical and thematic concepts. A sample coding is given below:

Table 3.2.

Codebook Sample (Illustrated)

Code	Definition	Example from a Poem	Theme
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Beauty_BTU Love_VL	Expressions indicating the eternity of beauty	A thing of beauty is a joy forever.... (Keats)	The Self and Beauty
Material_MTL Immaterial_MLR	Matter is impermanent	For a morsel of bread / Is Your name sold for a pittance (Khan)	Material impermanence
Essence_SNC Existence_XST	Truth lies in essence	O thou whose mighty palace roof doth hang / ...and overshadoweth/ eternal whispers (Keats)	The physical world has its essence located in the eternal world.
Annihilation_NHL Oneness_INS	One recognises oneself only through annihilation.	Death has become worship pure / and a source of love emerged (Khan)	It is only through death that one gets oneness with the true self.
Freedom_FDM Autonomy_TNM	Freedom is either the loss of personal will willingly or the securing of autonomy.	My Madeline! Sweet dreamer! Lovely bride! / Say, may I be for aye thy vassal blest? (Keats)	Willing surrender of freedom before beloved.

3.3.7. Reliability Check

To eliminate the threat of bias and ensure the credibility of the study, the data were triangulated through a combination of literary and philosophical methods (Patton, 2002). Validation of themes was undertaken over many poems (Guest et al., 2012). Conceptual alignment and order were maintained throughout this lengthy data analysis process, utilising Ibn Arabi's and Kant's frameworks. It was ensured that the coding remains consistently systematic throughout through prior definition. Guidance and feedback from the supervisor were constantly sought. Data was triangulated through the application of both the thematic and content analyses.

3.3.8. Ethical Considerations

Despite dealing with purely textual and non-human material for the research, ethical principles of the academic research regarding integrity, transparency and responsible scholarship were constantly upheld. It has been ensured that the study remains credible, authentic and ethically acknowledgeable. All the philosophical and poetic sources were meticulously cited in APA format. An authentic and widely accepted translation of Khan's poetry by Sahibzada was used as a data source. All the primary and secondary sources were acknowledged. Since this study involved the interpretation of poetry therefore a deliberate effort was made to align the interpretation with the philosophical frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Being mainly interpretative and explanatory in nature, this research avoids presenting findings as universally and definitively acceptable.

3.3.9. Preferring Thematic and Content Analysis Methods over Other Methods

The study employed a comparative analysis because it provides ample space for a dialectical relationship in the cross-cultural realm between the works of Ibn Arabi, Kant, Keats and Khan (Damrosch, 2003). It also emphasised that the East and West were interconnected in their literary, mystical and philosophical output. As a comparative study that seeks self-recognition, this study also enriched the literature on selfhood and its cosmic link in the light of the mysticism, philosophy and poetry of the East and the West (Zepetnek, 1998).

The study has been conducted using thematic analysis and content analysis to explore the cosmic self in the poetry of Keats and Khan through the philosophical frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. These methods are the most appropriate for this research because they align with the philosophical, interpretive and textual nature of the study that engages symbolic language, imagery and aesthetic expressions. Since the study deals with abstract themes such as the cosmic self, freedom, love and beauty, etc, in the written texts of poetry, therefore, thematic

and content analyses were preferred over discourse analysis, grounded theory or narrative analysis

3.4. Conclusion

This chapter was divided into two sections, with the first focusing on the philosophical and literary underpinnings of the study, which provided an interpretive foundation for examining the mystical and philosophical concepts of selfhood in their association with cosmic significance in the poetry of Keats and Khan. The chapter also included the conceptual framework developed for data analysis, drawing on the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. The comparative study approach was considered the most appropriate tool for examining the cross-cultural and universal significance of the cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's works.

Data will be analysed in the succeeding three chapters, which are sequentially ordered, beginning with Keats, followed by Khan, and then pinpointing convergence and divergence in Keats's and Khan's poetry, and finally, the significance of the cosmic self.

Figure 3.1.

Theoretical Foundation

Table 3.3.

A Specimen Table for the Selection/ Distribution of Data Concerning Dimensions of the Cosmic Self in Keats's Poetry

Ser	Title	Oneness / Annihilation	Love / Beauty	Essence/ Existence (Dualism or Polarity)	I	Immaterial/ Material (dualism or polarity)	Freedom/ freedom of choice
1.	Lamia	<p><u>Hermes finds oneness and unity with Lamia, who is also in search of the love they have lost, which is reflected in Hermes's request to Lamia.</u></p> <p>“Thou smooth-lipp'd serpent, surely high inspired! Thou beauteous wreath, with melancholy eyes, Possess whatever bliss thou canst devise, Telling me only where my nymph is fled,— Where she doth breathe!”</p>	<p>The ever-smitten Hermes empty left His golden throne, bent warm on amorous theft: From high Olympus had he stolen light, On this side of Jove's clouds, to escape the sight Of his great summoner, and made retreat Into a forest on the shores of Crete. For somewhere in that sacred island dwelt A nymph, to whom all hoofed Satyrs knelt</p>	<p>From vale to vale, from wood to wood, he flew, Breathing upon the flowers his passion new, And wound with many a river to its head, To find where this sweet nymph prepar'd her secret bed: In vain; the sweet nymph might nowhere be found, And so he rested, on the lonely ground</p>	<p><u>The 'I' in Keats's poetry represents a longing for life, love, and pleasure, which is often overshadowed by the realities of misery and pain. This 'I' is not just a personal pronoun, but a profound exploration of self-identity and its cosmic connections in Keats's poetry.</u></p> <p>“When from this wreathed tomb shall I awake! When moving in a sweet body fit for life, And love, and pleasure, and the ruddy strife Of hearts and lips! Ah, miserable me!”</p>	<p><u>Only the imaginative power can uncover the secrets of the immaterial behind the beautiful nature and love</u></p> <p>And in those meads where sometime she might haunt, strewn rich gifts, unknown to any Muse, Though Fancy's casket was unlock'd to choose.</p>	<p><u>Willingly giving up freedom</u></p> <p>For somewhere in that sacred island dwelt A nymph, to whom all hoofed Satyrs knelt; At whose white feet the languid Tritons poured Pearls, while on land, they wither'd and adored.</p>

Table 3.4.

A Specimen Table for the Thematic and Content Analysis of a Single Dimension of the Cosmic Self in Khan's Poetry

Dimension: Freedom / Surrender / Free Will

Ser	Title	Pashto Extract	English Translation	Interpreting Attribute	Image
1.	<i>Wali?</i> (Why?)	<i>maa ta musku stargu ki khkuli wuwi wali suk zrrra wubaailee? Sa rangi shaida shi suk? Suk chi chaa ta wukhaandi Wali pa khanda shi suk?</i>	And to me, in smiling eyes, My beloved gently spoke – Why does one the heart surrender? How does one fall in love? (<i>Sahibzada, pp. 6–7</i>).	Willing to surrender before love and a charming smile	Lover falling for beloved
2.	<i>Da Faridun da Mur Khat</i> (Letter from Faridoon's Mother)	<i>Daa zama rooh chi rukhaan shu da da stargi yi krri bali Daa Tasweer zama da zhwand dey sa khanda da sa zhaarra da Da shahbaz di wazar shagh dey pust suoo na da bulbali Daa suboot da shah da mini, daa zaari da da Ghulam</i>	When my soul absorbed the light, Both his eyes commenced to glow; This, the essence of my life – Sometimes laughter, often pain; And the eagle's sheer swoop; And the <i>bulbul's</i> melody; And an emperor's proof of love; An entreaty of a slave (<i>Sahibzada, pp. 14–15</i>).	If the poet compares himself with the emperor, he also compares himself with the enslaved person.	Eagle, nightingale, emperor and salve
3.	<i>Da Faridun da Mur Khat</i> (Letter from Faridoon's Mother)	<i>Maa ka daaw pa yo armaan sta, khpal zhwandoon tamaam tamaam Maa khpal hosh ku laal la warka chi tri taa la jurr krri jam</i>	I have wagered on just one Of your longing; indiscreet, To the potter, I gave up All my consciousness, to make On the wheel, for you, a cup (<i>Sahibzada, pp. 18–19</i>).	Willingly handing over his self and his control to the beloved.	The potter, the cup which has the luck to keep kissing the beloved's lips

CHAPTER FOUR

The Whispering Cosmos in Keats's Verse

There lies a den,
Beyond the seeming confines of the space
Made for the soul to wander in and trace
Its existence, of remotest glooms.
Dark regions are around it, where the tombs
Of buried griefs the spirit sees, but scarce
One hour doth linger weeping, for the pierce
Of newborn woe it feels more inly smart:
And in these regions many a venom'd dart
At random, flies; they are the proper home
Of every ill: the man is yet to come
Who hath not journeyed in this native hell?

(Keats, 2012, lines 515–526).

4.1. Introduction

This chapter presents a literary analysis of Keats's selected poems about his concept of the cosmic self. The chapter proceeds by dividing the analysis into different dimensions of the cosmic self in Keats's poetry through the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Keats's poems are cited as stanzas mainly in the case of odes and line numbers in the case of long narrative poems, as well as odes not written in stanzaic form.

4.2. Cosmic Self as Freedom and Autonomy

4.2.1. Lamia

Keats's poem "Lamia" presents an intentionally well-conceived design that combines *Akbarian* and Kantian perspectives on freedom as a dimension of the cosmic self. Both perspectives also exhibit some divergence, based on the transition from the origin. Being a mystic, Ibn Arabi renounces freedom in favour of yielding to and merging personal will with the divine. In

contrast, Kant, a rational critical philosopher, advocates for freedom of the self and rejects depriving it of freedom and autonomy. Both perspectives, however, converge on the question of being taken over by the ephemeral, which Ibn Arabi as well as Kant reject on account of being subservient to the worldly and external authority, respectively.

Keats also highlights his perspective on freedom through various images and symbols in his poem "Lamia." The theme of relinquishing freedom and submitting to love is exemplified by Lamia, who yearns for union with a corporeal entity, Lycius, as well as by the messenger god Hermes, who desires the same with an incorporeal entity, nymph Aphrodite. Thus, the desire to willingly give up freedom is always present. Myth has it that Lamia, a paragon of femininity, was cursed to be transformed into a chthonic devourer. Keats metamorphosed her into her previous corporeal self, who falls in love with a Corinthian youth, Lycius. This transcendence from a spirit to an empirical form symbolises Ibn Arabi's concept of manifestation being represented in corporeal form. The transformation of Lamia into a physical form also symbolises her restlessness over her imprisonment in the current state of incorporeality and immortality. This transformation from the state of spirit may also mean losing immortality and accepting the pains of human form, but she is even willing to tolerate that in favour of winning freedom. Freedom and autonomy are far more significant than anything else through the magical potion administered by Hermes, "weird syrups that would keep / Her loveliness invisible, yet free / to wander as she loves, in liberty..." (Book I, lines 107–109).

The Kantian conflict between heteronomy and autonomy is evident through the interplay between love, passion and reason in Lamia. Lycius also willingly gets into a heteronomous relationship with Lamia when he forswears his freedom in her love. However, Apollonius, as a symbol of reason, occupies an intermediary position between Lycius and Lamia. Apollonius's position is that of the Kantian moral and rational principle that keeps a balance between Lycius

and Lamia. Keats, however, does not seem convinced by that, so he symbolically accentuates this through the loss of both Lycius, representing love and Lamia, representing passion. This equilibrium, though, gets compromised by both Lycius and Lamia ignoring Apollonius's presence. The following lines present the promises that Lycius and Lamia make to each other in a fit of passion:

You have deserted me;—where am I now?

Not in your heart while care weighs on your brow:

No, no, you have dismiss'd me; and I go

From your breast houseless: ay, it must be so. (Book II, lines 742–745).

This disengagement of Lycius from his mentor, Apollonius, under the influence of Lamia, violates Kant's moral and universal principles but fulfils Ibn Arabi's principle of winning freedom through losing freedom and autonomy. Keats illustrates both viewpoints firstly through Lamia, who represents Ibn Arabi's divine spirit, and through Lycius, who willingly bows down in servitude to her out of love.

4.2.2. Endymion

The theme of freedom and autonomy is also visible in Keats's poem "Endymion." Keats demonstrates a visible convergence between Ibn Arabi and Kant through the character of Niobe. It is neither the unequivocal metaphysical non-compliance out of arrogance like Satan, as Ibn Arabi would disapprove of, nor the pronouncement of radical autonomy, as Kant would reject, that Keats symbolises through Niobe. She represents a disobedient spirit cursed with eternal mourning by the gods. Keats writes about the proud and arrogant queen of Thebes, Niobe, though somewhat mercifully:

Those who would watch. Perhaps, the trembling knee

And frantic gape of lonely Niobe,

Poor, lonely Niobe! when her lovely young

Were dead and gone. (Book I, lines 337–340).

Niobe becomes a symbol of disobedience, arrogance and intransigence in her refusal to accept the will of the gods. Consequently, she is punished by a methodical dispossession of her children. Another such arrogant and recalcitrant example is that of Satan, who refuses to prostrate before Adam when ordered. She also faces a similar eternal damnation.

Sacrifice is a form of submission. Keats presents this through “Endymion” by “High genitors, unconscious did they cull / Time’s sweet first-fruits—they danc’d to weariness, have always been there to win over gods...” (Book I, lines 320–321). Our progenitors, Adam and Eve, gave up paradise just to taste deep human emotions of love and suffering. This sounds so familiar with the previously analysed poem “Lamia,” where she loses freedom for the sake of tasting the emotion of love. This aligns more with Ibn Arabi than with Kant. Ibn Arabi approves of the Fall as a positive experience for humans to freely and autonomously realise their true potential. Kant accepts sacrifice out of moral duty but rejects the Fall as a form of moral and rational failure, as well as being dominated by selfish desires.

Endymion’s sister Peona represents a rational and moral principle. She tries to fend her brother off from suffering and pain by leading him to an isolated place of contained freedom, the lonely island. They sail through water that symbolically represents Endymion’s slow transformation through a directed path, as represented by water and a boat. Keats describes this in the following words:

Peona guiding, through the water straight,
Towards a bowery island opposite;
Which, gaining presently, she steered light
Into a shady, fresh, and ripply cove... (Book I, lines 427–430).

The above excerpt thus associates Keats with Ibn Arabi and Kant. In Eastern mysticism, discipleship is the approved practice of giving up self before a master. In some *Sufi* traditions,

woman takes the form of purity and submission to the extent that some *Sufis* present themselves to the divine in the form of a woman. Ibn Arabi's *Tarjuman ul Ashwaq* ([The Translator of Desires](#)) presents woman as a profound theophany ([Sells, 2021](#)). Although Kant suffers from typical 18th-century gender bias towards women, he approves of the moral and rational principle in accepting freedom as represented by Peona.

Keats is fond of symbolically representing human emotions through characters in his poetry. For instance, "Lamia" demonstrates reason, passion and love through the characters of Apollonius, Lycius and Lamia respectively. In "Endymion," reason is represented by Peona, love by Cynthia and passion by Endymion. As happens in "Lamia" with Apollonius, Peona loses her brother Endymion forever through a willing relinquishment of his freedom to Cynthia because both slowly and gradually disappear from her sight. Kant disapproves of such love that compels someone to become almost apathetic towards social obligations, but Ibn Arabi admires this as a mystic attribute. Keats expresses the same helpless reason to stop someone from willingly losing freedom, because reason suffers from its own limitations. He symbolically represents this through the swords and grasshopper in, "...swords / Against the enchased crocodile, or leaps / Of grasshoppers against the sun..." ([Book I, lines 714–716](#)).

Love at the expense of freedom may be acceptable to Ibn Arabi, but not to Kant, who shares Peona's surprise at the loss of reason when she says, "Is this the cause? / This all? Yet it is strange, and sad, alas!" ([Book I, lines 722–723](#)). Keats's attitude towards such a love is ambiguous because he neither condones nor condemns Endymion or Cynthia. It is, though, an evolutionary experience.

Dove symbolises ideal freedom as well as beauty and innocence. This freedom suffers from the threat of being snatched. Despite love being either an emancipator or usurper of freedom, it is one such emotion that may usually influence this deprivation. According to Ibn

Arabi, when the goal is directed towards submerging will into the divine will, then it becomes an emancipator:

Young dove of the waters! truly, I'll not hurt

One hair of thine: see how I weep and sigh,

That our heart-broken parting is so nigh. (**Book I, lines 585–587**).

However, when the goal is directed towards personal ambition and worldly gains, then it becomes a usurper. Keats's image of an elephant that longs to be set free from the tortuous living under yoke of flesh represents a desire to attain freedom from the corporeal realm that, "sue[s] not for my happy crown again; / Only I pray, as fairest boon, to die, / Or be deliver'd from this cumbrous flesh..." (**Book I, lines 746–754**). This longing for freedom is both *Akbarian* and Kantian in connotation, as Ibn Arabi proposes freedom from worldly obsessions and Kant from irrational desires.

Many ancient civilisations, from the Egyptian to the Ethiopian and Mongolian, have renounced freedom under the Bacchic influence of art, creativity and poetry. It is the aesthetic experience, art, poetry and music that actually sets humans free from the bonds of rituals as in Egypt, dryness as in Abyssinia and cruelty as in Tartary. The following synchronises with Ibn Arabi, who praises creativity as an act of the divinely free expression, and with Kant, who acknowledges creativity as a free play of the imagination and understanding. Freedom, through creativity, is thus a universal desire shared even by the ancient civilisations, as Keats says:

I saw Osirian Egypt kneel adown

Before the vine-wreath crown!

I saw parched Abyssinia rouse and sing

To the silver cymbals' ring!

I saw the whelming vintage hotly pierce

Old Tartary, the fierce! (**Book IV, lines 259–264**).

Keats then moves on to yearn for freedom. Only the wings of freedom can enable humans to delve deeper into the soul and take out the richness inside. It is freedom, not in the physical sense, but in the spiritual sense. Keats writes, "...the pinions of my will. / 'twas freedom! and at once I visited / The ceaseless wonders of this ocean-bed..." where different images highlight attaining freedom through imagination, self-discovery and spiritual enlightenment (**Book III, lines 392–394**).

4.2.3. The Eve of St. Agnes

Keats's "The Eve of St. Agnes" depicts freedom to love in contemplation (noumenal and imaginal realm) and freedom to love in action (phenomenal and physical realm). Madeline symbolises freedom in the imaginal realm, and Porphyro in the physical realm. Both forms of freedom are acceptable as long as they remain within the permissible social bounds and are directed towards higher ends. Keats also portrays freedom and autonomy in this poem in a limited and ambiguous state.

The poem begins with restraint exercised on the part of Madeline, who initially behaves more in the tradition of Apollonius in "Lamia" and Peona in "Endymion." However, she turns completely rebellious and autonomous in action towards the end when she agrees to elope with Porphyro. The hour of disillusionment comes with its dawn upon Madeline with its impact. Her passivity and innocence are compromised when Porphyro sneaks into Madeline's bedchamber:

Her eyes were open, but she still beheld,
Now wide awake, the vision of her sleep:
There was a painful change that nigh expell'd
The blisses of her dream so pure and deep
At which fair Madeline began to weep... (**XXXIV**).

Freedom through escape is not acceptable to Keats, Ibn Arabi and Kant. Keats's attitude towards complete freedom is also marked by ambiguity and doubt. Images of "missal," being "blinded alike from sunshine and from rain," and "a rose...be a bud again" represent freedom from the harsh realities of life represented by "Paynims pray" (XXVII). Porphyro's journey to Madeline's bedchamber symbolically represents a pilgrimage. It is an experience of complete surrender. Porphyro willingly surrenders freedom but to Madeline, who is fast asleep, as symbolised by "sweet dreamer" and "silver shrine." If he forces such a love out of Madeline, that will not be inspired by freedom. Keats writes:

My Madeline! sweet dreamer! lovely bride!
Say, may I be for aye thy vassal blest?
Thy beauty's shield, heart-shap'd and vermeil dyed?
Ah, silver shrine, here will I take my rest. (XXXVIII).

Freedom for Kant rests in following the dictates of reason and moral principles, rather than being dominated by any irrational external force. Despite being unimpressed by material wealth and her social preeminence, she succumbs to the enticements of Porphyro and reluctantly accepts becoming his slave in love. Porphyro, though, boasts of being enslaved by her, turns out to enslave Madeline and deprives her of autonomy as:

She hurried at his words, beset with fears,
For there were sleeping dragons all around,
At glaring watch, perhaps, with ready spears—
Down the wide stairs, a darkling way they found. (XL).

Neither Ibn Arabi nor Kant would approve of such a freedom. They will reject this freedom that gives physical instead of spiritual access to the beloved and is unchecked by the social obligation or moral principle. Madeline is both uninfluenced by the physical and material, but she is subservient to passion under the passionate entreaties of Porphyro. Porphyro boasts of

being a slave, but he steals into Madeline's bed chamber and deprives her of autonomy. The poem thus brings a synthesis between freedom and surrender out of passion and desire for physical association.

4.2.4. Hyperion

Keats portrays an atmosphere of chaos in his poem "Hyperion." It is the loss of freedom by the old gods, Titans, and the gain of a kingdom by the new gods, the Olympians. As a mystic, Ibn Arabi sees the rejuvenation, manifestation and foundation of the divine, whereas as a philosopher like Kant interprets chaos as structural and natural disorder. Kant rejects chaos as freedom unhindered by the moral and universal principle. Ibn Arabi makes the divine responsible for bringing order through manifestation, but Kant makes reason responsible for bringing order. Having been guided by a desire for freedom, Apollo longs to be free to create a new order and a new world for himself. Apollo thinks like the Perfect Being of Ibn Arabi, who interprets it as the one who integrates in himself the perfection of the divine manifestation. This may also be someone who combines perfect rational and moral principles in accordance with Kant's transcendental idealism. The following lines illustrate this:

But cannot I create?

Cannot I form? Cannot I fashion forth

Another world, another universe,

To overbear and crumble this to nought?

Where is another chaos? Where? (**Book I, lines 141–145**)

This poem focuses on freedom. Even the gods who are stagnant and suffering from a lack of creativity are deprived of freedom, like the Titans. This stagnance is symbolised by the cry of fellow Titans in favour of the old order that Saturn "must be King" after "a golden victory" (**Book I, lines 125–126**). They faced defeat at the hands of the Olympian gods representing the

new order and creativity. This defeat, being unwillingly thrust upon them, is unacceptable to all the Titans except the philosophical Oceanus, who advises his brethren:

Tis the eternal law,

That first in beauty should be first in might:

Yea, by that law, another race may drive

Our conquerors to mourn as we do now. (**Book II, lines 228–231**).

Keats discourages any act that puts the natural order in peril at the direction of subjective inclination. The dialectical process of freedom through balance between reason and passion is highlighted through the juxtaposition of Oceanus and Saturn. Oceanus is reconciled to the existing state of dethronement, but Saturn does not accept living in a constant state of damnation. Keats emphasises this balance between reason (the Olympians) and emotion (the Titans) through Apollo, who says to Mnemosyne (the memory), “Or shall we listen to the over-wise, / Or to the over-foolish, Giant-Gods?” (**Book I, lines 309–310**).

4.2.5. Isabella; or, The Part of Basil (A Story from Boccaccio)

It is yet another poem that engages with the theme of freedom in a mystical and philosophical sense. True freedom comes with submission to the divine will in love and the renunciation of material possessions. Keats explicitly conveys his aversion to authoritarianism and exploitation of fellow humans based on material supremacy and worldly possession, as described in the following words:

For them the Ceylon diver held his breath,

And went all naked to the hungry shark;

For them his ears gush'd blood; for them in death

The seal on the cold ice with piteous bark... (**XV**).

Keats shares this repugnance of giving up freedom to worldly riches with Ibn Arabi and Kant. His attitude towards freedom is often ambiguous. Keats's poetry displays freedom and

autonomy that synthesises both Ibn Arabi and Kant. He seeks a self that is sometimes rebellious and sometimes checked by reason.

4.3. Cosmic Self as Annihilation and Oneness

4.3.1. Endymion

Ideas of Ibn Arabi and Kant are mirrored in “Endymion.” It is particularly concerning that oneness and annihilation are inextricably linked to love and beauty at both the earthly and cosmic levels.

Being manifestations of the divine, humans have always expressed their attraction for the heavenly bodies. They long for unity and oneness with these entities. Greek and Roman mythologies also reflect this desire and attraction for union. Keats presents the moon as Cynthia, Dian or Selene in “Endymion.” A Latmian shepherd, Endymion, succumbs to the moon that entirely masters him. He is willing to annihilate himself in the hope of securing oneness with the moon:

What is there in thee, Moon! that thou shouldst move

My heart so potently? When yet a child

I oft have dried my tears when thou hast smil’d. (Book III, lines 144–146).

The moon assumes a reality in the ineffable and noumenal realm, eluding human understanding, “What is there in thee, Moon!” (Book I, line 452–453). The desire for oneness through willing surrender, develops a mystical element in Keats’s poetry, much like Ibn Arabi. Everything having once been generated reverts to the primordial unity through oneness and annihilation by stepping “into a sort of oneness” (Book I, lines 795–796). Keats, though, does not entirely dissolve like Ibn Arabi and reconciles to the physical or phenomenal realm as in the following:

Fountains grotesque, new trees, bespangled caves,

Echoing grottos, full of tumbling waves

.....
.....

Thus, in the bower,

Endymion was calmed to life again. (Book IV, lines 458–464).

Keats’s negative capability is paralleled with the *Sufi* tradition of annihilation and oneness. It enables poets to write about a particular object with no personal interference or effort to draw logical conclusions. Keats often becomes a mystic in his poetic philosophy. He is relatively closer to Ibn Arabi’s concept of self-annihilation or the merging into the beloved. He ceases to be identified with his own self. Keats writes, “I was distracted; madly did I kiss / The wooing arms which held me...” (Book I, line 653–654). As a *Sufi*, Ibn Arabi views the universe and all creation as a manifestation of the divine through the principles of transcendence and emanation. On the contrary, Keats’s epistemological system posits physical existence as primary and the divine being immanent in creation.

In Kantian philosophy, anything that holds grandeur and vastness always overpowers the sensory perceptions, but even then, human reason tries to understand it intellectually. This is how humans acknowledge the superiority of reason. This is also related to Kant’s emphasis on moral duty and the categorical imperative, which prevents the self from utter annihilation and surrender. The following lines depict not only the Kantian sublime through “dazzled soul” but also *Akbarian* oneness and annihilation through “commingling with”:

.....she did soar
So passionately bright, my dazzled soul
Commingling with her argent spheres did roll
Through clear and cloudy,..... (Book I, lines 593–596).

Keats transforms the self into an association of self-annihilation and immanence. Keats elevates the status of the moon to a divine ruler, “queen of light.” It has a universal existence that

physically illuminates every created entity in addition to symbolising imagination and internal desires (**Book IV, line 837**).

4.3.2. Lamia

Another narrative poem, “Lamia,” particularly seems to explore the theme of self-annihilation and negation. It highlights the act of submergence with the object of love. Having analysed the poem from the *Akbarian* perspective of the Unity of Being, “**Lamia**” evokes a sense of transcendence by reducing all the distinctions between the self and the divine through annihilation. The divine status of Lamia is acknowledged the moment Hermes, himself a god, sees her “Thou smooth-lipp’d serpent, surely high inspired! / Thou beauteous wreath, with melancholy eyes...” (**Part I, lines 83–84**).

Lamia presents a perfect example of the Kantian noumenal reality. She embodies an indefinable mystery about herself being transformed into a serpent. Whether good or evil, there exists an impenetrable pall between her apparent and her actual self. The human self has always been drawn to curiosity and mystery. Being a master of illusion, she raises a mystery around herself. Lycius willingly surrenders, undergoes self-annihilation and yearns to be one with his beloved Lamia. Lycius gets disturbed when she complains of being ignored for the sake of Apollonius, “How to entangle, trammel up and snare / Your soul in mine, and labyrinth you there...” (**Part II, lines 52–53**). This self-annihilation and immersion of Lycius becomes so deep when Lamia disappears; he also faces death, “And Lycius’ arms were empty of delight, / As were his limbs of life, from that same night. / On the high couch he lay!” (**Part II, lines 307–309**). He had warned of this quite earlier before Lamia, “Even as thou vanishest, so I shall die. / Stay! though a Naiad of the rivers, stay!” (**Part I, lines 260–261**).

Keats displays a mixed approach towards annihilation and oneness in “**Lamia**.” He develops this poem on the structure of thesis (annihilation symbolised by Lycius as in Ibn Arabi), antithesis (symbolised by Apollonius as in Kant) and synthesis (annihilation is good

but entails doom). In the end, Lamia prevails with the characteristic Keatsian negative capability, where he likes to remain in mystery and doubt instead of reaching for fact and reason.

4.3.3. Hyperion

Self-annihilation and oneness in this poem are hidden in the very act of transformation of the characters like Saturn, Oceanus and Apollo. Keats's "Hyperion" blends the mystical framework of Ibn Arabi and the philosophical doctrine of Kant through a dialectical process of thesis, antithesis and synthesis. Not central, Keats's portrayal of the images related to agriculture and farming highlights the themes of annihilation and oneness. These images accentuate a natural process of dissolution and then regeneration, much like the natural law. One gets annihilated only to re-emerge. It is contrary to reason to agonise over falling into a state of nothingness and powerlessness. Oceanus repeats the same to remind his brethren of a new and better beginning because it is a natural law that those with "power more strong in beauty, born of us" are "fated to excel us..." (**Book I, lines 212–214**). Saturn's wife Ops, the goddess of fertility and regeneration, looks quite pale and sick because she has reconciled with this natural law of annihilation and regeneration. Keats describes her thus, "And Ops, uplifting her black folded veil, / Show'd her pale cheeks, and all her forehead wan..." (**Book II, lines 113–114**).

Only the loss of status and annihilation will let Saturn contemplate. This humiliation at the hands of the Olympian gods unfolds his transformation from the previous self, "Among these fallen, Saturn's voice therefrom / Grew up like organ, that begins anew..." (**Book II, lines 125–126**). All this is grounded in Saturn's self-annihilation. Nothingness and annihilation generate a new cosmic order. This is an accepted practice of mysticism where the soul is cleansed of its impurities and desires through annihilation and effacement. This revival after

annihilation through cleansing begins with contemplation as Keats opens the poem, describing that state of Saturn:

Deep in the shady sadness of a vale
Far sunken from the healthy breath of morn,
Far from the fiery noon, and eve's one star,
Sat grey-hair'd Saturn, quiet as a stone... (Book I, lines 1–4).

Three main characters in “Hyperion” highlight the dialectical process. Firstly, Saturn and the rest of his brethren can be grouped into thesis (refusing to reconcile with the loss of the throne and acceptance of annihilation), and secondly, Oceanus and Ops can be classified into antithesis (reconciling with the fact of the loss and acceptance of annihilation). Apollo can be placed into synthesis, possessing “knowledge enormous” that makes a god out of him (Book III, line 113).

4.3.4. The Eve of St. Agnes

It appears that Keats's poems are designed on an overlying superstructure and an underlying substructure. His poem “The Eve of St. Agnes” is particularly relevant to the concepts of self-annihilation and oneness. The poem begins with a mixed feeling of the *Akbarian* (desire for oneness and annihilation as represented by Porphyro) and Kantian (desire for rational control as represented by Madeline), but ends on a characteristic state of being in mystery and doubt. This poem also represents a spiritual journey of transcendence and reawakening.

The sense of negation and annihilation is best illustrated through the lines, “he melted, as the rose / Blendeth its odour with the violet...” symbolising a comprehensive annihilation for Madeline and Porphyro (XXXVI). This happens only to re-emerge as entirely new, like a scent manufactured out of different flowers. It is a natural cycle to reemerge and regenerate after utter annihilation into oneness, as Porphyro does in Madeline's dream, “Into her dream he melted, as the rose / Blendeth its odour with the violet, / Solution sweet...” (XXXVI). This

suggests an attainment of oneness, no matter how harsh the circumstances might be, as represented by the cold, icy surroundings, “Like Love’s alarum pattering the sharp sleet / Against the window-panes; St. Agnes’ moon hath set...” (XXXVI). The moment of sleep and union has passed, and the time of accepting the harsh realities of life has started. The night of St. Agnes has seen its fruition in the form of lovers being united.

It is worth noting that Porphyro and Madeline remain comparatively independent in their capacities at the beginning. With the annihilation of their individuality and unity, they cease to exist independently. Keats presents them melting like the rose that mixes its odour with the violet, “They glide, like phantoms, into the wide hall / Like phantoms, to the iron porch, they glide...” and finally vanish forever into the storm not to be seen again (XLI). These lines thus align with both Ibn Arabi and Kant, as they portray mystical union and the ineffability of the noumenal realm that the lovers step into after achieving oneness.

4.3.5. Isabella; or, The Pot of Basil

Keats’s narrative poem “*Isabella, or The Pot of Basil*” highlights love through the themes of union and separation. When the *Akbarian* and Kantian perspectives are placed in parallel, a characteristic dialectical relationship emerges between the metaphysical propositions of Ibn Arabi and Kant regarding life and existence. Oneness and self-annihilation run prominently through the poem, especially concerning Isabella, when Keats refers to her as:

And she forgot the stars, the moon, and sun,
And she forgot the blue above the trees,
And she forgot the dells where waters run,
And she forgot the chilly autumn breeze;
She had no knowledge when the day was done... (LIII).

Isabella entirely obliterates herself like a true mystic. This self-effacement is visible even in her physical form despite being as tall as a palm when Keats says, “...She withers, like a palm

/ Cut by an Indian for its juicy balm” (LVI). Such a mystic also undergoes a mystic experience of revelation after undergoing suffering and annihilation, when she sees a vision of her lover Lorenzo, “It was a vision.—In the drowsy gloom, / The dull of midnight, at her couch’s foot / Lorenzo stood... (XXXV).

Like Endymion and Lycius in the poems discussed earlier, even in this poem, it is unbearable to suffer separation from her lover, Lorenzo. If forced into severance, then even a lady like Isabella would not escape the adverse impact, as her “youth and beauty” would be “thrown aside” (LVII). Humans are not immortal but are confronted by death, as is represented by “dying hour” and “dead eyes,” forcing them to oblivion at the hands of the passing time (LVII). Isabella, though, demonstrates her autonomy through defiance of her brothers’ authority when she asserts her identity after the pot being stolen from her through “...O cruelty, / To steal my basil-pot away from me!” (LXIII). The pot of basil symbolises through its symbolic connotation of both life (plant) and death (pot itself) that holds Lorenzo’s severed head.

4.3.6. Keats’s Odes

The pervasive sense of forgetfulness, annihilation and oneness continues in Keats’s odes, too. His odes present many instances of annihilation and oneness. Keats longs to forget, annihilate and be one with an ineffable spirit like that of the nightingale in “Ode to a Nightingale.” It is hidden from his sight but exists only in an audible state somewhere in the forest, “Fade far away, dissolve, and quite forget / What thou among the leaves hast never known...” (Stanza 3). Only securing oneness with the nightingale will help him win freedom from the phenomenal to the spiritual world, where the experiences of “weariness, the fever, and the fret” are unknown (Stanza 3). Keats’s nightingale symbolises a divine essence covered behind an impenetrable veil symbolised by the dark and thick jungle that hides the bird. Nightingale thus symbolises the Kantian noumenal, which remains ineffable to human reason.

Keats's poem "**Ode on a Grecian Urn**" develops the theme of oneness and annihilation. "Thou, silent form, dost tease us out of thought / As doth eternity..." is a call to place two realms of physical and spiritual through eternity (**lines 44–45**). This is compared to eternity, which, through its infinity, combines all the realms. Keats's concept of imagination is similar to that of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Ibn Arabi makes imagination a bridge between the sensible and intelligible, whereas Kant makes it a mediating faculty between sensory perceptions and understanding. Keats means the same when he writes in "**Ode to Psyche**," "I see, and sing, by my own eyes inspired" (**line 43**). He offers his self to Psyche, "I will be thy priest, and build a fane / In some untrodden region of my mind..." (**lines 50–51**).

4.4. Immaterial and Material – Paradoxical Components of Cosmic Self

Keats's poem "Lamia" explores the interplay between immateriality and materiality, highlighting the constant interconnection between spiritual transcendence and earthly materiality. This analysis is situated within the framework of Ibn Arabi's mystical perspective and Kant's philosophical framework.

4.4.1. Lamia

Ibn Arabi pioneered the mystical framework of the Unity of Being. This framework is rooted in transcendence or emanation from a single source, allowing for a rich interpretation of both the material and the immaterial realms. The human self, when considered in a cosmic context, becomes a manifestation of the Divine essence in both the physical and non-physical realms. Keats says in "Lamia," "meads where sometime she might haunt, strewn rich gifts, unknown to any Muse," he inspires the idea of a mysterious and transcendent power inside the material world (**Part I, line 18**). The self thus transcends the ordinary and comprehends the divine mystery, otherwise unknown even to the most profound thinkers.

Kant's transcendental idealism offers a perspective on the distinctive coexistence of both the immaterial and material worlds. Human cognition is limited to the phenomenal realm. The

noumenal realm remains a mystery beyond our understanding. When Keats uses “Fancy’s casket,” being unlocked, he symbolises the capacity of the human imagination to transcend the phenomenal towards the noumenal (Part 1, Line 20). It lacks a physical existence, but it demonstrates the creative power of the human mind at work within the phenomenal or sensory experience.

The divine intervention of the god Hermes can be interpreted in various ways. In Ibn Arabi’s perspective, Hermes is a manifestation of the cosmic self symbolising *Khidhr*, an intermediary and an *isthmus* linking the material and immaterial realms. This divinity is symbolically represented by the luminous “throne of gold” (Part I, line 70). On the other hand, Kant, in his critical philosophy, would interpret Hermes as symbolising imagination and reason mediating between the phenomenal and noumenal realms. It is a moral will that regulates and longs for freedom and truth.

The regenerative cycle of development from immaterial to material and vice versa, as reflected by Lamia, “I was a woman, let me have once more a woman’s shape, and charming as before...” represents a dialectical relation. It suggests a journey of manifestations from the divine essence through various levels and finally into a physical state of the being (Part I, line 117). Lamia’s yearning for a material existence to project the self as a recognisable and identifiable entity rather than an abstract concept equally represents a Kantian emphasis on empirical experience.

Lamia’s dual nature symbolises an oscillation between reality and illusion. Lamia’s act of breathing over Lycius’s eyes accentuates her illusory and mysterious nature, “She breath’d upon his eyes, and swift was seen / Of both the guarded nymph near-smiling on the green (Part 1, lines 124–125). Keats has, however, undergone a deterioration with time under the material influence “the real are the dreams of Gods” (Part I, line 127). It is only the poetic imagination that can unlock the “guarded nymph” (Aphrodite) for Hermes, revealing the spiritual truths

otherwise hidden from human perception. The “dreams of Gods” also symbolise the yearnings of reason to understand the noumenal (Part I, line 127).

Despite a blending of the material and the immaterial, Lamia acknowledges the existential conundrum of transforming from the immaterial to the material form, “Finer spirits cannot breathe below / In human climes, and live...” representing Ibn Arabi’s denser physical realm (Part I, line 280). Keats also lists numerous attributes of Lamia, as well as her mysterious inner state that is symbolically represented by “mysterious sleights” and “a hundred thirsts” (Part I, line 285). The “finer spirits” are noumenal ideals that cannot be realised in the phenomenal realm of human existence, “That finer spirits cannot breathe below / In human climes, and live (Part 1, line 280–281).

The self suffers under the pain of estrangement from its immaterial source. It is the divine origin for Ibn Arabi, the moral or noumenal self for Kant and the ideal imagination for Keats. All these sources are immaterial. Lamia feels the same despite being surrounded by luxuries. She is unimpressed by the “misery in fit magnificence,” the “marriage song,” or the “pageants” all around her because she does not belong to the material world (Part I, line 109).

Apollonius is a man of philosophy. He stands out amongst the luxuriant and jubilant crowd, displaying an insight and moral control of a philosopher. Apollonius symbolises rational inquiry that can penetrate deeper into the immaterial through the “severe” gaze (Part I, line 157). He is the ideally perfect human for Ibn Arabi and Kant, who can penetrate and combine an understanding of the material and immaterial realms within himself.

Keats's exploration in "Lamia" presents a rich tapestry of allusions associated with the frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Keats’s lines, “His spirit pass’d beyond its golden bourn / Into the noisy world almost forsworn...” align with the profound concepts of Ibn Arabi and Kant (Part II, lines 32–33). Ibn Arabi and Kant do not deny the existence of material and immaterial realms, with a difference that Ibn Arabi binds those worlds into a single entity, but

Kant makes those exist independently of each other. Lamia also combines or lives in both the material and immaterial worlds, “Her throat was serpent, but the words she spake / Came, as through bubbling honey, for Love’s sake...” (Part I, lines 64–65).

Keats presents three sets of characters. The accessible physical realm, symbolised by Lycius, the inaccessible noumenal realm, represented by Lamia (though within herself she represents both the material and immaterial realms) lastly the philosopher Apollonius, who can penetrate both the material and immaterial realms. The difference between Lamia combining material and immaterial is that she conjured this duality, but Apollonius has achieved this through knowledge, reason and insight. Lycius's dependence on sensory perception is evident when Apollonius derogatively calls him a “fool” because he is so easily tricked by the fabricated state of Lamia (Part II, lines 291–295).

4.4.2. Hyperion

Keats’s narrative poem “Hyperion” illustrates the relationship between the material and immaterial. This poem can draw many parallels with the *Akbarian* and Kantian philosophical frameworks. The fallen Saturn in “Hyperion” represents the Fall of Adam from the ideal world of heaven. That is why he suffers from a severe existential crisis and is caught between the immaterial and material self. Material restraints can only bring helplessness, transitoriness and impermanence as Keats speaks through Saturn, “O aching time! O moments big as years!” (Book I, line 64). It manifests a divided identity.

Keats’s Saturn is derived from immaterial air and ocean. Saturn, being separated from the immaterial source, recalls painfully his source. The material world cannot circumscribe the truly immaterial essence of his self. Saturn hangs between the material and immaterial realms with a pain forever in his heart, “I have left / My strong identity, my real self, / Somewhere between the throne, and where I sit...” (Book I, line 114). But such a self as Saturn is, actually occupies an intermediary position between the material and immaterial realms. Keats

highlights this in a manner of the Kantian sublime, “space starr’d, and lorn of light,” reflecting an existence beyond the phenomenal realm (Book I, line 118). Saturn is from the heavens, but he is deprived of the heavenly light.

Kant uses a rational approach, but he also acknowledges its limitations. Saturn's dissolution into the “deep night” appears to signify the material self being subsumed by the vastness of the immaterial (Book I, line 357). Night represents a void and a gap. The act of losing oneself in a vast and dark void would be interpreted as a self surrendered by the divine will through the obliteration of material existence.

4.4.3. Endymion

Ibn Arabi argues in favour of gaining access to the immaterial by transcending material existence. Kant argues in favour of both the material and the immaterial worlds, where the self is identified through adherence to moral principles.

Keats's “**Endymion**” revolves around the themes of beauty, love and transcendence, exploring the realms of the material and immaterial. Keats is indirectly connected to the mystical precepts of Ibn Arabi and the philosophical propositions of Kant. Keats’s “Endymion” seems to swerve between the material and immaterial realms. Keats presents heaven as a converging point for all creation, connecting the material and immaterial. Keats populates his world with the “old trees” and the “daffodils” with the divine being immanent in these. Keats establishes a spiritual connection between the immaterial and material existence through reassuring phenomena, such as “clear rills” and a “shady boon” that provide solace to the “simple sheep” (Book I, lines 14–16).

Being a transcendental idealist, Kant posits that human cognition and perception are the primary means to understand the material and immaterial worlds. The tools to grasp in totality the immaterial or noumenal realm are not possible. Ibn Arabi and Kant argue that material acts as a veil due to density (Ibn Arabi) and due to rational limitation (Kant), hiding the immaterial

from humans. Moreover, Ibn Arabi holds that the material serves as a medium to the immaterial, being a theophany of the divine self (Ibn Arabi, 1980). The unknown ineffable Cynthia (the moon goddess) becomes a noumenal reality in Kantian philosophy. Ibn Arabi would interpret such beauty and grace as a manifestation of the immaterial divine in material beauty:

Yet still I feel immortal! O my love,
My breath of life, where art thou? High above,
Dancing before the morning gates of heaven?
Or keeping watch among those starry seven... (Book 2, lines 688-691).

The intercession of a perfect self, who has access to the material and immaterial, is presented through the character of Endymion's sister Peona. She becomes a spiritual guide like Apollonius (Lamia) or Oceanus (Hyperion) or the old maid (The Eve of St. Agnes), leading her brother "like some midnight spirit nurse" from pure noumenal attachments to the quiet forest land for contemplation (Book I, lines 414–415). Only contemplation to bring a balance between the material and immaterial would save Endymion from extinction. Keats symbolically represents this act of Peona as "guarding his forehead...from low-grown branches..." (Book I, line 416). She fills in the gap between the material and immaterial like an *isthmus*.

The poem presents a relationship between the material and the immaterial realms through the depiction of mortality and immortality. Endymion struggles to reconcile earthly life with his heavenly knowledge, reflecting a tension between the material and the immaterial. Keats says through Peona to Endymion, "thou dost know of things mysterious, / Immortal, starry; such alone could thus / Weigh down thy nature," which are the attributes of a self that gives in only to the immaterial (Book I, lines 505–507).

For Kant, the acknowledgement of immortality is not a necessary condition but rather rooted in the moral law (Kant, 1997). Peona and Endymion represent two opposite poles of existence. Endymion is entirely immersed in the idea of divinity and immateriality, but Peona only in the material realm. The moon (Cynthia) represents a state that combines both the material and immaterial in its celestial and spiritual association, such as “O Moon! old boughs lisp forth a holier din / The while they feel thine airy fellowship...” (Book III, lines 54–55).

Moon has the divine attribute of bringing the dead to life through a kiss:

O Moon! old boughs lisp forth a holier din

While they feel thine airy fellowship.

Thou dost bless every where, with silver lip

Kissing dead things to life... (Book III, lines 54–57).

Kant would find in the moon a source of the sublime that pleases by its beauty and overwhelms human faculties with shock. The moon combines both the *Akbarian* attribute of immanence (divine existence in the material and immaterial) and the Kantian attribute of aesthetic harmony, synthesising imagination and understanding.

Keats’s yearning to win release from the confines of the material world and get refuge in the immaterial world is reflected through “Endymion.” There is a longing to transcend the material existence which is fit for mortals, not for immortals, as Endymion says, “Let us ay love each other; let us fare / On forest-fruits, and never, never go / Among the abodes of mortals here below...” (Book IV, lines 630–633). Keats brings in both the material and the immaterial realms as attributes of the cosmic self, represented by the images of the moon, the pearls, and the characters of Endymion and Cynthia.

4.4.4. The Eve of St. Agnes

This poem also explores the question of material and immaterial. Porphyro's breath symbolises an *isthmus* connection between the material and immaterial "...frosted breath, / Like pious incense from a censer old..." (**Stanza I**). In Ibn Arabi's mystical framework, breath serves as a bridge between existence and the divine essence, materialising the constant regeneration of creation (**Chittick, 1989**). In Kantian philosophy, breath may be a complete phenomenal activity, but it also has a noumenal connection for being considered as indefinable (**Kant, 2006**).

"**The Eve of St. Agnes**" also offers imagery that brings a synthesis between the material and immaterial realms. Madeline's performance of fasting and prayer to summon her imaginary lover represents a connection between the two realms of material and immaterial existence through the spiritual act of meditation. Ibn Arabi makes meditation an integral part of the spiritual act that facilitates access to the immaterial realm. The material world is intrinsically significant due to its association with the divine. Kant views the material world as a conduit to gain access to the noumenal.

Initially, Madeline appears to have the material and immaterial converged in her character. She is a noumenal existence for Porphyro, who longs to be united with her. Similarly, Porphyro is a noumenal existence for Madeline, living beyond the material world of her own. When Porphyro prays, "all saints to give him sight of Madeline," he symbolically expresses a longing to unite with the noumenal (**IX**). Ibn Arabi would symbolise Madeline with a theophany as divine manifestation in the material realm, uniting in her the material and immaterial and located as an intermediary between the two realms. Kant would find in Madeline an object of aesthetic judgement combining in her the traits of beauty and sublime, a phenomenon and an example of moral purity.

Keats describes Madeline in mystical terms as "a glory, like a saint," whose mystical vision, kneeling in prayer, represents a longing for the immaterial through transcendence (**IX**). If Porphyro considers Madeline as a source of gaining access to the immaterial, so is Madeline,

who sees in Porphyro the object of love and access to the divine realm. The human self is so fragile when confronted with the dilemma between the material and immaterial; it gives up to the material. Madeline's tears symbolise the loss of the ideal and coming to accept the phenomenal existence (XXXIV). The "elfin storm from faery land..." facilitating the lovers' flight from the castle of the "barbarian hordes" becomes a material phenomenon out of the immaterial noumenal world to hide Madeline and Porphyro (XXXIX). Ibn Arabi and Kant would find in this storm a phenomenon that synthesises the material and immaterial realms as inseparable parts of reality.

Keats's poetry is a rich combination of the *Akbarian* and Kantian philosophies, making the material and immaterial responsible for a meaningful experience. Ibn Arabi is the pioneer of the Unity of Being between the material and immaterial. On the contrary, Kant is a dualist who holds that reality is dual, but he also believes in a single source.

4.4.5. Isabella; or, the Pot of Basil

Keats's poem "Isabella; or, The Pot of Basil" accentuates the sense of loss and separation, transitoriness, class division and reunion deeply associated with the materiality and immateriality. Keats particularly juxtaposes the material and immaterial through the characters of Lorenzo and Isabella, who represent immateriality, and Isabella's brothers, who symbolise materiality. Lorenzo and Isabella long for a romantic union, but Isabella's brothers pursue material wealth even at the cost of poor humans.

Keats loathingly portrays Isabella's despicable brothers. They thrive on the ancestral wealth built at the hands of the exploited class, "weary hands swelt / In torched mines and noisy factories..." evoking a sense of extreme marginalisation (XIV). Ibn Arabi would disapprove of this material exploitation, as a symbol of alienating humans from the immaterial and true source. This unacceptable exploitation would also be rejected by Kant to use humans as a means rather than as an end in themselves on moral grounds. The material wealth produces

internal emptiness, “Why were they proud?” of the “marble founts” and “red-lined accounts” turning Isabella’s brothers into slaves of the material (XVI). This kind of moral blindness would also be rejected by Ibn Arabi. The divine retribution is there for the deeds upon the material world. Lorenzo exists in spirit even after being murdered, “I am a shadow now, alas! alas!” as a sign of retribution(XXXIX).

The pot of basil used by Isabella to hide Lorenzo’s head invites interpretations in various ways. It can be compared to a phenomenal world as the pot and the noumenal world as the human head (LXI). The pot thus synthesises the phenomenal and noumenal realms, suggesting that material objects can serve as vessels for the immaterial. The dark forest where Lorenzo is murdered also represents the veil that helps the brothers to cover their crime. Such an act of murder would be condemned both by Ibn Arabi and Kant:

.....the murderous spite
Of pride and avarice,—the dark pine roof
In the forest, and the sodden turfed dell,
Where, without any word, from stabs he fell... (XXXVII).

Keats illustrates this divine punishment through a Biblical allusion to hell, “a smoke from Hinnom’s vale,” aligning with Ibn Arabi’s concept of hell and paradise (XXXIII). Lorenzo’s head also symbolically represents her desire to unite with the noumenal. Her apparel of “stifling widow’s weed” symbolises the grief out of a desire for reunion (XXIX). Isabella’s brothers are entirely devoid of moral principle. They perpetrate another crime against humanity when they steal away the pot of basil. This act of theft is also an attempt to compromise Isabella’s moral autonomy.

4.4.6. Keats’s Odes

4.4.6.1. Ode to a Nightingale

Keats's "Ode to a Nightingale" provides a poignant example of the cosmic self through the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. The nightingale oscillates between the material and immaterial realms in its flight. The poem is conspicuously divided into three stages of development from the material to the immaterial and then to the material with the invocation, "Forlorn! The very word is like a bell / To toll me back from thee to my soul self..." These echoing words are emphasised by, "Adieu! the fancy cannot cheat so well / As she is fam'd to do, deceiving elf..." (Stanza 8).

The poem begins with the characteristic pain in the material world, "drowsy numbness" aching his senses (Stanza 1). Keats is then propelled into the noumenal realm by an immaterial spirit, a "light-winged Dryad" residing in the trees (Stanza 1). Its immortal song can transcend him into the immaterial realm. This wood nymph, the nightingale, is an intermediary or *isthmus* (Ibn Arabi), materially manifested and uniting all the creation or transporting them to the immaterial realm. The simultaneous existence of the corporeal world with "weariness, the fever, and the fret," and the incorporeal world with "forest dim," accommodating the "immortal bird," reflects the Kantian paradigm of the phenomenal and the noumenal realms (Stanza 1, 7). This noumenal world of the forest also eludes the poet's understanding. Ibn Arabi would idealise the bird more for its power to transcend humans to the immaterial realm. Keats seems to accept the existence of the material and immaterial realms side by side. It can be symbolically represented by the ancient wine "cool'd a long age in the deep-delved earth," and ever ready to the "brim" for expression (Stanza 2). This argument of combining the material and immaterial realms through poetry is reiterated with flight "on the viewless wings of Poesy" (Stanza 4). Keats appears to be more in the tradition of Kant than of Ibn Arabi. His desire for transcendence to the noumenal is transitory despite suffering an existential dilemma, forcing him to fall in love with an "easeful Death" (Stanza 6). He returns to his "sole self" towards the end and a reminder to himself, "Do I wake or sleep?" (Stanza 7).

4.4.6.2. Ode to Autumn

This ode also evokes a sense of the material and immaterial as dimensions of the cosmic self. Keats synthesises both the material and immaterial through the portrayal of images, such as “mists and mellow fruitfulness,” paralleled with the “the close bosom-friend” (stanza 1). The conspiracy begins between the material (the sun) and the immaterial (autumn). The sun symbolises the entity uniting the material realm (the earth) and the immaterial realm (the heaven). Material or phenomenal world, though, has its temporal and spatial limitations of being ephemeral because “warm days” will eventually finish (Stanza 1).

In the next stanza, Keats dissolves the boundaries. The autumn (immaterial) is descriptively defined in material terms, “careless on a granary floor” or sleeping soundly “on a half-reap’d furrow” (Stanza 2). Abstract phenomenon, such as time, is also described in a concrete sense, like the “patient look” and the “cyder-press” (Stanza 2).

Time exists only immaterially as a perceptive reality in Kant’s transcendental idealism, but it is metaphysical and relational in Ibn Arabi’s mystical framework. Keats’s depiction of time is also both perceptive (immaterial) and relative (material as well as immaterial) in “Ode to Autumn.” In the beginning, time is cyclical in “Season of mists and mellow fruitfulness,” but fleeting in “Where are the songs of Spring? Ay, where are they?” and then reflecting death and decay through “While barred clouds bloom the soft-dying day” (lines 1–26). The melancholic stillness of time symbolises the impending doom that the time on the material earth will eventually cease to exist.

4.4.6.3. Ode on Melancholy

“Ode on Melancholy” is another example of Keats looking for an intermediary between the material and immaterial realms. He presents melancholy as a medium that can associate both the material and immaterial, like a cosmic self in the philosophical frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. The material realm alone can only influence an unacceptable escape from pain over

impermanence, or it can entirely overcome it. Keats describes this by drowning “the wakeful anguish of the soul” through escape to “Lethe” or by drinking on the “ruby grape of Proserpine” and “wolf’s bane” (**Stanza I**). Such an escape by material means is unacceptable.

In comes Melancholy “Sudden from heaven like a weeping cloud” in the second stanza. It is immaterial and noumenal as long as it remains in the immaterial realm (from heaven), but it is also phenomenal and material when it comes down to the material realm (weeping cloud or rain). It is then a melancholic and poetic self that becomes the receiving ground for the immaterial melancholy descending from heaven in material form, like the raindrops. One can forget sorrow through losing oneself in the material objects like the “morning rose,” the “rainbow of the salt sand-wave,” and the “globed peonies” (**Stanza II**). However, these material objects also symbolise impermanence, death and decay. Such intrinsically impermanent objects will naturally bring lots of pain but little pleasure due to their impermanence. It is a proven fact that beauty “must die” and pleasure is ever ready to say goodbye (**Stanza II**). It is only the contemplative poetic genius who has the cosmic self to reveal the truth from behind the curtain where, “Veil’d Melancholy has her sovran shrine, / Though seen of none save him whose strenuous tongue / Can burst Joy’s grape against his palate fine... (**Stanza III**).

The material world exists in time and space in accordance with the mystical framework of Ibn Arabi as well as the philosophical propositions of Kant. Keats describes this paradoxical relation when he describes beauty as existing in the “very temple of Delight,” where “Veil’d Melancholy has her sovran shrine” (**Stanza III**). Keats’s “**Ode on Melancholy**” is thus a mystical and philosophical poem that dwells on the themes of realising the cosmic self in the transitoriness of this world with material and immaterial associations.

4.4.6.4. Ode to Psyche

It is the “*P*” which truly becomes a cosmic and unifying ground for the material and immaterial in Keats’s “**Ode to Psyche**.” The ode opens in a physically material setting where the

protagonists and nature are interwoven into an indistinguishable state of perfect union. Like natural surroundings, the immaterial (Psyche) and the material (Cupid) are also united, but their distinct characteristics are intact. Keats describes all this as “couched side by side in deepest grass...” under the shade of a material nature “whispering roof / Of leaves and trembled blossoms...” (lines 10–11). The noumenal experience of love is expressed through the images of “arms embraced” and “lips touch’d not, but had not bade adieu” (lines 16–17).

Psyche is the symbolic representation of an unacknowledged poet like Keats in immaterial form. This argument gets proof that, despite being divine, Psyche, like Keats, also lacks worshippers who could praise her divinity, “no shrine, no grove, no oracle, no heat / Of pale-mouth’d prophet dreaming...” (lines 34–35). However, it is the poetic self “*P*” who is endowed with the cosmic touch to unite both the material and immaterial and build a castle through imagination in “some untrodden region of...mind...” (lines 50–51).

Thus, in Keats’s “Ode to Psyche,” it is the poet who becomes the unifying factor for the material and immaterial through the cosmic association of both realms.

4.4.6.5. Ode on a Grecian Urn

This poem has several emblematic instances of the material and immaterial. The urn symbolises the material and immaterial. It synthesises both the dimensions through the axiomatic words, “Beauty is truth, truth beauty,—that is all / Ye know on earth, and all ye need to know” (Stanza V).

The ode sets the stage of material and immaterial combined in the urn from the very beginning when Keats says, “What leaf-fring’d legend haunts about thy shape / Of deities or mortals, or of both...” Keats, however, develops the first stanza from the material through natural surroundings and “mad pursuit...” (Stanza I). From the material, Keats moves into the immaterial when he says, “Heard melodies are sweet, but those unheard / Are sweeter...” (Stanza II).

Another overriding image is that of stillness and quietude. A sense of serenity is visualised by making the urn both material and an immaterial existence. The urn also connects the past through its present material existence as “still unravish’d bride of quietness,” telling stories not only of the forests like a “Sylvan historian” but also of the deities and Arcady (lines 1–10).

In short, Keats’s “Ode on a Grecian Urn” is the interplay between materiality and immateriality as integral to the cosmic self. It serves as an *isthmus* between the realms.

4.4.6.6. Ode on Indolence

This ode resonates with the questions of materiality and immateriality as facets of the cosmic self. This Ode, along with the Sonnet of the Elgin Marbles, can be considered a sequel to Keats’s famous “Ode on a Grecian Urn.”

Keats recounts “figures on a marble urn” by giving the urn a visibly material form, personifying the immaterial Love, Ambition and Poesy (lines 1–10). The paradoxical nature of the urn, being both material and immaterial with images from the ancient past, makes the urn cosmic. Ibn Arabi's approach connects the material and immaterial into one cosmic whole, whereas Kant maintains that they are independent of each other. The epithets like “drowsy hour” and “blissful cloud of summer-indolence” highlight the merging of the ephemeral self with the ethereal one (lines 11–20). The immaterial world alone remains ineffable as it is noumenal, as Keats compares those with being “muffled in so hush a mask” (line 12).

Towards the end, as it is with Keats, he dismisses the phantoms or ghosts from the immaterial realms through words like “adieu,” “farewell,” and “vanish,” accepting living on “cool-bedded in the flowery grass...” (lines 51–60).

4.5. Cosmic Self – Essence and Existence

Keats’s poetry raises existential questions about the essence and existence in the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. The following paragraphs analyse Keats’s poetry in terms

of the essence and existence as dimensions of the cosmic self, drawing on the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant.

4.5.1. Lamia

Keats highlights the questions about essence and existence in this poem. Lamia falls in love with Lycius and transforms herself into a dazzling woman from a serpent:

..... dazzling hue,
Vermilion-spotted, golden, green, and blue;
Striped like a zebra, freckled like a pard,
Eyed like a peacock, and all crimson barr'd... (Part I, lines 47–50).

She embodies in herself the duality of essence and existence, being both a serpent and a woman. This blurs the margin between a thing-as-it-appears and thing-as-it-is (Kantian appearances versus reality). But all existence is the manifestation of the real existence (combining both essence and existence in its being in Ibn Arabi's system, the divine). Lamia represents a serpent in real existence despite being a woman in apparent existence. But Lamia equally represents a woman in essence because her pre-serpent state was that of a woman. Lamia thus combines both essence (woman) and existence (serpent) in the world (woman and serpent). Keats recounts this through, "I was a woman, let me have once more / A woman's shape, and charming as before." (Part 1, lines 117–118). This longing to become a woman once again reflects a longing on her part to reconcile with her essence and real existence (woman again).

We know that anything beyond physical apprehension is noumenal. Noumenal is ineffable. Discovering ineffable reality (noumenal) is not possible, within this life at least, because it lies outside possible experience (space and time). Phenomenal existence (Ibn Arabi's borrowed or manifested and Kant's contingent or empirical) is a mere illusion for Ibn Arabi and an appearance for Kant. Keats describes the same point when Lamia (illusion or

appearance) confronts Apollonius, and flees “At the mere touch of cold philosophy...” (Part II, lines 235–223).

4.5.2. Endymion

In this narrative poem, Keats juxtaposes the earthly and heavenly images. Keats aligns with Ibn Arabi in invoking the divine forms as the essence of all creations, as symbolised through the unseen flowers and mighty palace:

O thou, whose mighty palace roof doth hang
From jagged trunks, and overshadoweth
Eternal whispers, glooms, the birth, life, and death
Of unseen flowers in heavy peacefulness ... (Book 1, lines 432–435).

Life, death and gloom represent experiences associated with living on the physical levels. The essence and real existence manifests itself through the physical world in the shape of “the living flowers” that Endymion is advised to recline upon. Keats thus demonstrates that the divine essence is revealed through the existence of flowers and other creations. This interplay of the seen and unseen mirrors Ibn Arabi’s notion of essence and existence. Keats also symbolically portrays life and death overtaking existence silently, illustrating that the human mind shapes reality.

Keats describes the existential yearning through a mysterious essence and existence symbolised by “den.” This source (den) lies outside the constraints of time and space. These gloomy dark regions are the origin of the soul as both essence and existence. The following lines in “Endymion” allude to the same longing:

There lies a den
Beyond the seeming confines of space
Made for the soul to wander in and trace
Its existence, of remotest glooms. (Book 1, 515–518).

Kant, though, does not acknowledge the divine source behind the existence (noumena); he accepts its unknowability. Kant considers things-in-themselves and things beyond human perceptions as unknown (noumena). Thus, Keats seems to agree with Ibn Arabi and Kant on this point.

Keats, as in the rest of the dimensions related to the cosmic self, brings in the role of intermediary and *isthmus* again in the dimensions of essence and existence. He assigns the poet this cosmic role to strike a balance and synthesis between the essence and existence. The poet serves as an intermediary between essence and existence by becoming a source of pleasure and comfort. A dreamer lives only in the realm of essence without taking existence into consideration, producing agitation in the human self. Keats proves his personal preferences for being a poet through the following lines:

The poet and the dreamer are distinct,
Diverse, sheer opposite, antipodes.
The one pours out a balm upon the world,
The other vexes it. (Book II, lines 35–42).

Keats's poetry offers a kind of self that, in the light of interpretation through Ibn Arabi's mystical philosophy, serves as a bridge called *Barzakh (isthmus)* between essence and existence. True happiness lies in being with the divine essence, turning humans into light (a symbol of knowledge and divine transcendence in mysticism). This *isthmic* relation between the essence and existence is expressed in the following lines:

Wherein lies happiness? In that which becks
Our ready minds to fellowship divine,
A fellowship with essence; till we shine,
Full alchemiz'd, and free of space. (Book 1, lines 778–790)

The above-quoted lines are more in line with Ibn Arabi than with Kant. Keats, though, has already let the readers know about the intermediary who is the poet between the essence and existence on account of imaginative and creative powers. Endymion's sister, Peona, symbolises rationality as Apollonius in "Lamia." She offers an interplay between essence and existence, who has the potential to hear like her brother Endymion:

Brother, 'tis vain to hide,
That thou dost know of things mysterious,
Immortal, starry; such alone could thus
Weigh down thy nature. (Book 1, lines 505–508).

Peona thus preserves the identity of the essence and existence intact, instead of being carried over either by the essence or the existence.

Keats further elaborates on the divine transcendence and immanence symbolised through the nymph. All existence is a manifestation of the true essence (here nymph transcending), pouring forth soul into those (soul is immanent in creation). Thus, the divine essence exists in every phenomenon in the physical realm. This *Akbarian* concept is expressed through the following:

The nymph arose: he left them to their joy,
And onward went upon his high employ,
Showering those powerful fragments on the dead.
And, as he passed, each lifted its head,
As doth a flower at Apollo's touch. (Book III, lines 787–791).

Keats recounts the "delicious symphonies" and "airy flowers" that combine the essence and existence. The impact of the divine essence (delicious symphonies) upon the world of existence (flowers) is a transformative influence on new life. Keats describes the same, "Delicious

symphonies, like airy flowers / Budded, and swell'd, and, full-blown, shed full showers / Of light, soft, unseen leaves of sounds divine" (Book III, line 803–805).

Manifested existence is affected by time. Time can only affect physical existence, but the essence always remains untouched. Essence (Ibn Arabi) and noumena (Kant) are located outside time and space. However, existence is located within time, unfolding its progress (Ibn Arabi) and covering all experiences (Kant). Thus time pervades all phenomena. Being in existence in the physical realm, the only factor making one locate outside time and space is contact with the essence. It is the synthesis between the essence and existence as Oracle reminds Endymion due to his longing for the essence despite being a contingent existence himself:

Hence shalt thou quickly to the watery vast;
And there, ere many days be overpast,
Disabled age shall seize thee; and even then
Thou shalt not go the way of aged men;
But live and wither, cripple and still breathe
Ten hundred years: (Book III, lines 556–561).

Keats portrays images related to life and death. Keats compares death to the reanimation, by "...pure wine / Of happiness..." which is a union achieved between Endymion (existence) and Cynthia (essence) (Book III, lines 806–807). It is thus the establishing of a connection between eKant rejects this approach to life and death because he emphasises the state of existence in this phenomenal realm more than the state of essence in the ineffable noumenal realm.

4.5.3. Hyperion

Material existence offers a veil to hide the essence (Ibn Arabi, 1980). The noumenal remains ineffable because it transcends reason (Kant, 1998). This separation from the essence and a desire to reunite is found in Keats's poem "Hyperion." The loss of essence by the Titans is

influenced by external forces (the Olympians). However, this loss symbolically represents two distinct poles of the essence and existence within a single human self. The combination of both makes a perfect being like Apollo, who combines in his self the essence and existence. Keats symbolically represents this segregation and combination of essence and existence through different gods. Saturn represents complete loss of contact with essence and persisting in existence only; Hyperion symbolises existence, but he is trying to cling to the essence; Mnemosyne is the example of perfect essence; Apollo presents a synthesis between essence and existence. Saturn describes this loss from essence and transformation into mere existence in the following words:

.....I am gone
Away from my own bosom: I have left
My strong identity, my authentic self,
Somewhere between the throne and where I sit
Here on this spot of earth. (Book I, lines 112–116).

The state of Hyperion, who is looking over his dying world, is only to be taken over by the more powerful gods. He will not easily reconcile with this humiliation at the hands of the Olympian gods. He fumes with fear. All this is, however, subject to change since only existence separated from the essence cannot withstand the onslaught of essence. Keats describes Hyperion's state in the following words:

O lank-eared Phantoms of black-weeded pools!
Why do I know ye? why have I seen ye? why
Is my eternal essence thus distraught
To see and to behold these horrors new?
Saturn is fallen, am I too to fall?
Am I to leave this haven of my rest... (Book 1, lines 230–235).

Keats also describes pure essence Mnemosyne (the goddess of memory). Her description carries a state of majesty and quietude. She is as mysterious and indefinable as an essence (Ibn Arabi) or noumena (Kant) should be, as Keats writes:

Mnemosyne!
Thy name is on my tongue, I know not how;
Why should I tell thee what thou so well seest?
Why should I strive to show what from thy lips
Would come no mystery? (**Book III, lines 82–86**).

However, it is the Olympian god Apollo who combines in himself the attributes of both the essence and existence. He achieves the state of godhood (essence and existence) through a painful process of becoming. Keats's description of this realisation is no less than a mystic experience. Keats states how Apollo synthesises essence and existence in the following words:

Names, deeds, gray legends, dire events, rebellions,
Majesties, sovran voices, agonies,
Creations and destroyings, all at once
Pour into the wide hollows of my brain,
And deify me, as if some blithe wine
Or bright elixir peerless I had drunk,
And so become immortal. (**Book III, lines 114–120**).

Keats becomes a complete *Akbarian* in the above excerpts from "Hyperion." Keats follows in the mystical tradition, accepting that the true essence is left in heaven. This estrangement from the epicentre naturally leads him to the comparison with a "dead leaf" resting at the spot where it falls voicelessly (**Book I, lines 10–18**).

4.5.4. The Eve of St. Agnes

Keats describes essence and existence in his poem “The Eve of St. Agnes.” In this poem, the tension is highlighted through the characters of Madeline and Porphyro. Madeline symbolises purity, love and the essence of the human self. She gets attracted to the mysterious and dreams.

Keats reflects her state of essence through her somnambulism:

.....one Lady there,
Whose heart had brooded, all that wintry day,
On love, and wing'd St. Agnes' saintly care,
As she had heard old dames full many times declare. (Stanza V).

However, Keats does not give preference to essence at the cost of existence. An ideal self having cosmic significance is the one which combines both the essence and existence. Despite being so pure and innocent, Madeline gives in easily to the temptation of Porphyro. Porphyro represents the existence and earthly state of the human self. His playing on the lute in Madeline's ear while she is fast asleep symbolises his physical needs, “He play'd an ancient ditty, long since mute / In Provence call'd, “La belle dame sans mercy:” / Close to her ear touching the melody...” (Stanza XXXIII). Madeline gives in to this temptation despite being disillusioned initially about what Porphyro is in reality when she wakes up, “Now wide awake, the vision of her sleep / There was a painful change...” (Stanza XXXIV). This contrast in the composition, Madeline being essence and Porphyro being existence, is further accentuated through this disillusionment, “Ah, Porphyro!” said she, “but even now / ... / How chang'd thou art! how pallid, chill, and drear!” he has become (Stanza XXXV). The poem ends on a note of complete union between Madeline (essence) and Porphyro (existence) when they disappear from the people, symbolising mere existence. Keats describes this state as follows:

And they are gone: ay, ages long ago
These lovers fled away into the storm.
That night the Baron dreamt of many a woe,

And all his warrior-guests, with shade and form
Of witch, and demon, and large coffin-worm,
Were long be-nightmar'd. (**Stanza XLII**).

Keats moves from the Kantian separation of essence (concept) and existence (experience) to the *Akbarian* perspective that essence and existence are the same. Existence becomes a manifestation of the essence towards the end.

4.5.5. Isabella; or, The Pot of Basil

Keats's poem "Isabella; or, The Pot of Basil" deals with the matter of essence and existence. This poem also portrays essence and existence through different characters. It is a portrayal of human suffering and longing, such as Isabella's lamentation echoes the acknowledgement of the human condition in existence. Keats often builds a bridge through synthesis between essence and existence, but he either fails or deliberately ignores bringing any union between these in this poem. For instance, the poem ends on a tragic note:

And so she pined, and so she died forlorn,
Imploring her Basil to the last.
No heart was there in Florence but did mourn
In pity of her love, so overcast. (**Stanza LXIII**).

Keats sets this tragic note even in the midst when Isabella's brothers steal away the pot of basil from her. This act of stealing symbolises existence (Isabella's brothers) taking over essence (Isabella's love symbolised by the basil plant and Lorenzo's severed head) and entirely without accepting it as an equal dimension of the perfect and cosmic self (The Pot of Basil). Keats describes this in the following words:

Yet they contriv'd to steal the Basil-pot,
And to examine it in a secret place:
The thing was vile with green and livid spot,

And yet they knew it was Lorenzo's face... (*Stanza LX*).

Isabella's brothers symbolise existential and carnal desires without an iota of essence. Keats describes them scathingly. They had been entirely taken over by greed and turned into a state of dehumanisation. Keats defines them as utter villains and hypocrites. One can draw parallels between Isabella's brothers and Madeline's courtiers in "The Eve of St. Agnes." Keats dedicates a whole stanza to the pride of these villainous characters in the following terms:

Why were they proud? Because their marble founts

Gush'd with more pride than do a wretch's tears?—

Why were they proud? Because fair orange-mounts

Were of more soft ascent than lazarus stairs?— (*Stanza XVI*).

Keats does not condone Isabella forgetting entirely the touch with existence in her desire to rejoin with essence. Union must be won between both the essence and existence, and not with the essence only:

And she forgot the stars, the moon, and sun,

And she forgot the blue above the trees,

And she forgot the dells where waters run,

And she forgot the chilly autumn breeze... (*Stanza LIII*).

A union, though, is temporarily achieved when Lorenzo's severed head is secretly kept in a pot of basil. Isabella constantly waters the plant with her tears:

She wrapp'd it up; and for its tomb did choose

A garden-pot, wherein she laid it by,

And cover'd it with mould, and o'er it set

Sweet Basil, which her tears kept ever wet... (*Stanza LII*).

4.5.6. Keats's Odes

“Ode on a Grecian Urn,” “Ode to a Nightingale,” “Ode to Psyche,” “To Autumn,” “Ode on Melancholy,” and “Ode on Indolence” present Keats’s perspective on the essence and existence. Ibn Arabi and Kant can be interlinked thematically through various images in these odes.

4.5.6.1. Ode on Melancholy

Keats’s “Ode on Melancholy” revolves around the themes of essence and existence. It accentuates the idea that the existence (Ibn Arabi’s contingency and Kant’s lived experience) of every material phenomenon rests in impermanence for Keats (Ibn Arabi, 1989; Kant, 1998). Essence and existence are thus ontological for Ibn Arabi but ontological and epistemological for Kant. In this ode, Keats accepts existence as a lived experience from the very beginning by symbolising his rejection through “Lethe,” “wolf’s-bane,” and “nightshade” while accepting existence in its entirety (Stanza I). It also aligns with Ibn Arabi’s framework, postulating that existence is contingent upon essence. For instance, impermanence and melancholy are lived experiences with permanence to neither.

Everything has its essence in heaven, as Keats says, “melancholy fit shall fall / Sudden from heaven like a weeping cloud...” (Stanza II). It accentuates Ibn Arabi’s concept of the divine essence breathing through every existence between heaven and earth. Keats tries to overcome this reminder of impermanence by immersing himself in the beauty of existence symbolised as “morning rose,” “rainbow,” and “globed peonies,” despite the impermanence of these phenomena (Stanza II). These are signs of manifestations and self-disclosure. But Kant defines these as simple existence in the phenomenal realm. In “Ode on Melancholy,” Keats produces images of transitoriness and death, such as “Beauty that must die,” and pleasure “turning to poison” (Stanza III). The ode then concludes with a powerful message acknowledging those who have the strength to synthesise permanence and impermanence, “shall taste the sadness of her might, / And be among her cloudy trophies hung” (Stanza III).

While connecting the ending lines of Keats with the other odes, it is obvious that such a synthesis can be brought around by none other than a poet.

4.5.6.2. Ode on a Grecian Urn

The same theme of essence and existence as dimensions of the cosmic self echoes through Keats's "Ode on a Grecian Urn." This ode links permanence, impermanence and yearning for permanence. The urn symbolises essence and existence, whereas all the images on its surface represent existence. The urn becomes a symbol of essence and art when Keats describes it as "still unravish'd bride of quietness," and "foster child of silence and slow time" because he conveys immortality by portraying the urn as untouched by earthly time (**Stanza 1**). However, Keats makes the urn subject to creeping time and silent progress as existence. Urn also fits in with the *Akbarian* notion that considers all creation, despite being bound by space and time, as manifestations of the divine reflected through the concrete existential image of the "flowery tale" (**Stanza 1**).

In the philosophical paradigm of Kant, the Grecian urn and images upon it represent sensory objects in existence. These symbolise existence as empirical phenomena. The same urn, however, begins taking the form of both essence and existence when Keats invokes a comparison between the heard and unheard melodies:

Heard melodies are sweet, but those unheard
Are sweeter; therefore, ye soft pipes, play on;
Not to the sensual ear, but, more endear'd,
Pipe to the spirit ditties of no tone... (**Stanza 2**).

The breath of essence starts manifesting itself slowly and invisibly, like Ibn Arabi's divine disclosure, through sweet melodies and soft pipes in the second stanza. Keats elicits imagery like "mysterious priest," "green altar," and "lowing heifer" to evoke a profound sense of existential realities frozen in time (**Stanza 4**). Even the priest becomes a mere existence in time,

guiding the flock. It is only the urn as a piece of art that combines essence and existence. Keats emphasises this message through a paradoxical statement towards the end of the ode, “Beauty is truth, truth beauty” (Stanza 5). Through this powerful ending, Keats makes art as foundation behind the ontological and epistemological unity between essence and existence.

4.5.6.3. Ode to a Nightingale

Keats’s “Ode to a Nightingale” also explores the theme of essence and existence as dimensions of the cosmic self through various images. In this poem, Keats symbolises essence through the nightingale’s song (ineffable, noumenal), existence through intoxicants (physical, temporary, world of suffering) and synthesis of essence and existence through art, poetry (physical and spiritual).

The nightingale becomes a “light-winged Dryad,” combining both essence and existence through transcendence and immanence, reflected through her ability to sing of the “melodious plot of beechen green” (Stanza 1). It becomes as melodious as the soft pipes in “Ode on a Grecian Urn.” The nightingale thus becomes a divine manifestation of the true essence through this melodious symphony, inspiring union. This song also becomes Kant’s noumenal reality due to its ineffable nature. Keats longs to “fade away” and transcend existence for essence with the help of “draught of vintage” or with the help of “viewless wings of Poesy,” thus evoking a sense of sensory perception with the supra-sensory pursuit (Stanza 2 & 3).

Kant accepts the limitations of human reason. The song of the nightingale becomes a symbolic representation of universal essence for its immortality, “heard / In ancient days by emperor and clown alike” (Stanza 3). The nightingale also represents a temporary existence, but its song demonstrates the immortality of the essence. It is the same aesthetic ideal as Kant’s, characterised by universality and timelessness (Kant, 1998).

Keats's poetry offers a rich tapestry of Ibn Arabi's Unity of Being. It combines both the realms of existence and essence. Keats also accentuates the ontological and epistemological attributes of essence and existence.

4.5.6.4. Ode to Autumn

Keats's "Ode to Autumn" elaborates on the cyclical process of life that inspires a deep sense of essence and existence. Keats symbolises essence through autumn, existence through autumnal labour and a combination of essence and existence through a reconciliation in the cyclical process of seasons. In the beginning, it evokes a sense of conception and pre-nativity by sensual imagery with the sun being in a state of conspiracy with the earth. It impregnates the "mellow fruitfulness" and "swell the gourd and plump the hazel shells" (**Stanza 1**). In the *Akbarian* framework, these images describe the sun and the physical nature as essence and existence. The sun symbolises the divine essence, and the earth the physical existence. Kant's concept of essence is more akin to a conceptual understanding (what-ness) and of a phenomenal object (that-ness).

While describing the autumn in its existential state, Keats presents it in the autumnal labour having a state of passive immobility, such as "sitting careless on a granary floor" being "[d]rows'd with the fume of poppies," to a state of active mobility (**Stanza 2**). In Ibn Arabi's framework, it becomes a moment of repose and stillness with the autumn visibly existing as a divine manifestation and emanation through every phenomenon of existence. In Kant's transcendental idealism, these natural images represent existence in the phenomenal world with the conceptual frame of essence associated with the autumn. The autumnal sights also become existential realities, as reflected in the physical images of "barred clouds bloom the soft-dying day" when "small gnats mourn" and the "red-breast whistles" (**Stanza 3**).

Keats ends this ode on a note of reconciliation between the essence and existence, with the “gathering swallows” twittering in the sky to bid farewell to the autumn. However, the essence of autumn will re-emerge in the next autumn.

4.5.6.5. Ode to Psyche

Keats’s “Ode to Psyche” visualises through different images the essence and existence as facets of the cosmic self. Keats symbolises essence through Psyche, existence through her neglected presence and the combination of both the poetic imagination that “will be thy priest, and build a fane / In some untrodden region of my mind...” (lines 50–51).

Keats invokes “O Goddess!” he allows the essence of the soul to rest in the divine and cosmic whole (line 1). Psyche becomes a symbol of the universal essence being transcendent and immanent in all creation. Keats begins the ode in a completely physical setting, describing Psyche and Cupid lying in each other’s arms as existence:

Saw two fair creatures, couched side by side
In deepest grass, beneath the whisp’ring roof
Of leaves and trembled blossoms, where there ran
A brooklet, scarce espied... (lines 9–12).

Here, an apparent unity is achieved through Cupid, the “winged boy,” and Psyche, the “happy dove” (lines 21–22). However, it is the unity of the material and immaterial only.

The goddess Psyche is a late arrival in the mythological system. Keats describes this through “Too late for antique vows” and “Too late for the fond believing lyre” (lines 36–37). She is representative of an age when essence and existence are being looked at with suspicion and scepticism. Keats then moves on to his characteristic concept about imagination and poetry. It is the human mind which combines both essence and existence. Only the human mind has the capacity, and that is why, being a poet, Keats offers himself with the following words:

Yes, I will be thy priest, and build a fane

In some untrodden region of my mind,
Where branched thoughts, new grown with pleasant pain,
Instead of pines shall murmur in the wind... (lines 50–53).

Keats envisions not only Ibn Arabi's mystical framework, founded on the cosmic unity of essence and existence, but also Kant's epistemological viewpoint, with no apparent connection between essence and existence. Keats often shares many aspects of essence and existence with Ibn Arabi and Kant. However, he also develops his concept as well which is more tilted towards bringing a synthesis.

4.6. Cosmic Self through the Intercession of Love and Beauty

Keats presents his concept of love and beauty through different characters in his poetry. The following sections highlight Keats's approach to love and beauty in the philosophical frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. To recapitulate, Ibn Arabi considers love and beauty as the divine manifestations. Love is the cause of creation, and beauty is the manifestation of the divine reflected through balance and harmony. Kant considers love as guided by reason and moral duty. Beauty generates disinterested pleasure as pleasure for its own sake. It also leads towards generating moral values.

4.6.1. Lamia

Love and beauty are Keats's favourite themes. His main characters represent two counterpoles, with one side as love and beauty, and the other as the opposite. The characters in love long to be one with the object of love, though accepting its pitfalls. In "Lamia," every character except Apollonius is looking for love inspired by beauty. The poem begins with Lamia pining with love for Lycius, followed by the god Hermes. Lycius is also infatuated by Lamia's beauty and falls in love with her. Lamia's beauty is described suggestively by Keats as a "demon's mistress," a "lady elf," with stars on her head:

Her head was serpent, but ah, bitter-sweet!

She had a woman's mouth with all its pearls complete:

And for her eyes: what could such eyes do there

But weep, and weep, that they were born so fair? (Part 1, lines 59–62).

Keats describes the beauty of the nymph, Aphrodite, whom the god Hermes loves passionately.

She inspires worship from all "Satyrs," the sea god Triton pours "Pearls" on her feet:

And in those meads where sometime she might haunt,

Were strewn rich gifts, unknown to any Muse,

Though Fancy's casket were unlock'd to choose.

Ah, what a world of love was at her feet! (Part I, lines 18–21).

Keats makes this beauty lead to love. Keats links love with the ethereal and ephemeral. Love is divine as that of Hermes, but it is otherwise as that of Lycius and Lamia. Lamia yearns to transcend into a human form through love, like the divine manifestation. The way to secure this union is to transcend essence and existence, material and immaterial.

Keats portrays Lamia's love as having a hypnotic and trance-like influence upon Lycius. Although this kind of love may be idealised by Ibn Arabi, who advises annihilation in love, Kant may object on the grounds of losing control over reason and neglecting moral duty towards oneself as an individual and as part of a community. Keats compares this trance-like state of Lycius, when Lamia kisses him on his lips, to a "mesh" that tangles Lycius. What follows is described in the following words:

And as he from one trance was wakening

Into another, she began to sing,

Happy in beauty, life, and love, and every thing,

A song of love, too sweet for earthly lyres,

While, like held breath, the stars drew in their panting fires. (Part I, lines 296–300).

However, this love also takes a heavy form in the case of Lycius. He longs to get hold of the divine and cosmic strength under the influence of love. Keats uses imagery from the earthly to the heavenly to fitly describe Lycius's motivation behind love. Such a love may be idealised by Ibn Arabi, but not by Kant, who would reject it on the point of entirely giving in. Keats writes with reference to Lycius:

My silver planet, both of eve and morn!
Why will you plead yourself so sad forlorn,
While I am striving how to fill my heart
With deeper crimson, and a double smart? (Part II, lines 48–51).

Keats's approach towards love in "Lamia" can be understood by a few defining lines in the poem. Keats juxtaposes love and reason by, "His phantasy was lost, where reason fades / In the calm'd twilight of Platonic shades" (Part I, lines 234–235). At another place, Keats compares love in a hut with love in a palace, with the one demanding sacrifice and the other pain:

Love in a hut, with water and a crust,
Is—Love, forgive us!—cinders, ashes, dust;
Love in a palace is perhaps at last
More grievous torment than a hermit's fast:— (Part II, lines 1–4).

All this is contrasted with the philosophy. Keats becomes critical of the rational thinkers as symbolised by the character of Apollonius in "Lamia." Such a philosophy has corrupted the mysteries in heaven and rationally interpreted every natural phenomenon. The rainbow does not stand as beautiful and romantic as it used to be in the past. Keats describes this philosophical impact upon human thinking as clipping its "wings" in addition to:

.....Do not all charms fly
At the mere touch of cold philosophy?

There was an awful rainbow once in heaven:

We know her woof, her texture; she is given

In the dull catalogue of common things. (Part II, lines 229–233).

It is only Apollonius, the philosopher, who has the insight to reveal the truth about Lamia. Even Lamia gets scared at his presence. Apollonius tries to pull Lycius out of Lamia's trance-like influence by reminding him:

“Fool! Fool!” repeated he, while his eyes still

Relented not, nor mov'd; “from every ill

Of life have I preserv'd thee to this day,

And shall I see thee made a serpent's prey?” (Part II, lines 295–298).

Only a rational influence like that of Apollonius will disclose the true essence of Lamia being a serpent. On the surface, Keats appears to criticise Lamia for her dual nature, being a serpent in human form, but in reality, she becomes representative of art, poetry, imagination and beauty coming under scepticism due to the cold philosophy pioneered by people like Newton, etc. The result is that humans have stopped looking for metaphorical and symbolic meanings in natural phenomena:

Philosophy will clip an Angel's wings,

Conquer all mysteries by rule and line,

Empty the haunted air, and gnomed mine—

Unweave a rainbow, as it erewhile made

The tender-person'd Lamia melt into a shade. (Part II, lines 234–238).

Keats's poem “Lamia” is thus written in the tradition of a mystic like Ibn Arabi rather than a philosopher like Kant. Love and beauty strike a relation between other dimensions of the cosmic self. Philosophical reason, however, prevails over love in the end.

4.6.2. Endymion

Keats's poem "Endymion" also accentuates the tension between reason and love. It sets the aim from the very beginning of the poem through an idiomatic expression, "A thing of beauty is a joy for ever" (Book I, line 1). Ibn Arabi argues that true beauty belongs only to the divine, whereas all earthly beauty is a manifestation of that true beauty. That is why true beauty leads to love, because the universe was created out of love. But Kant justifies love and beauty on the grounds of moral principle and reason. An analysis of the characters and various images in "Endymion" reveals how Keats uses beauty and love to combine the phenomenal (material, existence) and noumenal (immaterial, essence).

Keats divides the characters into three groups in "Endymion." Cynthia (the moon goddess, essence, noumenal, immaterial), together with Endymion (shepherd, existence, phenomenal, material), symbolise love, and Endymion's sister, along with Glaucus (a sea god repulsed in love by a nymph Scylla), symbolise earthly pragmatism and reason respectively. Endymion is presented as total love, consumed by his poetic obsession with love for the luminous and captivating moon goddess (portrayed in the form of heavenly Cynthia and earthly as an Indian Maid).

.....But there are
Richer entanglements, enthrallments far
More self-destroying, leading, by degrees,
To the chief intensity: the crown of these
Is made of love and friendship, and sits high
Upon the forehead of humanity. (Book I, lines 798–803).

Not only this passionate love, but also the poetic and deeply contemplative nature of Endymion is also suggestively described by Keats. He often appears as a personal portrayal of Keats himself, torn between high ideals (poetry and beauty) and physical requirements (earthly constraints). He shares with Peona his high ideals and ambition in the following words:

Peona! ever have I long'd to slake

My thirst for the world's praises: nothing base,

No merely slumberous phantasm, could unlace

The stubborn canvas for my voyage prepar'd— (Book I, lines 770–773).

But Keats does not recommend love without pain and suffering. It is only through the journey of pain and loss, like a mystic, that one comes to know true love. Keats describes this symbolically through the disappearance of Cynthia from Endymion's sight:

One morn she left me sleeping: half awake

.....

.....

But she was gone. Whereat the barbed shafts

Of disappointment stuck in me so sore,

That out I ran and search'd the forest o'er. (Book I, lines 480–485).

The beauty that catches Endymion in love is also suggestively described by Keats. Being in heavenly form, Keats compared it with the celestial imagery, and being in the earthly self, she is described in sensual terms. All this reflects the intentional use of material and immaterial imagery by Keats to prove his mystical and philosophical inclinations. The moon goddess Cynthia is described as follows:

What is there in thee, Moon! that thou shouldst move

My heart so potently? When yet a child

I oft have dried my tears when thou hast smil'd.

Thou seem'dst my sister: hand in hand we went

From eve to morn across the firmament. (Book III, lines 144–148).

The same moon, Cynthia, when she assumes the form of an Indian Maid, then Keats describes her quite differently. She becomes entirely physical and sensual. However, from being a

celestial figure who accompanies Endymion in all his adventures, she turns into a static character:

Her soft arms were entwining me, and on

Her voice I hung like fruit among green leaves:

Her lips were all my own, and—ah, ripe sheaves

Of happiness!..... (Book III, lines 271–274).

On the other hand, the voice of reason and sanity, Peona, is as pure in her earthly form as Cynthia is in her heavenly form. She parallels the moon goddess in her purity and beauty, but with an air of reality around her. Peona tries to pull her brother out of Cynthia's love because that forewarns of separation and suffering:

.....Brother, 'tis vain to hide

That thou dost know of things mysterious,

Immortal, starry; such alone could thus

Weigh down thy nature..... (Book I, lines 505–508).

Endymion consecrates love as a transformative influence on the self. It is compared to Cupid's arrow, "...upmounted in that region / where falling stars dart their artillery forth..." (Book I, lines 640–641). It also provides them with protection against any peril like it does with Endymion who feels "not fearful, nor alone, / But lapp'd and lull'd along the dangerous sky..." (lines 645–646). This follows the *Akbarian* concept of love as a source of connection between the human self and the divine. This may also be equated with universal order and harmony that can be brought with love as a moral and disciplining influence in the Kantian philosophy.

4.6.3. The Eve of St. Agnes

Love liberates after securing union. "The Eve of St. Agnes" explores love and beauty. The poem develops distinctly in two phases that can be termed as pre-union and post-union of the lovers. The characters symbolising love, such as Madeline, as well as Porphyro and the

characters representing reason, such as old maid Angela and the aged beadsman, experience a noticeable change. However, the characters indifferent to love remain the same, such as Madeline's courtiers and her family. The story is developed through love thriving in the hearts of those who are miles apart and detached, like Madeline and her idealised lover Porphyro. Porphyro yearns to meet his beloved in person. He embarks on a perilous journey through a murderous world in order to have a union with his romanticised beloved, Lady Madeline.

The pre-union stage is marked by different Porphyro, Madeline and Angela, the old maid. The poem opens with the aged beadsman as alive and having seen all in his life. Keats uses the same image of death to close the poem in order to heighten a sense of the fleeting time. The love of Porphyro is described as pure and passionate. He can risk his life for Madeline, caring not in the least for his life or betraying even the least of fear:

For him, those chambers held barbarian hordes,
Hyena foemen, and hot-blooded lords,
Whose very dogs would execrations howl
Against his lineage..... (Stanza X).

Not only this, even Madeline is portrayed as a pure, angelic and innocent soul caring not for anyone. She harbours deep love for her idealised love Porphyro and prays for union or a single sight of him on a night of ritual like that of St. Agnes and "sigh'd for Agnes' dreams, the sweetest of the year." In the same stanza, Keats compares her purity and beauty to the divine, whereas she is oblivious to everything around her:

Full of this whim was thoughtful Madeline:
The music, yearning like a God in pain,
She scarcely heard: her maiden eyes divine,
Fix'd on the floor, saw many a sweeping train
Pass by..... (Stanza VII).

The old maid Angela is also portrayed as the one who is all praise for Porphyro for his daring act of sneaking into the palace despite being a poor soul herself, “A poor, weak, palsy-stricken, churchyard thing, / Whose passing-bell may ere the midnight toll (Stanza XVIII). Keats describes Madeline’s family and the courtiers in the most despicable comparisons, like that of Isabella’s brothers in “Isabella; or, The Pot of Basil.” Keats writes about her family:

For him, those chambers held barbarian hordes,
Hyena foemen, and hot-blooded lords,
Whose very dogs would execrations howl
Against his lineage..... (Stanza X).

However, the action starts taking another twist when Porphyro expresses his desire to sneak into Madeline’s chamber. The old maid, who has so far been so cooperative and helpful, turns indifferent. She realises that very soon the night of ritual is going to become the night of disillusionment. She questions Porphyro’s wisdom and purity of emotion as if he is out of his senses:

A cruel man and impious thou art:
Sweet lady, let her pray, and sleep, and dream
Alone with her good angels, far apart
From wicked men like thee. Go, go!—I deem
Thou canst not surely be the same that thou didst seem. (Stanza XVI).

The union comes with disillusionment and a sense of repentance. Love remains an ideal, and beauty is secure as long as these are in the realm of essence as intangible. Keats's attitude to union is ambiguous in this poem. The same Porphyro who appears as a hero and ideal initially assumes an entirely different form. Keats draws the state of Madeline as if she is suffering remorse. Despite all that, she cannot bear separation any longer after having secured union with her lover:

How chang'd thou art! how pallid, chill, and drear!

Give me that voice again, my Porphyro,

Those looks immortal, those complainings dear!

Oh leave me not in this eternal woe,

For if thou diest, my Love, I know not where to go. (**Stanza XXXV**).

Keats becomes as sceptical as Kant about love. Love should be inspired by moral duty and reason, whereas beauty needs to bring order and harmony in the universe. Ibn Arabi presents love and beauty as reflections of the divine, in addition to being a source of unity with the divine and cosmic. Keats treats love in this poem as leading towards union and transcendence to the ineffable realm, as Keats ends the poem with, “And they are gone: ay, ages long ago / These lovers fled away into the storm” (**Stanza XLII**). Angela and the beadsman are both no longer alive.

4.6.4. Isabella; or, The Pot of Basil

Love and beauty also annihilate. Keats appears to symbolise different worlds through the characters in “**Isabella, or The Pot of Basil**.” One group of characters, such as Isabella and Lorenzo, symbolise love despite belonging to different classes of the rich and poor vying for harmony; the other, such as Isabella’s brothers, symbolise emptiness and inhumanity and are agents of chaos. There is another intermediary world represented by the pot of basil holding the whole world in order and harmony. The order founded on love is turned twice into chaos. Once the order having been disrupted when Lorenzo and Isabella got united, and later on, when the pot of basil was stolen after the order had temporarily been established. The pot of basil is representative of the world united into one due to love.

The representatives of love and harmony, Isabella and Lorenzo, are poetically delineated in imaginatively ideal form by Keats. For instance, Keats recounts Isabella by using the images associated with love, beauty and grief. The poem opens with a short description of the

protagonist, Isabella, being a pure and innocent soul, holding a young pilgrim, Lorenzo, in her love, “Fair Isabel, poor simple Isabel! / Lorenzo, a young palmer in Love’s eye!” (**Stanza I**). Keats sets the tragic tone from the very start of the poem in the first stanza, which is a result of beauty and love. The opening stanza also compares Lorenzo to a “palmer,” a medieval devotional pilgrim to the Holy Land.

Isabella’s brothers symbolise exploitation, agents of chaos and anti-love. They are obsessed with collecting material wealth even at the cost of humans, “For them the Ceylon diver held his breath, / And went all naked to the hungry shark... (**Stanza XV**). Their inhumanity is also displayed in graphic detail by Keats, “There was Lorenzo slain and buried in, / There in that forest did his great love cease...” Lorenzo’s murder sets in a chaos and a chain of events that takes everything in its fold. Lorenzo’s spirit appears because it cannot rest until his murder is avenged, “Ah! when a soul doth thus its freedom win, / It aches in loneliness—is ill at peace...” (**Stanza XXVIII**). Isabella’s brothers are haunted by their crime against humanity. The order is re-established temporarily when Isabella hides Lorenzo’s severed head in a pot of basil:

She wrapp’d it up; and for its tomb did choose
A garden-pot, wherein she laid it by,
And cover’d it with mould, and o’er it set
Sweet Basil, which her tears kept ever wet. (**Stanza LII**).

Love can metamorphose into another form. For example, Lorenzo’s decapitated head is placed in a pot of basil, which takes vitality from Isabella’s tears. Love thus becomes a cosmic principle. If nurtured and respected like Isabella worshipping the pot, it will continue to grow stronger. The pot of basil is a symbol of the world, holding together multiple forms throughout the cosmos. Isabella forgets all her pain because she hides Lorenzo’s severed head that keeps comforting her, “And she forgot the stars, the moon, and sun, / And she forgot the blue above

the trees...” (Stanza LIII). This forgetfulness is, however, not condoned by Keats. The order is disrupted once again. This time it is not going to turn in favour. This time, chaos will wrap up all the action, “...and so she pined, and so she died forlorn, / Imploring for her Basil to the last” (Stanza LXIII).

Keats also highlights how love is threatened by material wealth, a perspective that neither Ibn Arabi nor Kant would likely approve of, given their strong anti-materialist stance. It is symbolically represented by Isabella’s cruel brothers and the corrupt “ledger-men” with their “covetous and sly” looks, in contrast to the pure and transcendent love between Isabella and Lorenzo (Stanza XVIII). Despite a profound longing for the noumenal realm, love is deeply connected to the phenomenal realm.

4.6.5. Keats’s Odes

Keats’s odes highlight an ambiguous approach towards love and beauty. These are immortal if associated with the immaterial and essence, but mortal if linked to the material and existence. For instance, the bird becomes immortal only when associated with the song (symbolic of creative art, poetry), whereas the nightingale symbolises the poet in “Ode to a Nightingale”:

Thou wast not born for death, immortal Bird!
No hungry generations tread thee down;
The voice I hear this passing night was heard
In ancient days by emperor and clown... (Stanza 7).

However, all this fades in a while because annihilation and oneness are transitory until supported by a natural process. That is why Keats comes back from this state of fancy that “cannot cheat so well / As she is fam’d to do, deceiving elf...” (Stanza 8). These lines can be quoted as Keats’s approach towards love and beauty. These lines define love and beauty in terms of immortality (nightingale, despite being a material entity), cannot be brought down by

anyone (unconquerable), and have given pleasure to the common and the extraordinary throughout the ages (universal).

Keats makes love and beauty again a source of strength and comfort in “**Ode to Melancholy**,” when he advises to, “...glut thy sorrow on a morning rose, / Or on the rainbow of the salt sand-wave, / Or on the wealth of globed peonies...” or then start kissing deep on her lips (**Stanza 2**). In “**Ode to Autumn**,” love and beauty take the form of essence and existence when Keats says:

Who hath not seen thee oft amid thy store?
Sometimes whoever seeks abroad may find
Thee sitting careless on a granary floor,
Thy hair soft-lifted by the winnowing wind... (**Stanza 2**).

But in the end, when the poet reconciles with existence, the message of impermanence is accentuated with the “gathering swallows twitter in the skies” (**Stanza 3**).

4.7. Conclusion

This chapter explored different aspects of the cosmic self in Keats’s poetry through the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. The analysis also highlighted that there are close affinities in Ibn Arabi, Kant and Keats regarding the different dimensions of cosmic self. Keats thus provides a link between Ibn Arabi and Kant through his poetry.

Having established the key findings regarding the concept of the cosmic self in Keats from the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant, the study now proceeds to analyse data from Khan’s poetry in the next chapter.

CHAPTER FIVE

Khan's Interweaving of "I" with the Cosmic Whole

Either make me a god
And prostrate yourself to me
Or be prepared to face me
In a never-ending war.
With this sword in my hand
I have power over your fate...

(Sahibzada, 2014, pp. 314–319).

5.1. Introduction

This chapter presents a literary analysis of Khan's selected poems (English translation on the right and transliteration on the left side of the page). It explores Khan's concept of the cosmic self through the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Khan's poetry has been cited with page numbers from *The Pilgrim of Progress*.

5.2. Cosmic Self as Freedom and Autonomy

Khan's poetry highlights examples of freedom at both the individual and collective levels. He entertains a deep-seated longing for self-identification and self-realisation. It is both at an individual and national level, reflecting his association. A cosmic self is entirely incompatible

with living under a constant subservience to anyone else. Sometimes the self is found willing to submit to the heteronomous forces and outside authority. It is always for the sake of love or for the sake of the nation, such as “And to me, in smiling eyes, / My beloved gently spoke – / Why does one the heart surrender?” (pp. 6–7). There are many strands of freedom, as suggested by Ibn Arabi and Kant.

According to Ibn Arabi, freedom rests not in blind subservience to external physical or internal forces. It is in the merging of one's will with the divine's will, thereby annihilating one's egoistic and individual self, because it belongs to the divine and is its manifestation in the physical world. It is akin to the self that absorbs light from the outside and is illuminated. It transcends the limitations of the ephemeral world. He writes in “*Da Fariddon da Mur Khat*” (Letter from Faridoon's Mother):

When my soul absorbed the light,	<i>Daa zama rooh chi rukhaan shu da da stargi</i>
Both his eyes began to glow;	<i>yi krri bali</i>
This is the essence of my life –	
Sometimes laughter, often pain.	<i>Daa tasweer zama da zhwand dey</i>

(pp. 14–15).

Khan always employs images to emphasise a point. For instance, the following analogy aligns with Ibn Arabi's concept of freedom, which involves the total surrender of the individual to the will of the divine. In answering a question when asked what life is, Khan responds:

Music wailing its death?	<i>Daa saaz khpal marg na karri saandi</i>
Or fire burning bright?	
Are there resting spots around	<i>Ka yau ur dey chi baleegi</i>
For the journey that is life?	
Or does breathlessness abound –	<i>Da di tlu muqam dama shta</i>
With life-giving breath, deserting	
Fragile citadel of life?	<i>Ka da saa na saa takhteegi</i>
Is it drawing pails of water,	
On a Persian water-wheel –	<i>Mangooti ka da arat dee</i>
Some are filled as others empty,	
Their sweet contents on the ground...	<i>Sa dakeegi sa tasheegi</i>

(pp. 124–127).

Life is like the buckets on the Persian wheel going down, getting filled, coming up, spilling over, giving water to the living, going back, getting emptied and then refilled. It is an endless cycle of providing vital force to the living, getting annihilated, coming back, giving life, getting annihilated and so on. The secret is not in the bucket that is getting filled and emptied. It is not just a small part in the shape of the bucket, serving a role in this overall system of giving life through the process of filling and emptying. It is a bucket tied to the wheel, the wheel to the wooden lever, the lever to the bull, the bull controlled by the human, and the human by the divine. Gnostic belief is that the divine is too sublime to create this imperfect world of vice and virtue (Russell, 1945). The divine rather deposes a lesser power to create this world. This lesser power functions similarly to all the components in the system of the Persian wheel.

The image of the clay pot is repeated at another place in the same poem. Here, Khan hands himself entirely into the will of the divine. It exercises a creative and shaping force over everything between the heavens and the earth:

I have wagered on just one	<i>Maa ka daaw pa yau armaan sta, khpal</i>
Of your longing; indiscreet,	<i>zhwandoon tamaam</i>
To the potter I gave up	
All my consciousness, to make	<i>Maa khpal hosh kulaal la warka chi thri taa</i>
On the wheel, for you, a cup.	<i>la jurr krri jaam</i>

(pp. 18–19).

Khan portrays freedom through the images of the nightingale and the eagle, presenting them in contrasting terms. The nightingale, confined to the physical world, longs for freedom, while the eagle soars heavenwards, gaining freedom from the confines of the physical world. These birds represent the desire of the self to secure freedom from the materiality of the world through following different paths. In the case of the nightingale, it is to lose the self in the melodious and captivating songs, and in the case of the eagle, to lose self in soaring higher and higher in the heavens:

And the eagle's sheer swoop;	<i>Da shahbaz da wazar shagh dey pust</i>
And the <i>bulbul's</i> melody;	<i>suroona da bulbali</i>
And an emperor's proof of love;	<i>Daa suboot da shah da mini, daa zaari da</i>
An entreaty of an enslaved person.	<i>di Ghulam</i>

(pp. 14–15).

Kant propounds freedom with precepts founded upon the principles of autonomy and heteronomy. He rejects freedom that is achieved by giving up one's own will before the will of some outside force and accepts freedom that is rooted in one's own will in the universal moral principle. Such a freedom seeks the maximum moral good for others instead of oneself. What differentiates Khan in his concept of freedom that emerges from his poetry is its foundation resting not on the rational principle but on the emotional and spiritual experience with the longing to set oneself free from external constraints. Khan writes in "*Jannat aw Duniya*" (*The World and Heaven*):

Every moment, the hue of life	<i>Har saa'at har rang da zhwand, sta da wakht</i>
Is a helpless slave of time;	<i>bi kas ghulam</i>
And, in Heaven, says the priest,	<i>Aw jannat ki mula waai wakht ba wi zama</i>
Time, my slave is bound to be.	<i>ghulam</i>

(pp. 56–57).

Sometimes, while reading through Khan's poetry, one feels that fate plays a crucially dynamic role. It is to the extent that humans appear to be condemned by fate, which makes freedom seem like nothing but a subterfuge cast before them. Kant argues that freedom is based on the rational will. Khan veers slightly from Kant in considering freedom as being guided by the restrictions imposed by time and fate. It is the conflict between free will and fate. As Khan writes in "*Laka Wakhli Chi Mashoom*" (*Like a Little Child Who Plays*):

Time and life constitute Fate;	<i>Wakht aw zhwand dagha taqdeer dey</i>
From one fire to the next,	<i>La yau aura yi bal la butlam</i>
I have been led without respite.	<i>Daa zhwandoon wu ka yau daam wu</i>
Was this life, or but a snare	<i>Da uroonu da ghamoonu</i>
Of raging flames and grief...	

(pp. 98–99).

Khan’s poem, “*Da Khapiru Shahzagai*” (*The Fairy Princess*), is deeply immersed in light and colour. She does not have the courage either to let go of this, or she intentionally does not want to leave, unlike the human self. Ibn Arabi and Kant both agree on the rejection of material and worldly possessions that confine the self to earthly chains through lure and lustre. It is not the bondage of time and space only, but also of fate that clips the wings of humans and prevents them from free action:

Oh, music of the <i>anklet-bells</i> !	<i>Maa wi sar mi lugey sha la taa stargi mi</i>
Come, drown your melody,	<i>qurban</i>
Within the mystic strains of the lute,	<i>Raaza chi di da noor jahaan la dwaarra shoo</i>
And <i>tablas</i> rhythmic beats;	<i>rawaan</i>
And come oh beckoning will-o-wisp!	<i>Ay shrranga da gungroo da rabaab taal aw</i>
And lose your entity,	<i>rang ki doob sha</i>
Within the coloured sunbeams,	<i>Aw ay ur urakiya sa da nmar pa rang ki doob</i>
As they dance upon the sea.”	<i>sha</i>
It said, “I am a captive,	<i>Wi rang ranrra niwaley yem, maa dartlu ta</i>
Of both colour and the light,	<i>na prigdee</i>
And much as I would like to go,	<i>Aw maa khpali wazari alwatu ta na prigdee</i>
They won’t let go of me;	
And nor will both my wings permit,	
My body to take flight,	
My soul to soar, be free.”	

(pp. 50–51).

Ibn Arabi and Kant would likely approve of the poet's assertion that life is precious and worth living. Yet, it still requires realising its true potential through freedom, either by surrendering to the divine will, as in Ibn Arabi, or by yielding to moral principles, as in Kant. Once humans tie themselves up with the colours and lights of the material world, then it becomes useless to long for freedom. Therefore, it is advisable to fasten it to the external force of the divine by setting it free from the earthly desires, as Ibn Arabi advises, or to the internal by listening to the voice of reason and abiding by the categorical imperatives, as Kant advises. Khan writes in “*Laka Wakhli: Chi Maashoom*” (Like a Little Child Who Plays):

I have thus my precious life,	<i>Daasi maa daa khpal zhwandoon</i>
Turned to cinders, worthless dust;	<i>Da masti silab ki law ka</i>
And I, seriously bound,	<i>Pa khpala laas mi zaan bandee ka</i>
In the chains of wrath profound.	<i>Da su qisma dawzakhoonu</i>
Either life is a lost battle,	<i>Laka wakhlee chi maashoom</i>
Or I am ill-equipped...	<i>Dakk shkarey da sru aw spinu</i>

(pp. 98–99).

Sometimes one finds striking similarities between Khan’s themes with Ibn Arabi’s mysticism. Khan argues freedom is generated not only from outside by tying up one’s own self with the will of the divine but also from the inside by annihilating one’s own self through self-abnegation and thus securing freedom from the negative selfish desires. Khan uses images that highlight freedom and transcendence. Khan associates the nightingale with the divine connection in his poem “*Shaheed*” (The Martyr). It becomes a symbol of the cosmic self caring not in the least for the material and worldly possessions but merging itself in the divine will:

I have brought no offering for you	<i>Maa raawarri taa la na dee da di sru gulu</i>
Of a necklace of red flowers,	<i>amiluna</i>
For the nightingales of Heaven	

Of what use are earthly flowers! *Da Jannat bulbulan sa kai da duniya di*

(pp. 276–277). *bagh guluna*

At another place in “*Za Hum Jadugar Yema*” (I, too, am a Wizard), Khan highlights freedom by comparing the material and immaterial worlds through the voices produced by humans and the music, respectively. Worldly autocrats can silence the voices produced by humans in various forms through different means to muzzle their expression, but the voice of music works in a mysterious way that cannot be repressed. Thus, music has metaphysical connections because it influences one’s senses by its power of harmony and balance. It compels the listeners to win liberation from self through ecstasy and transcendence:

When my voice is muffled, *band ka mi awaaz krree suk za saaz ki thri na*
I escape in music’s tunes, *watakhtam*
And in the plaintive notes create, *Senga sawee sawee da ranguno dunya jurra*
Painful world of many hues... *karam*

(pp. 159–160).

Ibn Arabi’s mystical philosophy is frequently echoed in Khan’s poetry. Love is considered not as an enslaving sentiment but as a liberating experience. Even if one submits one’s will and surrenders entirely to love, it liberates the self from anything else. If this love is directed towards the divine, then one can gain complete freedom from worldly desires by losing oneself in the divine will. Khan writes in “*Sawal Jawaab Da Lewani Aw Mulla*” (Pious Priest and Madman):

.....Oh madman! Finally *lewania! ta ye suk?*
Who are you and all your kind? *Mulla! za da cha armaan*
I am just somebody’s longing, *Za yau gul da chaa da gutto*
And a flower of someone’s shape, *Prut pa pkhu ki da janan*
Tapering fingers, *hennaed* bright,
Lying coyly, in repose
On beloved’s pretty feet.

(pp. 118–119).

Kantian freedom is rooted in the principles of moral autonomy and practical reason uninfluenced by any external force and guided by moral duty. Set against such preferences, Khan's notion of love is that of a powerful sentiment. Even one that even kings can willingly abdicate their thrones. It aligns with the *Akbarian* principle of winning freedom through losing freedom for the sake of love. He writes in "*Deodasi*":

“Who am I? a poor outcast,	<i>Maa ta yi wi "ay musawira, maa ta wugora,</i>
And the lowliest of the low,	<i>za sa yem</i>
Dedicated to the temple	<i>Yawa khwaara da but winza da kaminu da</i>
And it's idol, but an enslaved person.”	<i>kaminah"</i>
I said, you're beauty's daughter,	<i>Ma wi ta da husn ur yi, ta rangeena</i>
And a princess, colourful,	<i>shahzadgai yi</i>
And for just a fleeting glance	<i>Sta pa yau sawee nazar ba zar takhtoon</i>
Of your lovely, languid eyes,	<i>shi qurban</i>
Kings will abdicate their thrones.	

(pp. 106–107).

Khan, like Kant, is rebellious towards usurpers and rejects any attempt to snatch freedom through coercion or exploitation. The powerful or those who have access to authority usually subjugate the deprived classes. One commonly finds this in religious seminaries. They practise religion without understanding the true sense of its universal humanity. They discourage anyone with an inquisitive approach or with a true sentiment of love for humanity. Khan thus becomes a Kantian in the moral principle. He often longs to promote harmony by highlighting this conflict through symbolic characters like the snake, the priest and the beloved in his poem "*Mansoor*":

I prepared a throne of love,	<i>Maa da meeni takht ka jurr khaisht la da</i>
For beauty of Beloved's face;	<i>janaan da makh</i>

Furtively, the pious priest, *Ghalay warta rroond mulla ghalay laka maar*
 On it like a snake emerged! *wukhat*

(pp. 204–205).

In another poem, “*Ay Zama Watana*” (Oh Motherland), the poet desires to “turn to cinders,” and get annihilated to reemerge as hard as a Kantian autonomous person. He idealises an indomitable person to any external dictation except that dictated by the will. The moral and universal principles guide him. Khan uses images such as “cinder,” and “mountains,” to highlight the unconquerable and tough nature of his motherland, where life moves on like “rivers,” and rills through the “valleys,” and “gorges,” despite having suffered many wounds from the “unsheathed swords” (pp. 280–281). These symbols also indicate that life may encounter disturbances on its journey, but it will always remain autonomous and act by free will.

As noticed earlier, Ibn Arabi seeks detachment from materiality and takes refuge in the annihilation of the self by submerging his will in that of the divine. He often considers the soul being imprisoned in the human body. That is why it longs for unity with the divine essence. Although human is metaphorically compared with dust, they can be transformed into a paragon of virtue and cosmic significance through gaining freedom from bodily confinement. Khan writes in “*Ay Zwanah*” (Oh Young Man!):

Oh <i>Pakhtoon</i> this is your land!	<i>Ay pakhtuna sta watan dey</i>
Oh <i>Pakhtoon</i> this is your land!	<i>Ay pakhtuna sta watan dey</i>
Come collect the dust again,	<i>Da di bagh khawri rawaakhla</i>
Of this orchard, once so fair;	<i>Thri na nawey bustaan jurr krra</i>
From it once again create,	<i>Ay da sawee baagh maaliara</i>
Scented flowers and perfumed air.	<i>Da nuroonu jahaan jurr krra</i>
Oh gardener of a blighted land,	
A world of colours recreate!	

(pp. 284–287).

Many poems of Khan also present the Kantian concept of freedom. It is seen in throwing a challenge at anything that attempts to deprive. The free self thus wins autonomy of the human self instead of being subservient to external forces, such as in “*Sodaagar*” (*The Merchant*):

Either make me a god	<i>Yaa maa khudai ka, sajda wuka ya zama aw</i>
And prostrate yourself to me	<i>sta dey jang</i>
Or be prepared to face me	
In a never-ending war.	<i>Wey daa toora zamaa laas ki staa da zhwand</i>
With this sword in my hand	<i>ikhtiyar zamaa dey</i>
I have power over your fate...	

(pp. 314–319).

Kant supports self-determination, without which it can never attain sublimity and cosmic significance. This self-determination enables humans to abide by moral laws, because a person who lacks autonomy and independence cannot decide and act independently. He says in “*Da Bachu Taraana*” (*The Children’s Anthem*):

I shall now disown my name	<i>Daa noom ba badal krrum yaa ba krrum badal</i>
Or I shall the world transform!	<i>jahaan</i>
I shall for my people fight,	<i>Za ba zam pa jang da qaam</i>
When my manhood I attain!	

(pp. 292–293).

This desire for self-recognition resonates in Khan’s poetry. For instance, the act of forbidding mourners from visiting his grave or offering any respects, like laying a wreath there, should he suffer a useless and meaningless death like cowards. Khan writes in his poem “*Wasiyat*” (*The Will*):

If my body were not bathed,	<i>Ka pa khpulo weeno na wum lambidlay</i>
In my blood and sanctified,	<i>Pa maa ma palito da jumaat ghaarri</i>
Do not ever desecrate	<i>Chi qatri qatri mi foj da dushman na ka</i>
	<i>Muri! maa pasi pa kum makh ba ta</i>
	<i>zhaaree</i>
	<i>Yaa ba da bi nangah mulk baagh-i-aden</i>
	<i>krrum</i>

The precincts of the mosque with it. *Yaa ba krrum da pakhtanu koosi
wijaarri*
(pp. 288–289).

Sometimes Khan’s images become harsh. It is particularly concerning the cowardly and unpatriotic people. He denies them the right of burial or even a funeral. Although Kant did not accept the harshness and emotional aspect of this advice for fear of disrupting social order, he approves retaining moral and rational autonomy at any cost for the dignity of humanity. This kind of freedom with no advice for disrupting world order in Khan parallels Kant’s notion of freedom. Khan says in the same poem, “*Da Bachu Taraana*” (*The Children’s Anthem*):

Oh one’s head is little more,	<i>Sar sa da spee sar wee chi fida na wee pa</i>
Than a dog’s, if unconcerned,	<i>qaam</i>
Uncommitted to the tribe,	<i>Nar sa khwazunay wee chi sheida na wee pa</i>
Of what use is his standing, state	<i>qaam</i>
If he is another’s slave...	<i>Noom namoos yi sa wee chi yi noom wee da</i>
	<i>ghulam</i>

(pp. 292–293).

Similarly, Khan also invokes *Akbarian* concept of freedom with the same vigour and gusto. He turns this into a matter of a spiritual question. True freedom rests not in being subservient to the worldly or individual caprices but to the will of the divine through realisation and transcendence by connecting back to the true essence. This theme is best illustrated by turning the dust into something higher and more beautiful, as the creator did in the case of humans at the time of creation. He writes in “*Ay Zwanah!*” (*Oh Young Man*):

Come collect the dust again,	<i>Daa di baagh khaawri rawaakhla</i>
Of this orchard, once so fair;	<i>Thri na nawey bustaan jurr krra</i>
From it once again create,	<i>Ay da sawee baagh maaliara</i>
Scented flowers and perfumed air.	<i>Da nuroonu jahaan jurr krra</i>

(pp. 284–287).

One frequently comes across images of the cupbearer “*Saki*” and “wine” in Khan’s poetry. These are associated with both the Kantian and the *Akbarian* concept of freedom. In Kantian terms, these images convey the theme of making a moral and rational choice by selecting from the cup of wine, which represents life. It can bring either joy or sorrow, without any restriction. In the *Akbarian* terms of freedom, it is like relapsing into a state of stupor in love of the divine and thus winning freedom from attachment to the material world through transposition into a higher realm. Khan says in “*Saki*” (*The Cupbearer*):

Oh <i>saki</i> ! You choose the wine,	<i>Da saki laas ki sharaab dee, da khanda dee</i>
Let me have it with a smile;	<i>ka da gham</i>
I am mad, and do not care,	<i>Chi da soz aw ka da saaz dee, da masti ka da</i>
I'm indifferent to them both!	<i>maatam</i>

(pp. 378–379).

These examples illustrate that Khan’s poetry blends the concepts of Ibn Arabi and Kant regarding freedom and autonomy. Freedom is an attribute of the cosmic self. Humans have developed a love for freedom and autonomy since creation, as reflected in the religious scriptures. However, humans were made superior to any other creatures. Humans are rational because they can strike a balance between entirely surrendering to the divine and maintaining freedom, together with autonomy.

5.3. Cosmic Self as Annihilation and Oneness

Khan’s poetry presents an interplay of themes related to the mystical and philosophical questions of existence, annihilation and oneness.

Ibn Arabi founds his mystical framework on the Unity of Being. He considers being as emanated or transcended from a single source of true essence, linking the creator and the created into a single whole. The creation is a reflection of the Divine Essence. But this true essence can only be realised through self-annihilation and oneness. For example, in “*Sawal*

Jawab Da Levani Aw Mulla” (Pious Priest and Madman), the act of prostration is compared to “the reduction of one’s self to dust,” which is a concept of self-annihilation in the *Sufi* literature (pp. 116–119). The self is suggested to be effaced in the presence of the divine to achieve oneness with the *One*.

Developing further on the theme of oneness through self-annihilation, another poem by Khan, “*Sparley*” (Spring), displays jubilation over the Divine or the Beloved as permeating through every atom in the universe. It is compared to the light from *Mount Sinai*, where the divine was revealed to the Prophet Moses (pp. 188–192). Thus, a state of the self, turned into ashes upon the Divine manifestation, can only attain oneness and unity with the cosmic self. It is unthinkable, argues Khan, that the divine would ever inflict eternal damnation and punishment on such a beloved creature as a human. Only humans have the role to maintain balance and explore this cosmos based on reason and understanding.

As illustrated earlier, Kant develops a metaphysical framework based on his critical philosophy. Sometimes, he refers to this system as transcendental idealism. Kant restricts the role of human understanding and accepts the limitations of human reason, especially when juxtaposed with the sublime and noumenal. It is the human mind that structures experience to make it comprehensible and definable. The divine, though, always remains beyond human understanding and reason. This ineffability of the sublime is expressed in Khan’s poem “*Suka*” (Summit), where he yearns for the “sole object of ... love” that the summit conceals, eluding definability on account of being a noumena (pp. 128–129). Khan longs to track down what is hidden behind the summit by force of a symbolic journey of mystical transcendence. Khan emphasises love and annihilation as means to gain access to the indescribable.

Khan is with Ibn Arabi in his desire to transcend physical experience for unity with the divine through self-annihilation. He represents this through the iconic figure of *Hallaj*, who had pronounced “I am the Truth” in Khan’s poem “*Mansoor*.” This poem also highlights how

one suffers persecution on the path towards self-realisation and oneness with the Divine. He longs to achieve this state of annihilation through the symbolic act of “kiss me,” following which he will be entirely dissolved and submerged in the universal essence (pp. 204–205). Kant, however, rejects self-annihilation. He emphasises accepting the limitations of reason and being humbled by the sublime due to its vastness and magnitude.

Khan’s poem “*Meena*” (Love) is about the decaying and regenerative attributes of love. He highlights these through the loss and rebirth of the beloved. Love is the primary cause behind creation. The Divine had fallen in love with self and so desired to see similar attributes in creation through manifestation (pp. 152–153). It is the creation that, once created, should reunite as suggested by the *Sufi* ideal of self-annihilation and sacrifice. Kant rejects any notion of mystical annihilation in favour of human autonomy and dignity.

Khan’s poem “*Chi Adam Khaawru Ki Kini*” (When Man Mingles with the Earth) makes self-annihilation as an initial step towards attaining cosmic self. He uses a strong analogy of human transformation into dust and then getting rebirth. He emphasises through symbolic images of fertility yielding healthy crops of “wrath and worth” to show the process of creation and destruction that takes place ceaselessly (pp. 225–227). For Kant, it is a natural process of human autonomy rather than self-effacement that holds significance.

The mystical and philosophical themes of annihilation and oneness, as integral parts of the cosmic self, recur throughout Khan’s poetry. Being the foremost mystical philosopher of the school of *Wahdat ul Wajood* (The Unity of Being), Ibn Arabi considers the universe and the self as tied up in one cosmic whole manifested in the divine attributes, which are possible to be united with only after annihilation and dissolution of the self into the real essence. It is, however, not at the cost of entirely obliterating the self; instead, it is an extension of the self. In a passage from his poem “Letter from Faridoon’s Mother,” he says, “And when you became a spark of the fire as it burned, / I became the raging flame, / As it crackled and curled...” (pp.

14–19). Khan uses fire to represent the restlessly oscillating state between the finite and the infinite, making the self part of the cosmic reality. This synchronises the self with the divine reality in the *Akbarian* sense.

Khan describes this state of annihilation and oneness in his poem “*Wruk Khayal*” (*Longing*). He secures oneness by merging into one and assuming the form of both the lover and the beloved. Khan writes:

Both my eyes and heart surrender,	<i>Maa khpal zrrah stargu ki khur ka, dir pa</i>
With great love, I walked towards him;	<i>meena war rawaan shum</i>
A strange world then I encountered,	<i>Ajeeba jahaan ta laarrum ham aashiq shum</i>
And most willingly became,	
Both the lover and the loved.	<i>ham janaan shum</i>

(pp. 78–81).

With eyes and heart being offered reflects the state of a self entirely surrendering to the divine will and attaining a state of unity with the higher reality. It is a purely mystic experience from Ibn Arabi’s perspective. On the contrary, for Kant, it will be a movement towards unity with the universal moral principles by forsaking selfish desires in the will of a more expansive humanity. However, there is no room for equating this with mystical experience in the Kantian philosophy.

Khan uses images to project oneness and annihilation, such as fire, light and wine. These phenomena take entirely new forms. This process of metamorphosis through regeneration keeps taking place constantly. He writes in “*Masti*” (*Ecstasy*):

When light is ecstatic,	<i>Ranrra chi masta shee ranga ranguna shi</i>
It turns into colours.	<i>Khaawra chi masta shee sra sara guluna</i>
When the Earth is ecstatic,	
It produces red flowers.	<i>shee</i>

(pp. 92–95).

The ecstatic state of light transforming into a multi-coloured entity illustrates how one object, such as light, transforms into multiplicity. This finds a strong connection with Ibn Arabi's framework of the Unity of Being.

This theme of total annihilation through oneness is again expressed through another, "*Da Khaapiru Shahzadgai*" (The Fairy Princess). Khan writes, "And lose your entity, / Within the coloured sunbeams, / As they dance upon the sea..." (pp. 48–51). This is complete submergence and dissolution of the self in the divine, bringing unity and oneness. This experience cannot be defined according to the Kantian principle of synthesis. However, it fits in the *Akbarian* terms.

Khan's poetry thus serves as a bridge between the mystical framework of Ibn Arabi and the Kantian philosophy concerning the dimension of annihilation and oneness. Ibn Arabi considers annihilation and oneness as inseparable experiences of mysticism and his system of the Unity of Being. Kant's philosophy emphasises the transcendental self, considering the unity of understanding and sensory perception. This synthesis takes place at the rational level. Kant may interpret the annihilation of the self as transcending selfish desires in favour of the greater good and order in the community. Khan is more driven towards Ibn Arabi than towards Kant. His poetry consists of images and analogies that emphasise these experiences in the light of the *Akbarian* perspective.

5.4. Immaterial and Material – Paradoxical Components of the Cosmic Self

Khan's poetry explores themes with mystical and philosophical underpinnings on the interplay between materiality and immateriality. His poetry presents imagery related to existential questions about the cosmic self, as it emerges from both the material and the immaterial. Khan explores these dimensions of reality by drawing on the analysis from the life resonating with the self in the frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Khan's favourite themes are often about materiality, immateriality and transitoriness of material existence in mystical and philosophical

terms. The following analysis explores the material and immaterial dimensions of the cosmic self through Ibn Arabi and Kant.

Khan's poem "*Da Khaapiru Shahzaadgai*" (*The Fairy Princess*) encapsulates the conflict between the material and the immaterial being. These are inseparable dimensions despite being paradoxically at opposite ends. Khan tries to set himself free from the material confinements, as in the following words:

.....come take this palace,	<i>Wey yi waakhla daa mahal daa takht daa tool</i>
And this throne, all that you see!	<i>sazoosamaan</i>
But where will you take refuge?	
One cannot flee from oneself.	<i>Di ghama patiday nishte suk pat ba shi da zaan</i>

(pp. 48–51).

Khan's poetry shows no hesitation in forsaking symbols of material wealth, such as the crown and throne. It recounts that the divine is manifested in the material realm, but the material is merely an illusion. In mystical systems, it serves as a veil to conceal the divine from humans due to its density. The self is a microcosmic part of an ineffable macrocosm. It comprises, broadly speaking, both the material and the immaterial realms. There is no escape from the material self because it is the one that defines the human self in Kantian terms. It is equally important in Ibn Arabi's system, because it is the manifestation of the divine's love.

In another poem titled "*Khayal*" (*Fancy*), Khan sounds quite *Akbarian* and Kantian in his approach. He develops a link between the material and the immaterial:

Fancy, with some caution, care,	<i>Khiyaala lag pa khiyal ki za his pa pata di</i>
Go your way, proceed!	<i>pui na krrum</i>
You have not made me the wiser,	<i>Chi kum khkulai kum halaal dey chi sa husan</i>
About what is beauty, right!	<i>aw sa kamaal dey</i>

(pp. 62–65).

Khan blames fancy (immaterial) for not being able to unearth true beauty (another immaterial concept). Khan thus agrees with Kant that it is beyond the reach of human imagination and reason to discover the noumenal or immaterial. It becomes a human failure for Ibn Arabi to lose contact with the immaterial and divine. It should not miss witnessing the divine manifestation in the phenomenal beauty of the sensory realm.

In another poem, “*Khaawri*” (Dust), Khan describes in vivid imagery the search for self. Grave symbolises imagination. It is a part of the material and immaterial through the transitoriness of life, as he writes:

In the grave lie buried deep,	<i>Chi janaan pa mastu stargu guti wraurri</i>
Hands and feet, fingers and lips;	<i>sitaar la</i>
Who can dig a grave and bury,	<i>Pa qabroonu ki prati dee laas aw pkhi shundi</i>
Drunken glory of the eyes,	<i>aw guti</i>
When, beloved with plectrum,	<i>Suk shee qabar jurrawaley da di sru stargu</i>
Plucks the strings of a Sitar	<i>khumaar la</i>

(pp. 72–75).

Thus, Khan juxtaposes the decay of the material with the immaterial. Ibn Arabi would interpret this as the spiritual ecstasy that the self undergoes in the face of divine beauty, just as the *Sufis* do. For Kant, this would be akin to accepting the limitations of the corporeal body in order to access sublime immaterial beauty.

Ibn Arabi’s concept is that each individual manifests a unique attribute as a self and as part of the divine immaterial cosmic whole. Khan makes the same individual as part of the divine being autonomous, rather than being governed by anyone else. He is indifferent to material wealth and praise. Both the mystical and philosophical qualifications of the self with the intrinsic attributes are exemplified in Khan’s poem “*Reedi Gul*” (The Flower). When he finds a flower alone and unappreciated in the desert, he feels pity for that flower. However, the pity turns into praise when he comes to know its real value, which is entirely contingent upon

the same unique state of being alone. “The flower” thus becomes a symbol of unparalleled self, combining the immaterial and material:

I shall not exchange this wasteland,	<i>Za ba daa sahraa warna krrum da Iran pa</i>
For the Persian garden green.	<i>gulistaan</i>
Here I am one of a kind,	<i>Dilta za yau aw yaktaa yam, halta zar</i>
There are thousands there like me.	<i>zamaa pa shaan</i>

(pp. 76–77).

Khan holds a strong belief in the life hereafter, where all existence is immaterial. Humans can control whatever is in the material realm; however, the immaterial (noumenal) is beyond understanding. This immaterial realm is a part of the human self for Ibn Arabi, but for Kant, it is beyond human comprehension and perception. Khan is both *Akbarian* to accept the existence of an immaterial realm and Kantian to hold that both worlds exist independently of each other.

Khan says in his poem “*Taali*” (*Swing*):

If the insights of the mind	<i>Ka da fikar nazar tiz dey</i>
Are as sharp as razor’s edge;	
If the wall of Fate, as strong,	<i>Da qismat dewaal muhkam dey</i>
As the granite of the hill;	
It’s the other side that’s worrying	<i>Dikhwa dikhwa khu ba sam krrum</i>
And dependent on His grace.	<i>Khu daa gham di akhwa gham dey</i>

(pp. 66–69).

Khan means “the other side,” the immaterial realm,. According to Ibn Arabi, it is the archetype of the material world. Kant would also agree that the noumenal world stands outside our understanding, because humans can only have access to the material world.

In his poem “*Wruk Khayal*” (*Longing*), Khan draws a comparison between the material and immaterial self. He follows both Ibn Arabi and Kant. Like Ibn Arabi, the poet explains his existence on the principles of Unity of Being, because he represents the material manifestation of the divine. It is only through this material manifestation that the divine can be witnessed. It

also explains existence in terms of Kant's philosophy, that reality is composed of dual dimensions of the material (physical, phenomenal) and immaterial (noumenal). It is human perception, as Kant says, that colours and interprets the physical realm, whereas the noumenal realm remains outside human perceptions. Khan writes about this:

I shall make myself your form,	<i>Za ba khpal zaan sta wujood krrum chi ta</i>
So that you can then be seen;	<i>stargu ta khkaara shi</i>
With my feeling, I shall clothe thee,	<i>Khpal ehshaas ba di jaama krrum chi yau</i>
So that you can become,	<i>khaisht yau nandaara shi</i>
The nonpareil of beauty.	

(pp. 78–81).

Khan thus follows the principle of divine self-disclosure, where the material realm becomes a manifestation of the divine. In Kantian philosophy, this principle is referred to as synthesis, which imagination brings together between sensory and supersensory experiences.

Khan's poetry provides ample examples to support Ibn Arabi's proposition that material is a manifestation of the divine in this universe. Similarly, Khan's poetry also provides numerous examples to illustrate what Kant considers material and immaterial as distinct entities, with the immaterial existing beyond the realm of human experience. The following excerpt from Khan's poem "*Talaash*" (*Search*) reflects this approach. Khan tries to find answer to his material existence through reason as well as through mystical experience. Here, Khan agrees with Ibn Arabi and Kant, because he discovers only impermanence for his physical and material state. Khan discovers life in death. Khan says:

The answer to my life I seek.	<i>Zaan la jawaab da khpal zhwandoon</i>
I am mad; a truly raving lunatic,	<i>guram</i>
.....	<i>Za lewaney yem, lewaney yem</i>
	<i>rikhtiya</i>

And when I fix my gaze upon myself,	<i>Zaan ta chi stargi mi ra waarrawuli</i>
	<i>Bas marg</i>
	<i>Aw neesh da adam</i>
	<i>wugurama</i>

Nought else but death and non-existence do I see.
 I am mad; a truly raving lunatic,
 Life, ambient in the eyes of death, I see.

*Za lewaney yem, lewaney yem
 rikhtiya
 Di marg pa stargu ki zhwandoon
 guram*

(pp. 82–89).

Khan places the material and immaterial in juxtaposition to each other in his poem “*Sawaal Jawaab da Lewaney Aw Mulla*” (Pious Priest and Madman). Here, the madman confesses to heaven being in a state of ecstasy and intoxication for him:

What is Heaven, madman tell me?	<i>Lewaniya! jannat sa dey?</i>
Pious priest, our concepts differ –	<i>Mulla! staa jannat piti dey</i>
For you Heaven is no more	<i>Ao zamaa jannat wisaal dey</i>
Than a gourmet’s spread, for me	<i>Yau khumaar yau mastee dey</i>
It’s communion and being drunk	
With the wine of ecstasy.	

(pp. 116–119).

These lines aptly exemplify Ibn Arabi’s mystical framework. Khan rejects the material world being an illusion and worthless (gourmet) and accepts the oneness with the immaterial as the only objective. Kant’s transcendental idealism, however, considers the material and immaterial as distinct. He, though, does not reject the material since that is inevitable to know the material existence through experience.

In another poem, “*Tapus ka Jawab*” (Question or Answer...), Khan engages in a dialectical relationship concerning life. Khan tries to define life in material and immaterial terms. Khan compares life with material and transitory as well as with the intangible and permanent images. Although Kant’s transcendental idealism leaves life undefined due to its noumenal association, he often compares it with order and organisation. Ibn Arabi’s mystical framework considers life as a manifested reality of the divine. Khan thus combines Ibn Arabi

and Kant through the images and theme conveyed through these lines. Life is noumenal and beyond human understanding, though it can be defined only after its juxtaposition with the material realm. However, life can also be defined in Ibn Arabi’s words that it is an interplay of the material as manifestation and immaterial. Khan writes:

Come! Hold forth, oh pious priest!	<i>Waaya waaya mulla jaana!</i>
Is life just a question mark,	<i>Zhwand tapus dey ka jawaab</i>
Or an answer with some meaning?
.....
.....	<i>Zhwand imaam dey ka gulfaam dey</i>
.....	<i>Ka mimbar dey ka mihrab</i>
Or the pulpit for the sermon,
Or the prayer niche in the mosque,	<i>Zhwand Firawn dey aw ghuroor dey</i>
.....
.....	<i>Daa Namrood da zaro takht dey</i>
Is life Pharaoh and his pride?	<i>Ka rangeen marg da Mansoor dey</i>
.....
.....	<i>Da bahaar dey ka gulaab dey</i>
Is it Spring, or the rose hiding	<i>lag pat shawey da tiari na</i>
From the darkness for a while...	

(pp. 124–127).

Whether it is beauty like that of the rose or the pulpit, or Pharaoh’s arrogance, nothing will stay. All will have a fall on account of the existential attribute of transitoriness and impermanence. However, these visible forms are the manifestation of the invisible and immaterial divine essence. The mystical frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant, as noticed, may look at these lines through the prism of a mystic or philosopher by interpreting them in terms of the phenomena and the noumena. Noumena, like life, are always in a state of intangibility.

Khan’s poem “*Suka*” (*Summit*) presents a self that is troubled by the question of exploring and uncovering the mystery. It is ineffable, immaterial and noumenal. Being so, it is also beyond the comprehension and understanding of human reason. The poet uses images highlighting material existence between the material and immaterial realms. This immaterial

and cosmic self is symbolically represented by the summit covered behind a foggy veil and winding path, as in the following lines:

Far away in the far distance,	<i>Lari lari pa wryazu ki yau speena suka</i>
Clothed in the clouds of darkish hue,	
One can see the summit white,	<i>khkaari</i>
Of mountain reaching out,	
To the sky in all its pride;	<i>khu pa laarah ki dee ghroona aw dari dee da</i>
But the way to it is winding,	<i>ghamuno</i>
All across the hills and dales,	
And the gorges, ever-winding,	
Of interminable grief.	

(pp.128–129).

Khan becomes both a mystic and philosopher in the *Akbarian* and the Kantian tradition. He synthesises the spiritual and the immaterial shadow of the divine with the material, visible and earthly summit. For Kant, only a cosmic self endowed with the attributes of autonomy and moral principle can unveil the mystery behind the summit, while simultaneously acknowledging its limitations.

Khan pitches a philosopher against a lunatic in his poem “*Ajaba Falsafa*” (**Strange Philosophy**). It seems Khan assumes the role of a philosopher himself instead of the lunatic, which he generally likes to be known. The lunatic is not unmindful of the material realm. He accepts it with all its charms and riches. On the contrary, a philosopher like him can neither take pleasures of the world nor of the hereafter due to his habit of weighing every action in the light of good and bad. He thus deprives himself of the pleasures of this material world. That is why Khan longs to be blessed with the ecstasy and insight of a lunatic instead of the superficial approach of a philosopher. Looked at this perspective, Khan acknowledges both Ibn Arabi and Kant. Like Ibn Arabi, he accepts an intrinsic connection between the material and immaterial realms, with the latter being a manifestation of the former. Khan also acknowledges Kant, who accepts the existence of separate material (phenomenal) and immaterial (noumenal) realms. However, a philosopher possesses a rational insight, and the requirement is only to support that

with sincerity and devotion like that of a lunatic. The philosopher looks at the superficial, declaring fear instead of sincerity and passionate ecstasy essential to discover the truth. Khan writes:

To the blind I am recounting	<i>Ma rroond ta shuru karree da ranrraa aw noor qisa da</i>
Tales of light and effulgence –	<i>Da junoon aw daa janaan da sa ajaba falsafa da</i>
And of madness, the beloved,	<i>Wira wira da qahaar na da eemaan asli hissa da</i>
What a strange philosophy!	<i>.....</i>
.....	<i>Zrra di kigda pa seena ki dulta rang aw hisaab raawrra</i>
.....	<i>Sta sharaab dulta haraam dee sharbat rawrra gilass raawrra</i>
Fear, fear of our God,	<i>Za tur aw speen guram bas zamaa dagha qisa da</i>
Is essential part of faith.	<i>Dagha tul zamaa umeed dey daa tallal mi falsafa da</i>
.....	<i>Lewaniya! Lewaniya! daa tul aqal zamaa waakhla</i>
Put your heart back in your breast,	<i>Khu badal ki raala rakrra yau qatra di khpal armaan</i>
For sincerity's not needed,	<i>Sta da ukhku na qurbaan sham sta da dardunu ta paskhigam</i>
Mere form here pursue!	<i>Chi pa dwaarru ki khumaar dey da khubunu da janaan</i>
Your red wine is not permitted,	
Here, orange juice consume!	

(pp. 132–143).

It is the longing, in the end, that enables humans to discover the mystery behind the noumenal or immaterial, which Kant equates with a yearning to understand the sublime.

Khan becomes explicit while describing different colours symbolically representing the material and the immaterial dimensions of reality. Khan writes in his poem “*Rangoona*” (Colours):

White, the colour I dislike,	<i>Speen sara mi na lagee</i>
White, the colour of deceit,	<i>Speen dey da riya rang</i>

.....
Black, the devil's clothes and wares,	<i>Tur dey da shaitaan libaas</i>
Black, denial's sword and sheath.	<i>Tura da inkaar toora</i>
.....
Red, the colour of the rose,	<i>Soor dey da gulaab aw</i>
Red, communion's joy, repose;	<i>Da wisaal aw da khumaar rang</i>
.....
Green the eyes of Ghani Khan,	<i>Shni da Ghani stargi dee</i>
Green the hue of constancy,	<i>Sheen dey da wafaa rang</i>

(pp.174–175).

Whatever meanings that Ghani Khan gives to the same colours are different from those of Ibn Arabi. The common aspect is that both agree upon associating colours with symbolic meanings. Ibn Arabi holds colours to be associated with the divine and material symbols of manifestation. Kant, though, does not see any symbolic or external meanings in the colours. He interprets colours according to his inner perceptions. Khan interprets white as a symbol of the priest, hypocrisy and deceit (Ibn Arabi's divine light); black of death and sorrow as well as infinite emptiness (Ibn Arabi's hidden mystery); red of the colour of the rose, intoxication and building a bridge between the material and the immaterial (Ibn Arabi's love and divine wrath). Green is the symbol of hope, permanence, rebirth and spiritual rejuvenation (Ibn Arabi's eternal life). These colours, with their symbolic associations, would also be interpreted as manifesting divine attributes in a unique relation with each colour. Kant, as stated earlier, interprets these colours in terms of sensory experience in the phenomenal world, with no symbolic association other than the personal. Khan is thus closer to Ibn Arabi than to Kant in his association of the symbolic meanings with colours.

In his poem “*Sparley*” (*The Spring*), Khan explores the theme of impermanence and permanence. He draws on the distinction between materiality and immateriality as part of the divine, like Ibn Arabi. Khan often becomes a complete pantheist. The beloved pours forth intangible beauty and effulgence in the form of the material manifestation, “[What is Spring but the Beloved is actually in ecstasy / Who is spreading His effulgence in every particle and every breath / He is spreading His light]” (pp. 188–192). The Spring is an expression of the divine attributes, characterised by the ecstatic expression of the divine in the form of beautiful flowers and lush green fields. Kant would interpret the same colourful and fragrant surroundings of the Spring not in terms of the manifestation of the divine but in terms of subjective experience. This subjective experience demonstrates balance and order all around in this season.

The material possessions are made meaningless compared to the immaterial ones. Khan often behaves like a complete *Sufi*. Sometimes, it becomes complicated to interpret “beloved” in his poetry. It needs careful reading and uncovering the images or symbols associated with the beloved. Like a mystic, he mostly applies the beloved to the divine. On the initial reading of his poem, “*Dua*” (*Prayer*), Khan appears to address the divine by using the word beloved; however, the same beloved can also be used interchangeably with the worldly beloved. Khan is very little Kantian in the sense of giving meaning to the empirical experience through perception. He is more of an *Akbarian* to find something divine in the material phenomena of the simple beloved’s eyes. Khan’s poem, “*Dua*” (*Prayer*), describes the beloved’s eyes:

In my beloved’s lovely eyes,	<i>Stargu da janaan ki zamaa khkulee</i>
A universe of beauty lies;	<i>jhaanoona dee</i>
Take Your world, it’s Yours to keep,	<i>Waa di khla duniya za wurray staa da</i>
I am not in need of it!	<i>duniya na yem</i>
See, within my beggar’s bowl,	

The crown of Alexander lies,	<i>Gura di faqeer kachkul ki taaj da Sikandar</i>
I beg from the generous,	<i>dey prut</i>
Moreover, the misers shun, decry.	<i>Za yem da sakhyaanu da shumaanu gadaa</i>

(pp. 200–201). *na yem*

When the human self becomes engrossed in material wealth and riches, the divine is said to go behind a dense veil. The divine thus becomes inaccessible to us. Kant is not explicitly visible in the above excerpt, but he also follows the same approach of rejecting material wealth on account of its inherent limitations. He instructs humans to be guided by rational and moral agents.

Khan’s poem “*Chi Adam Khawro Ki Kini*” (*When Man Mingles with the Earth*) showcases the material existence through the fleeting nature of the objective nature and material life. Khan uses the symbol of “viper” for humans getting lost in worldly riches. Khan reiterates that the existence in the physical world is temporary and transitory. The divine manifestation in the form of the material nature will always be there, but humans will dissolve and decay. It seems that Khan considers the world to exist permanently, but humans get lost and forgotten. The poem lays down the status of humans in mystical terms through fertility images of the crops getting decayed and then regenerated. The regeneration can also be interpreted as part of practical philosophy by Kant, who recommends that humans getting developed from bad into good. Khan highlights this permanence and impermanence of the immaterial and material realms in the following words:

When man mingles with the earth,	<i>Chi adam khaawru ki kini sa zarghoon</i>
Crops so green of worth emerge;	<i>krree</i>
When coiled upon his wealth he sits,	<i>Manjila chi pa daulat shee nu khamaar</i>
Then like a viper venom spits!	<i>shee</i>
.....
.....

And these gardens, full of flowers,	<i>Da chi nan paki za mast aw maghroor</i>
In which so proud, I stroll around,	<i>garzam</i>
Come the morrow, who can tell,	<i>Saba khudai khabar da chaa ba daa</i>
Whose shall be these bowers green!	<i>gulzaar shee</i>

(pp. 225–227).

Khan criticises the human tendency to stoop down to the lowest level of pursuing material wealth as the ultimate goal. Khan blankly rejects such a material pursuit. It degenerates the divine connection inside humans. This leads to the community getting disorganised and disorderly. This kind of consequence is not only unacceptable to Khan but surely so to Ibn Arabi and Kant as well. Khan thus places the material and immaterial side by side. Khan repeats the same theme in his poem “*Zhwand*” (Life):

When there’s ease, a life of comfort,	<i>Chi araam wee aw samaam wee aw yaaree</i>
Friendship is merely based on wealth,	<i>pa jaidaad wee</i>
Every cad becomes <i>Farhad</i> ,	<i>Khurbaanu hum sheerinee wee har taroo</i>
Every donkey-maid, <i>Shireen</i> !	<i>paroo Farhaad wee</i>

(pp. 246–249).

Khan uses *Mansoor* as his favourite symbol to emphasise the significance of combining material and material into one human self. *Mansoor* falls so deeply in love with his beloved, the divine truth, that he makes a throne out of himself. Having made that, he even begins worshipping the throne. The throne symbolises the seat of the divine is not somewhere far in the heavens but very much close and before the eyes of *Mansoor*, the lover. It is not acceptable to the priest, who teaches the divine residing somewhere far in the heavens. If the priest does not teach this, the market will be compromised. Consequently, the priest demolishes the throne built by *Mansoor* for own worship since that is working like a death knell to his business. The priest is the exact antonym of *Mansoor*, symbolising authoritarianism and dogmatism. Khan’s poem thus fits in with the *Akbarian* and Kantian frameworks to criticise the religious bigots for

their materialism and superficiality. Khan writes in his poem “*Mansoor*” (*Mansoor*), while criticising the bigotry of the religious clerics and idealising the sacrifice of *Mansoor*, who has borne intolerable suffering:

I prepared a throne of love,	<i>Maa da meeni takht ka jurr khaisht la di</i>
For beauty of Beloved’s face;	<i>janaan da makh</i>
Furtively, the pious priest,	<i>Ghalay warta rroond mulla ghalay laka</i>
On it like a snake emerged!	<i>maar wukhath</i>

(pp. 204–205).

Time is immaterial and perceptive. Change occurs in material phenomena only, but it gets meaning in terms of time. Time wraps up so tightly around human experience that it becomes inseparable. Time becomes as material as our material experience or existence is. This approach fits in entirely with Kant, who considers time to be part of perception. On the contrary, Ibn Arabi makes time perceptive as well as objective, existing at different levels from the divine to the realm of material existence. Sometimes, Khan also intensifies the conflict between the material and the immaterial through the analogies of time and mortality. His poem “*Wakht*” (*Time*) presents time like a cup of ecstasy, short-lived and fleeting. According to Ibn Arabi, time embodies the impression of a divine attribute that, in its essence, combines the past, present and future. It is neither perceptive nor objectively absolute by dynamic. Khan describes this state of mortality and the fleeting nature of life against the dynamic movement of time in the following words:

If break you must, now is the time	<i>Ay da masti jaama dagha staa da mateedu</i>
To break, oh cup of ecstasy!	<i>dey wakht</i>
Do not in the mirror look,	<i>Ma gura aina ki Laila hasi ba di wuzharai</i>
<i>Laila</i> , it will sadden you.	<i>Laarra kah zwaani shee bia har wakht da</i>
When our youth has passed away,	<i>zharreedu dey wakht</i>
Anytime is time to grieve!	

(pp. 234–237).

Nothing material will ever live beyond a limited duration of time.

Khan becomes critical in his poem “*Da Faqeeranu Ghazal*” (*The Hermit’s Sonnet*) of the material preoccupation. Even the vast and rich towns of the past have been turned into desolation and rubble. Material attachment only brings pain and a deeper sense of loss in the end, since nothing material is enduring:

Every atom cries out,	<i>Har zara krree duaa chi duniyaa da faanee</i>
Life is fleeting, shall pass.	
And yesterday’s towns	<i>Da paroon khaaryu ki nan da weeraanee</i>
Are silent and still.	
Life is only a dream.	<i>Dey yau khub daa zhwandoon daa zwaanee</i>
And youth is no more	<i>yau nasha</i>
Then the pleasure of wine;	
Why fret over it?	<i>Wali zee pa zharraa wali zee pa zharraa</i>
Is the question to ask!	

(pp 232–233).

Thus, Khan strikes a mystical note more in line with Ibn Arabi, though Kant can also not be underwritten. Khan tries to bring a synthesis between the material and the immaterial. He considers these as dimensions of the cosmic self through the portrayal of images that bridge the gap between the phenomenal and the noumenal realms. Both Khan and Keats converge on accepting the existence of a higher, ineffable noumenal (immaterial) realm. Being poets, both agree that the noumenal realm can become accessible through imagination and synthesis of the material and immaterial.

5.5. Cosmic Self – Essence and Existence

Khan’s work presents a rich tapestry of exploration into the themes of essence and existence as dimensions of the cosmic self. His themes can be interpreted in the mystical and philosophical frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Khan’s poetry probes beneath the surface, exploring the transcendent through images that encompass both the sensory and the supra-

sensory realms. He is in pursuit of exploring the philosophical and mystical questions of being and uncovering the connection between the earthly and the divine.

Khan's poem "*Zama Da Bachu Mur*" (*The Mother of My Children*) reflects a mystical theme that "a flower from heaven..." is gifted by an angel like a poet who is given poetry in imagination. He ties existence and the divine into one connection with humans, being located at the manifest end (pp. 4–5). As far as Kant's metaphysics and epistemology are concerned, he is a dualist who holds that the phenomenal realm exists on the visible and perceptible end and the noumenal realm on the invisible, ineffable and imperceptible end. Both exist independently of each other. The world of being or phenomena is perceived through spatial, temporal and causal relationships, but the noumena cannot be perceived through these filters.

Khan follows this in his poem "*Shandaana*" (*Shandana*), where he connects the intangible essence and tangible existence when recounting the beauty of his granddaughter. The essence of the human self is shown to be derived from the divine effulgence. Ibn Arabi also argues the same in his mystical framework of the Unity of Being. This essence becomes existence when Khan compares her coming down on earth to a particle being drowned in the wide river. Khan writes on the birth of his granddaughter:

A drop of moonlight	<i>Awa yawa zara da noor wa</i>
Drowned on beauty's moonlit waters;	<i>Shwa daryaab ki da noor dooba</i>
A splash of starlight	<i>Pa khuboonu da zwaanee ki</i>
Woven in the dreams of youth...	<i>Yawa shughla da noor payelee</i>

(pp. 10–11).

Khan thus connects the essence and existence, though accepting the elusiveness of the essence.

Khan lends existence profounder meanings than it appears to have. He recalls a letter written by his beloved wife in "*Faridoon Da Mur Khat*" (*Letter from Faridoon's Mother*), when he was behind bars. He connects the existent self with the essence of all creation. Khan

describes his wife as being the essence of all existence in the universe, “I became the path and guide; / I became the cup and wine...” (pp. 14–19).

Ibn Arabi’s mystical philosophy emphasises the unity of essence and existence. On the contrary, Kant’s transcendental idealism focuses on the duality of existence, with one aspect being empirical or phenomenal and the other being transcendental or noumenal. Khan also reasserts the same conflict between the empirical and the transcendent in his poem “*Talaash*” (Search). He writes “black and whirling river of anxiety...” reflecting the acceptance of the Kantian incapacity of the human reason to delve deeper than the sensory. He emphasises this by the images of “a spark of light...” or “a fire in the wilderness,” displaying negligible human understanding of the noumenal essence that Khan tries to unveil through annihilation by “drowning within the whirlpool” (pp. 82–89).

Khan’s poem “*Saakht*” (Creation) describes essence and existence. He writes “To each is apportioned its proper weight, / Held in balance, in harmony...” and thus connects the essence and existence into balance. It also highlights that reality exists on the ends of both essence and existence. Neither can be ignored or denied. Humans are also especially blessed with the insight to understand and discover the true essence of the power of reason. Khan further writes about the ineffable essence (noumena):

Who are you? Where are you? What are	<i>Charta yi sanga yi kum zaai yi</i>
you?	<i>Dalta khabara di wraana shee</i>
These are the questions unanswered till	<i>Nura chi har sumra grana shee</i>
now.	<i>Wru wru pa fikr asana shee</i>

(pp. 34–35).

On many occasions, Khan displays ambiguity on the unity of essence and existence. In his poem “*Mashaal*” (Mashaal), Khan acknowledges the human capacity to create and serve as the

essence of another creation like a candle that lights another candle. Khan's daughter-in-law becomes the source of creation when she says:

<i>Nageena</i> was all laughter,	<i>Nageena pa khandaa shwa navee gul</i>
At the fresh rose and the spring;	<i>navee bahaar ta</i>
And cried out to me, "Baba!	<i>Wi gura baba! Navey gul mi raawrru</i>
I have added a new flower,	<i>staa gulzaar ta</i>
To the garden of your dreams;	<i>Wa'ada mi krra poora chi kuma taa aw</i>
And fulfilled for you the promise	<i>maa wa krree</i>
Made to you some time ago,	<i>Daa laal mi dar la turu daryaboounu ki</i>
And tis ruby recovered,	<i>moondaley</i>
From the swirling waters deep."	

(pp. 24–25).

Khan's poem "*Badiva*" (*The Kite*) reflects human desire to explore and uncover the essence behind creation. In this attempt human self soars high in heaven. Since humans take their essence from the divine, therefore, like a kite they soar in heaven on the hope of getting closer to the divine essence. Essence, however, always remains elusive and inaccessible:

In a wide expanse of sky,	<i>Dumra weerr asmaan ki da khpal rang</i>
Streaks of colour you display,	<i>saaskey khkaara krri ta</i>
Mounted on the steed of wind,	<i>Baad baandi war sur di laandi</i>
You observe the static form,	<i>khaawru nandaara krri ta</i>
Of the earth stretched out below;	<i>Ta da banyaadam da bakht aw tikhti</i>
And your form, a clutch of clay,	<i>yau tasweer yi</i>
Into madness you transform.	<i>Yawa rangeen khumaar pa taar</i>
	<i>tarralee da taqdeer yi</i>

(pp. 24–25).

In another poem, “*Laka Wakhlee Chi Mashoom*” (Like a Child Who Plays), Khan highlights the process of continuous creation. Essence, which is the unknowable ground of all creation (Ibn Arabi), keeps continuously creating. This process of continuous creation is rejected by Kant, though. Through the depiction of a child who drops flowers in a flowing stream, Khan represents a continuous flow of life and creation. The child symbolises essence, who keeps dropping flowers (existence) in the flowing stream (world). The image presents a continuous phenomenon. Khan also accepts the intelligible and noumenal nature of essence. Khan writes:

Like who plays,	<i>Laka waakhli chi mashoom</i>
With a basket full of flowers,	<i>Dakk shkarey da sru guloonu</i>
And in great glee and laughter,	<i>Khaandee chaghi wayi ghurzai yi</i>
Throws its contents to the waves;	<i>Lapi lapi pa maujoonu</i>
On the shore he stands amused,	<i>Dey pa ghaarra warta khaandee</i>
As the flood devours the flowers;	<i>Kharr sailaab yi gul yausee</i>
And he little understands...	<i>Na pa zur da sailaab puigee</i>

(pp. 96–99).

Khan’s poem “*Deodasi*” also revolves around the theme of the search for essence. It is always the creator who appears reflected in creation. The poet compares this dimension of the creator being reflected in creation through an artist, a poet or a painter whose inner self always gets reflected in creation. The higher the intensity, the greater the creation. So is with the divine that holds the actual essence of humans. The divine also manifests itself through creation. Looked at from this angle, it demands that humans should keep looking for the true essence. Khan describes this manifestation of the essence in the following words:

If it’s <i>Laila</i> whom I paint,	<i>Ka tasweer da Laila jurr krram da Shireen</i>
Or <i>Shireen</i> , intense <i>Mansoor</i> ,	<i>ka da Mansoor</i>
In the eyes of each, reflected,	

Is myself, my pain, my dreams... *Da har yau stargu ki za yem zamaa darrd*

(pp. 104–111). *zamaa khuboona*

Moreover, in the same poem, the “world of feeling, beauty” being lost to consciousness also aligns with the Kantian concept of noumena (intangible and essence). Such a futile search, failing to win unity with the essence, leaves behind only “smouldering pain” (pp. 104–111).

In his poem “*Wru*” (*Softly*), Khan turns the sunrays into the seething ocean of light. The essence and existence are emphasised through the images of spark and particle. The sunrays also symbolise a continuous vital force being poured into existence. All existence is rooted in an ineffable essence. By the *Akbarian* philosophy, this existence emanates from the divine essence, which is light and effulgence. Khan says:

And I, a dream of morn, a hope by night	<i>Za da sahar khub da shpi umeed yem da wisaal</i>
Of union in my dreams;	<i>Za da chaa da mast zrra yau basarey yem da</i>
Of some ecstatic heart a spark	<i>khiyal</i>
Of roving fancy, free.	<i>Nmar dey yau daryaab jurr da shughlu zaru</i>
The sun’s a brimming ocean	<i>zaru</i>
Of the rays of glittering light;	<i>Nmar hara zara da nmar, daryaab da daryaab</i>
The sun, its every particle –	<i>saaskee</i>
An ocean in expanse.	<i>Baam da ishq wuchat dey daa ka’abi da</i>
The eminence of love transcends	<i>manaaru</i>
Both minarets and domes!	

(pp. 112–113).

Particles of the sunrays symbolise the divine. Existence being held by an ocean within itself is like an indivisible cosmic whole being held together by the essence.

The essence of humanity resides in the immaterial and spiritual world, where a supreme and invisible power designs it, as Khan portrays in his poem “*Sawal Jawab da Lewani aw Mulla*” (*The Pious Priest and the Madman*). The poet describes the essence of human existence as a “flower” rooted in the “longing” of the divine:

And, oh madman! finally,	<i>Lewanaya! ta yi suk?</i>
Who are you and all your kind?	
I am just somebody's longing,	<i>Mullah! za da chaa armaan</i>
And a flower of someone's shapely	
Tapering fingers, <i>hennaed</i> bright,	<i>Za yau gul da chaa da gutu</i>
Lying only in repose	
Of beloved's pretty feet.	<i>Prut pa pkhu ki da janaan</i>

(pp. 116–119).

As reflected in the above excerpt, despite being the epitome of beauty, the flower, symbolically representing existence, dissolves in the beloved's feet out of reverence and humility. Kant would interpret this as reality existing in both the realm of phenomena and the realm of noumena, which are represented by the flower and the beloved, with their distinct existences, respectively.

Khan often becomes a pantheist in his "*Laarr Sha*" (*Get Away!*). He considers physical existence (phenomenal) as a manifestation of the divine. Superficial and dictatorial priests lack the capacity to uncover the divine essence due to their preoccupation with material existence. If they do not have the required insight, then they can equally not discover the true message in the Holy Book, which is the phenomenal existence of the noumenal essence, saved as a word. Khan makes the flower and its existence symbolic of the divine essence. While describing this state of essence and existence, and a longing to uncover the mystery behind existence, Khan writes in his poem "*Laarr Sha*" (*Get Away!*):

Get away, Oh pious priest!	<i>Laarr sha mullah jaana! sa dee staa pa</i>
What is there in all your books?	<i>kitaaboону ki</i>
We have been promised, in our dreams,	<i>Moong sara wa'adi da wafaa shawee dee</i>
Faithful love and constancy!	<i>khuboону ki</i>
And my youthful love, so bright,	<i>Meena mi rukhaana pa mastee aw</i>
Is engulfed in ecstasy;	<i>khumaaroonu ki</i>
And His mercy is apparent	

In each smiling flower's face! *Rahm yi muskay dey da guloonu pa*
(pp. 122–123). *makhoonu ki*

The following analogy from Khan's poem "*Tapus ka Jawaab*" (Question or Answer) is enough to spellbind readers with its ingenuity. Khan answers a question in one of his poems when asked what life is:

Is it drawing-pails of water, *Mangootee ka da arat dee*
On a *Persian* water-wheel – *sa dakeegee sa tasheegee*
Some being filled as others empty,
Their sweet contents on the ground?

(pp. 124–127).

In the above excerpt, life is like the buckets on the *Persian* wheel, tied to the essence through several intermediaries, such as the *Persian* wheel, the wooden liver, the bull and humans controlling the wheel. The essence thus rests in the divine will attaching the bucket to itself through the wheel and wooden lever. Gnostics hold that essence rests in a lesser power because the divine is too sublime to create this imperfect world. Thus, the poem presents a cyclical relationship between essence and existence, constantly circulating between the phenomenal and the noumenal realms.

Khan presents an analogy in his poem "*Ajaba Falsafa*" (*Strange Philosophy*) where the poet accepts the ontologically existential state of the human self as derived from the physical realm, akin to being made of clay. However, it combines in its essence both the material and the immaterial:

From my posture as I bend, *Daa chi sumra khkata tlay shee pa sajda*
From my forehead all prostrate; *zamaa jabeen*
From my body made of clay, *Daa chi sumra akhlee noor daa zamaa*
As it takes on divine light; *khaakee wujood*

From my tongue as it takes in, *Daa chi sumra zamaa zhabah shee sakalay*
Taste of honey that's divine. *angbeen*

(pp. 132–143).

The above-quoted lines evoke the images of clay and divine light that not only elucidate the *Akbarian* mystical philosophy of Unity of Being as one in essence and existence but also the Kantian philosophy of moral principle when the poet describes his “tongue as it takes in, / Taste of honey that's divine...” (pp. 132–143).

According to Ibn Arabi, humans are a reflection of love and beauty, with the divine as their essence, fostering human self-appreciation. Everything takes its essence from the creator (ineffable and invisible), but the creation is visible in its existence. Khan's poem “*Da Buḍay Taal*” (*The Rainbow*) reflects a journey from the physical world of existence to the realm of essence, in pursuit of attaining unity with the divine essence. Khan begins this journey with the wine and goblet in his hand:

And when I went out asearching, *Daa chi za pa talaash laarrum*
A fine staging-post I found; *Pus paraaw maqaam mi wumoond*
And when I thirsted for beauty, *Daa chi za taagey da noor yem*
Fair *saki* and goblet found. *Speen saki ao jaam mi wumoond*

(pp. 148–149).

As evidenced in the above lines, Ibn Arabi's concept of unity in multiplicity is through the images of flower, light and fire, holding a single essence. Similarly, Khan also accepts the Kantian emphasis on limitations of human reason to discover the ecstasy of love, “In the dark world of cold logic, / Lover's madness has been lost...” (pp. 148–149).

The theme of essence and existence gets repeated in another poem, “*Dwa Stargi*” (*Two Eyes*). Every created existence, including earth, underground and sky, derives its existence from the essence. It is manifested everywhere, from the place of holy worship to the temple of

idolatry. Khan presents this all-encompassing image of the universe from station to station in the following words:

Sometimes I gaze at the earth,	<i>Kala guram zmaki ta aw kala guram sturu ta</i>
And sometimes at stars above,	<i>Aw kala gulistaan ki da qabroonu khaazu turu ta</i>
And sometimes, in the fields of flowers,	<i>Guram but khaana ki staa da husan tajallee kala</i>
At tombstones grey, and bluish black...	<i>Kala pa sajdu ka'abah ki guram khalqu nuru ta</i>

(pp. 164–167).

In the above lines, the images conform to the philosophical frameworks of both Ibn Arabi and Kant. He accepts the existence of the physical world as well as its essence. Kant, though, does not believe in separate essence; he argues for separate phenomenal and noumenal realms.

Khan makes physical existence subject to some predetermined rules. Khan symbolises life with a river, which goes through different circumstances in its existence in the physical realm. However, it keeps moving towards its real essence. It derives sustenance from the essence, but is fated to follow pre-set paths. These paths are like a river flowing through a set course, watering, expanding and drying up and finally losing its identity through dissolution in the ocean. He argues for humans moving towards the final destination in their real essence.

Khan's poem "*Seenda za Seenda Bahiga*" (*Flow Oh River, Flow Along...*):

Every man is like a river,	<i>Har sarray seend dey rawaan kala mast aw</i>
And forever on the go,	<i>kala wru</i>
Sometimes jubilant and frisky,	<i>Kala ghar kala maidaan ki kala ghaley pa miru</i>
Sometimes pensive, very slow;	<i>Da qismat da zanzeer wal dey daa da dah</i>
Sometimes in the gorges deep,	<i>raftaar da tlo</i>
Then o'er undulating plains,	<i>Da ubu rasolu chal dey har waakhah wuni</i>
Over arid wastelands, vast,	<i>gulaab la</i>
In a quiet, easy sweep;	<i>Seend khpal khaisht aw gharsangoona</i>
And the chain of fate has bound him,	<i>shukraana wurree daryaab la</i>
To a pre-determined speed.	
It's a question of conveying,	
To each blade of grass, each rose,	
And to each majestic tree	

Both its sustenance and life.
All its beauty and its surging,
As it dashes over the rock,
In a tribute to be paid,
To the expectant ocean floor.

*Seenda za seenda bahiga! seenda za seenda
bahiga!*

(pp. 169–173).

For Khan, existence encompasses both the grandeur and breadth of the divine and the simplicity of the mundane. Khan’s poem “*Gugal*” (*My Bosom*) synchronises the essence and existence quite like the *Akbarian* mystical philosophy. He considers humans to be composed of the effulgence and fire. Khan even becomes philosophical when, like the ancient philosophers, he describes the essence of humans as being composed of different particles. However, in physical existence, humans hardly display divine attributes. Khan describes this in the following lines:

[O my strange God
I am composed of everything except
you,
This ocean of light and fire
So vast as to cover the whole sky
And so tiny like a droplet...

*Ajiba di yem jurr karrey
Ay zamaa Khudaya ajaba
Bi da taa na nur da har sa
Da hauma yem murakaba
Daa da ur aw noor daryaab
Dumra lui laka asmaan
Dumra wrukey laka saaskay
Dumra land laka yau aan
Daa qissa da suz aw saaz
Wali wali sa la sa la?*

(pp. 182–187).

The above lines fall in the *Akbarian* mystical framework of essence and its manifestation through existence. These also align with the Kantian transcendental idealism. Kant makes human perception responsible for interpreting the world of existence. This poem sounds like a philosophical manifesto by Khan. He makes the human heart hold an entire universe within.

Khan’s poem “*Shpa Wah Da Spralee*” (*It was a Night in Early Spring*) is a practical example of essence and existence. He makes everything exist with an essence behind it. Khan opens the poem by declaring rhythm and balance as the essence behind existence. Life seems to be full of pain and sadness, but in reality, it is much more than that. Khan also suggests that

the existence on earth is not just about happiness, but also about sadness. This pain always follows upon material beauty that is transitory and fleeting. Khan considers beauty as the essence of all existence. Both Ibn Arabi and Kant consider that harmony and balance are significant aspects of existence:

Cycle of the rhythmic beats,	<i>Taal da saaz zhwandoon dey chi gadeegi pa</i>
Is the life of music's notes	<i>suroonu ki</i>
As they dance within each tune,
.....
.....	<i>Sta da swaal jawaab shta na jumaat ki na</i>
Neither in the numerous books,	<i>kitaab ki shta</i>
Nor within the countless mosques;	<i>Dagha de pat shawey dey musaigi pa guloonu</i>
But, here it is all hidden, and	<i>ki</i>
Smiling at the numerous flowers!	

(p. 194–197).

The same poem, “*Shpa Wah Da Spralee*” (It was a Night in Early Spring), further elaborates on the Kantian dualism as well by acknowledging the limitations of the human reason to unveil the essence (noumenal). So, Khan rejects reason and the books of logic as sources of finding answers to the question of the relation between essence and existence. This can be discovered with the help of intuitive insight and aesthetic experience. Khan says:

Beauty, only beauty, is,	<i>Husan dey bas hasan chi ham Khudai aw ham</i>
	<i>janaan dey</i>
Both God and the beloved,	<i>Di fani makaan ki bal mashaal da laamakaan</i>
	<i>dey</i>
In this finite, transient world,	<i>Yau da gulaab makh ki chi khkaara kum</i>
	<i>jawaboona dee</i>
A flambeau from Eternity...	<i>Nishta yau ham nishta da mantaq pa kitaaboonu</i>
	<i>ki</i>

(pp. 194–197).

The essence of the human self rests in the creator. There is no need to look for the creator either in the heavens or in the barren deserts. This theme is conveyed by Khan's poem “*Mansoor*” through the imagery highlighting beauty and unity as essence in the Akbarian framework. He

locates essence within one's self instead of being sought after in the heavens, "Searching Beauty in the sky, / In his heart a field of flowers, / To his great surprise emerged!" (p. 205). The poem also finds a parallel in the Kantian framework, which would interpret that ineffable noumenal reality unveiled by Mansoor. He says, "He had surely something seen, / That is why to the gallows he went..." and thus confessing his limitations of the rational capacity to go beyond existence (pp. 204–205).

Existence in the physical realm is transitory. Humans often hide aspects of transience in the crowd of life by losing themselves in music, youth and the beloved, which are nevertheless fleeting. These fill the poet with grief. One finds the theme of essence and existence portrayed vividly in Khan's poem "*Da Zhamee Makhaam*" (*A Winter's Eve*), where the sound of a "crackling fire" is juxtaposed with the "music of life" and the "beloved's charm" (p. 206). Khan evokes the *Akbarian* metaphysics of the essence and existence. These are indivisibly one and part of the divine essence like the "beloved's charm" being concealed in the "music, / Of youth and its passion..." with the "main-string of grief" constantly reminding the existence of its finitude and transitoriness (pp. 206–207). This also aligns with Kant's concept of life being a combination of opposites. It is the beauty that is inherent not in the object but in the human self that perceives it. He thus endows the self with the cosmic strength to perceive beauty.

Khan's poem "*Yau Khub da Shaair da Sabaa da Ranrraa*" (*A Dream of a Poet*) combines the frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant, exploring notions of beauty, light, divine attributes and the sublime. The poem evokes a strong resonance of temporality and transitoriness of existence. It is coupled with transcendence, such as the "dream" of a poet about "morning and light," which highlights the temporal connotation of existence through words of a dream. Morning and light are never permanent but fleeting moments being part of the "heavenly light" as would be interpreted by Ibn Arabi (pp. 214–215). Another line states that it comes and goes like a

dream in this world, asking what it was that passed away and what it is that has come to the world, as if humans are in a state of ignorance despite having experienced life. This reflects the Kantian noumenal, which eludes human reason and understanding. Ibn Arabi's continuous process of creation is reflected in Khan's poetry when he compares humans to members of a caravan that comes to this world, stays for a little while, and then departs. The concluding lines, however, evoke the Kantian notion about the ineffability of the noumenal essence, depicting the poet's state of confusion and ignorance. He tries to know whether all this coming and going of humans to this world, like a dream, is a result of damnation or a consequence of bliss that assumes physical form in this world. Khan writes:

What was it that's gone,	<i>Daa sa woo chi tir shoo, daa sa woo chi</i>
What is it that's here	
A caravan moving	<i>raaghlah</i>
But whose? And of what?	
Beloved, my sweet-heart,	<i>Da sa qafila, daa da chaa qafila?</i>
My heart-throb, my love!	
Was this just a dream,	<i>Janaana dilbara janaana zamaa</i>
Or the tale of my love?	<i>Daa sta wu yau khub ka qisa wa zamaa</i>

(pp. 194–197).

In another poem, “*Qismat*” (Fate) Khan uses his favourite images of the pliant clay, the potter, the wine-cup, the ewer, the candle on the mausoleum, lamp in the tavern and battered heap. These highlight the process of how and where humans take their essence from in a comparison with a pot of clay. This pot, though, is equally liable to be broken into pieces quite easily. So it is with humans who can be broken and turned into dust easily. This also depicts the human self not as independent but as dependent upon the will of the divine to be turned into whatever the divine wills it to be. This poem again compares essence with the noumenal and intelligible divine, but the phenomenal existence is nothing more than a “particle of dust.” Khan says:

Little matter, but being pliant clay,	<i>Za narma khaṭa yem, laas da kulaal ki</i>
In unknown hands, that mould me as	
they will –	

Perhaps into a goblet,	<i>Yaa ba da mayu jaam sham au yaa koozah</i>
Of varied hue and dye,	
To be kissed by drunken lips	<i>da jumaat</i>
Or pitcher, to be touched by pious hands	<i>Yaa divagey da ziyarat da maykhaani</i>
And hold but only water in my being;	<i>faanoos</i>
Or lamp, to hold a wavering taper of a night,	<i>Yaa da dairaan teekrey sawey aw maat</i>
And light fair revellers to a senseless slate;	<i>Zwaanee mastee zhwandoon da bal da laasa</i>
Or light with unctuous glow,	<i>dee</i>
Some pious shrine;	
Or battered, on a dung-heap,	<i>Zamaa na was shta aw na mi waak</i>
Midst the dust,	
Lie, but another particle of dust!	

(pp. 216–217).

The human self is thus the reflection of the divine, with all actions and decisions willed by the divine, leaving humans as will-less and helpless. However, like Kant, Khan also accepts the limitations of the human self, despite being blessed with an indomitable will and rational power. Khan also poses questions about dual realities, which continually transform from one state of essence to another state of existence and vice versa. For instance, the clay represents Ibn Arabi’s idea of the essence, which transforms itself into multiple forms, such as a pitcher that may have been designed by a pious hand. This transcendence also highlights the dual realms of phenomena and noumena, aligning with Kantian philosophy, where the essence in the noumenal realm remains inaccessible to human understanding.

In another poem, “*Wakht*” (**Time**), Khan further delves into the question of essence and existence with reference to time. The existence of time is as temporary as that of existence. The way existence undergoes different stages, so is the case with time that moves on. Time is linked with the internal human state. It lies in human perception, wraps around and defines their experiences. In literature, the noon time symbolises the climax of one’s life. There is only the twilight or the evening of life, followed by the onset of darkness and blindness, representing

death. Noon time, being the representative of the climax of life, is the time of youthful vigour and energy:

The mid-afternoon of Summer –	<i>Takkanrra ghrama da liwnu da garzeedu dey wakht</i>
Time for fools to take a walk!	<i>Laarraah, tar wagmi da yaar di stargu da leedu dey wakht</i>
As the twilight hour set in –	<i>Zirr mazigaray da zhwand ghamgina shaan nasha laree</i>
Time to get a glimpse of love,	<i>Tura shpa da zhemi da awrolu awreedu dey wakht</i>
And to hear soft replies.	

(pp. 234–237).

In the above lines from the poem “**Time**,” Khan evokes a sense of impermanence about the phenomenal world, which extracts existence from the essence in the noumenal or supra-sensory world. On the contrary, time exists in human perception that helps structure human experiences. Khan seems closer to Ibn Arabi than to Kant because he does not limit time to human perception, but rather to reveal the true essence of things.

Like the atomistic philosophers, Khan also locates human essence in particles. He may use this particle as a symbol of the worthlessness of humans. However, in ancient philosophy, human was considered to have been created out of a particle. Human is composed of light and particles of dust, holding light and dark, good and sin inside, symbolising essence and existence in Khan’s poem “***Pa Awya Kaalah Zhwandoon Ki***” (**Of the Three Score Years and Ten**). Khan writes:

Oh of light and moon the master!	<i>Da nuroonu spugmu Khaana! zarah</i>
What is there that can be found,	<i>khaawra ki ba sa wee</i>
In a particle of dust?	
How much darkness,	<i>Sumra shpa sumra ranrra sumra kha sumra</i>
How much light,	
How much virtue,	<i>guna</i>
How much sin?	

(pp. 256–257).

The above lines are characteristic of Khan because it is customary for him to question metaphysical issues of essence and existence. He becomes sceptical in this poem. He accepts the limited capacity of human reason to unveil the noumenal (Ibn Arabi's essence). The poem also aligns with Kantian duality, featuring a contrast between light and dark, as well as virtue and sin. "Of the Three Score Years and Ten" also follows an *Akbarian* approach, which compares the divine knowledge and lack of knowledge to light and dark, respectively.

Besides arguing for the atomistic composition of the world, Khan also supports the impermanence of life in his poem "*Da Faqiranu Ghazal*" (*The Hermit's Sonnet*). This poem forbids shedding tears and accepts what is at one's disposal. Since the essence of humans is dust that mixes with the earth after spending some time in existence. Every particle of the earth manifests transitoriness and decay. For Ibn Arabi, transience may be considered as weak composition by the ordinary, but for the gnostics, it is an imperfect manifestation of the divine, like a light that is reflected through a mirror. Khan writes in the same poem regarding this quintessential attribute of humans:

This world is no more	<i>Wrura dey daa jahaan yau makaan da</i>
Than a dwelling, whose fate	<i>fana</i>
Is extinction and loss;	<i>Warta ma krra zhara warta ma krra</i>
Why fret over it! Why fret over it	<i>zharra</i>
The flower, which was born	<i>Makhaam khaawri shee gul, chi sahar</i>
With the light of the morn,	<i>shee paida</i>
By the shades of the evening	<i>Warta ma krra zharra warta ma krra</i>
Is gone and no more...	<i>zharra</i>

(pp. 232–233).

Khan employs images accentuating the fleeting nature of life, such as flowers that dissolve into dust. Sometimes, it is even the smallest particle of an atom that grieves over its impermanence.

Khan adopts the *Akbarian* approach, viewing existence as impermanent, yet also permanent, being rooted in the divine. Kant rejects any connection between the phenomenal world (roughly Ibn Arabi's existence) and the noumenal world (roughly Ibn Arabi's essence). Khan often integrates both the frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant in his poetry by developing a concept of the cosmic self. He focuses on the mystical relationship between the human self as existence and the divine as essence. He rejects segregation between the essence and the existence as in Kantian transcendental idealism.

5.6. Cosmic Self through the Intercession of Love and Beauty

Khan eulogises love above all other sentiments. Khan speaks like a mystic in his poem "*Sail*" (Excursion), where he gets ecstatic in love to the extent of surrendering the pleasures of life and becoming an ascetic:

We have tasted the wine,	<i>Moong da janaan da shoonda sharaab</i>
Of the beloved's lips,	<i>sakalee dee</i>
Drunk and ecstatic are we;	<i>Zaka mast mast majnoonan nan biyaban ta</i>
Therefore, obsessed like <i>Majnoon</i> ,	<i>zoo</i>
Let's to the wilderness go...	

(pp. 254–255).

This resonates with Ibn Arabi's framework, which posits that divine love is the essence of creation and existence, thereby linking creation and the Creator in a cosmic connection of unity. On the other hand, Kant does not consider love to be a metaphysical experience, but rather a principle of the moral universal. Khan is thus closer to Ibn Arabi in his approach towards love rather than to Kant.

Love and beauty interweave different dimensions of the cosmic self. These are the inseparable dimensions of the cosmic self. The following paragraphs highlight images that convey the themes of love and beauty from mystical and philosophical perspectives.

Ibn Arabi considers love as the focal point that brings convergence between the physical and the divine selves by merging them with the essence and existence, material and immaterial. This transcendence of love from the physical to the spiritual is reflected in Khan’s poem “*Wali*” (*Why?*). In this poem, he juxtaposes the pains of love with the comforts of beauty, exhibiting multiple and paradoxical attributes that combine the finite and infinite into one. Kant’s concept of beauty rests on the subjective and perceptive capacity of the human self, which makes its harmony and balance created by the interplay of imagination and understanding. It is aimed at some implicit purpose without being explicitly purposeful (Kant’s beauty has a purpose without purpose). Khan writes:

Love, with flowing tears spoke;	<i>Meeni pa zharra wuwi</i>
Beauty, in love laughter spoke;	<i>Husan pa khanda wuwi</i>
And to me, in smiling eyes,
My beloved gently spoke –	<i>Wuli suk zrra wubaailee?</i>
.....	<i>Sa rangi shaida shee suk?</i>
How is it one falls in love?	<i>Suk chi chaa ta wukhaandee</i>
Why, when someone smiles at one,	<i>Wuli pa khandaa shee suk?</i>
One returns the smile anon?	

(pp. 6–7).

Khan accepts that beauty and love are mightier than reason. He emphasises this theme in his poem “*Saakht*” (*Creation*). Khan means that a conflict always ensues between reason and beauty. Reason is incapable of reaching to the unknown and indefinable, but beauty does have the wings to soar beyond the rational, offering unity with the sublime: He writes:

Reason no more than two paces can take	<i>Aqal khu dwa gaama laarr shee bas</i>
Thereafter loses itself in the maze;	<i>Akhwa ta wruk aw hairaana shee</i>
In beauty there lies, Your ultimate proof,	<i>Husan ki hagma daleel dey sta</i>

Enlightening the eyes of the heart and the soul. *Stargi da zrra pri rukhaana shee*

(pp. 34–35).

In another poem, “*Jannat aw Dunya*” (The World and Heaven), Khan emphasises the divine aspect of beauty and love as well as the endearment of these in the physical world for their impermanent nature here. Human heart becomes cosmic due to seat of love, a combination of firelight, and is blessed in its essence by the divine. Change is the beauty of life. But this impermanence and transitoriness hides its secret. Khan accentuates these themes through images, symbols and comparisons in the same poem. Love is both “fire and light” that burns in the heart, much like a furnace, aligning with the mystical viewpoint that love is both an enervating and consuming experience. Khan writes:

Love is fire and some light,	<i>Ishq sa ur wee aw sa noor wee zrra lamba</i>
Heart as smoulder and in flames,	<i>laka tanoor wee</i>
For this life I shall surrender,	<i>Pa di zhwand ba za warzaar krram janatoona</i>
Your eternal Paradise.	<i>staa tamaam</i>
.....
.....	<i>Zaka us rabaandi graan dey, chi yi khaisht</i>
It is now so loved, endearing	<i>shee zar tamaam</i>
As its beauty’s like the morn,	<i>Tal spugmai da swaarlasami, tal janaan da</i>
Like a dream that quickly fades;	<i>shpaarhsamey</i>
If the moon were not to wane,	<i>Husan ki hagma daleel dey sta</i>
Love were always to be young...	<i>Stargi da zrra pri rukhaana shee</i>

(pp. 56–57).

The above lines also reflect that beauty possesses a consummating force.

Khan’s poem “*Yau Jaam*” (A Goblet of Wine) displays the ecstasy of union. Khan associates love and beauty with the bashful smile of the beloved in many poems. It is a state of ecstasy and intoxication in beauty and love that he can forget his pain. Khan also longs for the

company of his beloved, without which life is prone to turn passive and inactive. Khan writes in this poem:

Raving mad, my dreams ignite,	<i>Mast mast raakrra khuboona chi patt krram</i>
Overcome my maddening grief;	<i>pri ghamoona</i>
To the rhythmic beat of life,	<i>Shuru krra da zhwand taal ta naazuk da</i>
Strike the notes of beauty's strains,	<i>khaisht suroona</i>
Lover and beloved be,	<i>Dilbar sha dilruba sha yau jaam jaam</i>
Bring a goblet full for me!	<i>raawrra</i>

(pp. 40–41).

Beauty has its essence in the divine. It is theophany. This comparison of the self with the flame continues in another poem by Khan titled “*Reedi Gul*” (*The Flower*). This flame derives its sustenance and light from the divine. Worldly beauty is the manifestation of divine beauty. Similarly, beauty attracts itself even if one is in a barren and desolate desert. This is Ibn Arabi's concept that all beauty rests in the ultimate beauty. Khan says:

Here is this parched arid land,	<i>Dalta de tur registan ki za da rang aw noor</i>
I'm a flame of blazing beauty	<i>lamba yem</i>
And of colours of all hues;	<i>Da khaisht chapah naghma yem, karishma</i>
I am beauty, with no peer,	<i>da lamakaan</i>
Of a silent melody;	<i>Staa pa baagh ki pa zargoonu dee gulaab</i>
And the miracle supreme,	<i>zamaa pa shaan</i>
Of a timeless space unseen.	<i>Yau bi nooma soor daryaab ki yau bi noom</i>
In your garden there are myriads	<i>saaskey rawaan</i>
Of red roses kin to me;	
In a faceless, flowing river	
Of red rose, one of too many,	
I shall certainly then be.	

(pp. 76–77).

As seen, Khan's philosophy of love also aligns with Ibn Arabi and Kant. He approaches the same subject differently, interpreting love in human and personal terms. Despite its mystical and philosophical connotations, Khan often defines love in human terms, as reflected in “*Bachay Chi Lui Shi*” (*My Child When You Grow Older*). He gives love the characteristics of

both ecstasy and suffering. Such characteristics are unique to humans, rather than being possessed by any angelic or heavenly being. Khan writes:

When in love you are entwined,	<i>Bachay chi luy shi, pa di ba pui shi</i>
You will ecstasy imbibe;	
You shall wait upon the wind,	<i>Hala ba mast shi chi bandiwaan shi</i>
When you suffer and sigh.	
My child, you must grow older,	<i>Hala ba khur shi chi aswilay shi</i>
My child, you must grow old.	<i>Bachiya! lui shi, bachiya! lui shi</i>

(pp. 32–33).

Beauty carries a transformative and transcendental force as reflected through Khan’s poem “*Da Fareedon da Mur Khat*” (Letter from Faridoon’s Mother). He projects the cup and the cupbearer as agents of vital force and regeneration. It not only fits in with Ibn Arabi’s mystical approach, considering the universe as experiencing a continuous creation, but also with Kant, considering beauty as a source of moral and intellectual dignity. Khan remains firmly grounded; however, sometimes he transcends the physical boundaries and acknowledges beauty for its mystical and emotional effects. Khan says:

These two finely formed red lips	<i>Daa sri sri da saqi shoondi sa mastee aw sa</i>
Of the <i>Saki</i> , and red wine;	<i>Khayyam</i>
In the burning of desire,	
Music’s melody divine;	<i>Daa pa soz ki rang da saaz dey, da member</i>
And atop the niche of the prayer,	<i>da paasa jaam</i>
Goblet bubbling with delight.	

(pp. 14–19).

Khan makes an entreaty in his poem “*Da Khaapiru Shahzadgai*” (The Fairy Princess) to be concealed by beauty from pain and suffering. The fairy princess lives in a fortified palace protected from suffering and pain. Kant’s aesthetic ideals are a source of protection from the painfully practical experiences of life. It falls within the *Akbarian* mystical philosophy. This philosophy, as discussed before, holds that beauty is the manifestation of the divine essence,

whose attainment brings solace and protection to the seekers. Khan pleads to the fairy princess in the following words:

...Oh princess!	<i>Maa wey ay da jannat bibi, za staa da dar</i>
I am your servitor;	<i>malang yema</i>
And will as a devotee,	<i>Dir tang da di jahaan da ghamoonu na yi</i>
Sit beside your palace door.	<i>tang yema</i>
I'm weary of the world outside,	<i>Lag pat mi krra da gham di turu stargu na</i>
Afraid of pain and store;	<i>mahal ki</i>
Oh hide me from the eyes of grief	<i>Zar wruka daa zara ba shee da sturu pa</i>
Within the palace walls...	<i>ghubal ki</i>

(pp. 48–51).

The above lines fall within the frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Khan is convinced that beauty transcends normal and mundane existence.

The kite is as a creation of love as human is of the divine. Khan's poem "*Badiwa*" (*The Kite*) symbolises human existence longing to be as close to love as possible. Despite being bound by fate, it aspires for the infinite. This dual approach reflects Kant's concept of the human condition as being suspended between sensory experience and moral aspiration. It also reflects Ibn Arabi's concept of the human soul as simultaneously bound by material existence but yearning for the divine. Khan's imagery remains distinct in its earthy and emotive resonance. These often ground cosmic themes in the immediacy of human experience. Khan makes the kite a product of love and beauty:

With your side-locks all aquiver,	<i>Sanree di rapeegee sa mastaana di raftaar</i>
What a drunken, rapturous gait	<i>dey</i>
You display, as you ascend	
Up the highway to the sky;	<i>Gura da kaaghaz na chaa jurr karrey khpal</i>
See how from some scraps of paper,	
Someone for himself has made,	<i>khumaar dey</i>
Self-intoxicating wine.	

Like a lover for his lass,	<i>Baad ta di ashiq pa shaani khaandi</i>
For the wind you wait –	
In all laughter, happiness,	<i>khushaligi ta</i>
In a patient state,	
Like a drunken peacock, you	<i>Masta sooli maara di taawus hasi gadigi ta</i>
Dance along the way...	

(pp. 70–71).

Khan’s poetry declares love and beauty as inseparable constituents of the cosmic self. He considers love and beauty as the forces that unify all creation. He makes it a medium of approach to the divine. Khan highlights this in his poem “*Jannat aw Duniya*” (**The World and Heaven**) by bringing both Ibn Arabi and Kant to a single point:

Love is fire and some light	<i>Ishq sa ur wee aw sa noor wee, zrra lamba</i>
Heart as a asmoulder and in flames,	<i>laka tanoor wee</i>
Like a furnace glowing bright,	<i>Pa di zhwand ba za warzaar krram</i>
For this life I shall surrender,	<i>janatoona staa tamaam</i>
Your eternal Paradise.	<i>Banda naway rang mahal ki nawey nawey</i>
Man in each new, tinted palace,	<i>janaan ghoari</i>
A fresh, new beloved craves;	<i>Tal tiara ki dey wrakigi, tal ranrra ki hum</i>
Fresh, red flowers in the desert...	<i>randeegi</i>

(pp. 56–61).

Khan’s poetry appears to strike a personal note. His poetry is relatable to all readers due to the physical and human touch that he brings to love and beauty.

Beauty and love are associated with longing and transitoriness. It is love that links the divine with creation, and it is the beauty that the divine manifests and acknowledges as its own. In his poem “*Deodasi*,” when he writes, “the longing of a dream,” he means that the human beauty of the maiden servant has no relation with the phenomenal in its entirety. The divine is always reflected in the maiden-servant *Deodasi* as given below:

And her beauty was nought else,	<i>Khaisht yi na wu, yaw arman wu da cha</i>
But the longing of a dream,	<i>shaayir khwub ki leedalay</i>
By a poet who dreamt and saw,	<i>Mrrawi stargu ki yi gham wu, khumari da</i>
In her drooping eyes was grief	<i>cha pa wruk</i>
And the ecstasy of love	
For a lover of her dreams.	

(104–111).

In the above lines, Khan thus venerates the beauty of *Deodasi* as having taken its source from the divine essence. He also laments over the transitoriness of life, when he recounts her beauty in words, “Of the flowers you are a fairy, / But, in youth’s ecstatic spring, / Why these colours of the fall...” and so he becomes not only *Akbarian* but also Kantian in his approach towards the concept of beauty (pp. 104–111).

For Kant, beauty is a subjective and personal experience. Kant propounds that beauty has a purpose without explicitly following a purpose, bringing harmony between imagination and understanding (Kneller, 1986). This world, along with all its beauties, cannot be without reason. These have been spread around for the sake of worldly creatures that were created with so much love and compassion. It is out of question to accept the argument of the dogmatic religious followers, who interpret the divine in terms of being vengeful and retributive. Khan’s poem “*Saprley*” (Spring) builds on the same theme by evoking images of colours. Colours like green and red, spread all around in the Spring, manifest the “cup-bearer’s love” (the divine). These elicit a personal and spiritual response from the poet, generating harmony in his inner world of imagination and understanding. The cup-bearer symbolises the divine, with the beauty of nature serving as a source of expression for universal balance and harmony. Khan describes this in the following words:

It's impossible to think that,
 Anyone can still believe,
 That the God who fashioned hell-fire,
 Is the same person who gave us these.

 This is the proof of the cup-bearer's love,
 This red wine brimming chalice
 The cup-bearer's eyes that are drunken
 This drunkenness has been made for me...]

*Daa dimaagh zama chari na mani
 Chi da gul khaliq ba saqar krree jurr
 Senga khwagi ba pri zama kreki lagi?
 Chaa che maa la nargis aw dilbar krru
 jurr
 Daa shinkay chaman, daa guloona sra
 Daa mast mast shaani mastaana
 makhaam,
 Daa saboot da saqi da meeni dey,
 Daa da sru sharabu barpura jaam.
 Da saqi chi stargi khumari di,
 Daa khumaar yi ma ta jurr karrey dey*

(pp. 188–192).

In the above lines, a compassionate, loving and attentive self invites trust and confidence. The divine being, closer than the jugular vein, is the only undeniable truth that can respond to the complainants and dejected souls.

Another poem by Khan, “*Dwa Stargi*” (*Two Eyes*), presents the intimate connection between the lover and the beloved. It inspires trust in sharing mysteries and untold secrets, which cannot be shared with anyone else. It strikes a note in line with Ibn Arabi’s concept of love. Khan appears to turn beloved into a manifestation of the cosmic self and essence that unites all existence. Khan writes:

Listen oh beloved Prince!

 To You in a moment one,
 All one’s secrets can confide.
 Secrets which to others, cannot

*Waawra shahzada zamaa, ghulam di gila
 mand dey
 Khalaq da ghmaoonu qisey krri stargu
 ghamkhuru ta
 Taa ta yau saa’at yawa lahza ki sarrey
 wuwaayi*

Over many years, it has been told...

Hagha chi waailey na shee nuru ta

(pp 164–167).

True Beauty can only be visualised by closing one's eyes and looking through the eyes of the heart. It need no follow logic and rationality. Search for beauty acquaints one with grief and pain. In his poem "*Ajaba Falsafa*" (*Strange Philosophy*), Khan evokes images of light, effulgence and intoxication. For example, "a slender thread of light," and "a wave of our drunkenness intense," that emanate from the divine, which Ibn Arabi equates with the divine manifestation. Khan thus describes this state in the following words:

Beauty does not have a form,

Khaisht Wajood laree na surey

Nor a shadow one can see,

*Da dah noor ba hala guri chi pa patu stargu
guri*

Its existence is apparent

Ilm speen rukha mashaal dey khu pri na shi

To closed eyes, which do not see!

leedey sturey

Knowledge is a lighted torch,

*Da noor stargi di pa zrrah ki da nuroonu
duniya guree*

But with it, one cannot see

Samandar da khaisht suk gir krree da

The bright radiance of stars.

mantaq pa kuzaney ki

(pp. 132–143).

Beauty lies in the harmony between love and beauty as well as between the physical and the spiritual. As such, spring is the season that brings harmony and synthesis between the physical environment and the spiritual state. Everything appears to be going well due to this synthesis. However, the contemplative and philosophical humans see something else in all this. They are filled with a sense of dejection at the transitoriness of this harmonious state of beauty and life. As highlighted earlier, Khan recounts in his poem "*Shpa Wa Da Sparlee*" (*It Was a Night in Early Spring*) that the soul being ensnared and imprisoned by beauty evokes a sense of earthly beauty, giving access to the divine. This physical world manifests the divine:

It was a night in early spring,	<i>Shpa wa da sparlee zhwand rapeedalu pa</i>
Life was throbbing in the buds,	<i>guloonu ki</i>
All the world was glowing bright,	<i>Tul jahaan rukhan wu wa tiarah zama</i>
Darkness clouded my sad thoughts.	<i>khiyaloonu ki</i>
Soft light of the moonbeams, soft,	<i>Aw khkulee da spugmei ranrra da mini da</i>
Like the voice of faithful love,	<i>awaz pa shaan</i>
Was attempting to entwine,	<i>Rooh yi da zhwandoon niwaw da husan pa</i>
Soul of life in beauty's snares.	<i>daamoonu ki</i>

(pp. 194–197).

Love has nothing to do with material appearances. It is driven by a longing to gain oneness with the beloved. Khan's concept of beauty is entirely spiritual. Khan demonstrates in his poem "*Liwaney aw Mulla*" (**Pious Priest and Madman**) a dialectical contact between a priest and a madman. Beauty, a "faintly smiling thought" and "a slender thread of light," is a subjective experience. He aligns his philosophical themes with beauty. However, he parts ways with Kant in considering love and beauty mutually inseparable, arousing emotive and spiritual effects in the beholder. Khan says:

What is beauty and its essence?	<i>Liwaneya! husan sa dey?</i>
Madman! Tell me if you please!	<i>Mullah! leher da khumaar dey</i>
Pious priest, it is a wave.	<i>Yau muskey muskey shaan khiyal dey</i>
Of our drunkenness intense	<i>Yau narey da ranrra taar dey</i>
And a faintly smiling thought,	
And a slender thread of light!	

(pp. 116–119).

It is only the emotion of love that brings union between the material and the immaterial. It allows to experience the spiritual in our mundane existence on earth. True love on earth is like

witnessing the reflection of the divine. Whatever experience one undergoes in earthly love is not different from connecting with the cosmic link to the divine. He has prepared Paradise and made the heavenly objects illuminate their path. Even the sight of the beloved's eyes is like drinking heavenly wine on earth, ushering in new life. One finds this philosophical dimension in Khan's poem "*Janaan*" (*Beloved*), where Khan again depicts the beloved's eyes as emitting "colours and light," spreading "myriad hues of love" all around. Thus, the manifestation of cosmic beauty is beloved, representing the synthesis of love and beauty. The same poem also offers a precedent of the Kantian concept of beauty and love, the subjective experiences. Khan writes about the paradoxical relationship of pain and comfort, joy and sad longing in the following words:

Eyes which are in love are immersed,	<i>Dwu mayinu stargu ki ragoona pa sawoonu</i>
Myriad hues of love reflect.	<i>Maa ta yi jahaan dakk kah da guloonu da nuroonu</i>
And for me, they fill the world,	<i>Goot yi da sharaabu da jannat pa jahaan raakah</i>
Full of colours and of light.	<i>Khub ki zhwandoon raaghey shu zhwandoon dakk da khuboonu</i>
.....
.....
Signs of God, so well concealed
In love's secrets you have revealed.	<i>Rabb di raata ukhud patt da meeni raazonu ki</i>
In my lap you've poured in heaps,	<i>Waa di chaul julai ki zama sturee pa pandoonu</i>
Shining stars wrapped in moonbeams.	<i>Saaz da houru awram staa da husan pa saazonu ki</i>
In your beauty's music heard,	
Is the music of fair damsels,	
As they dance in Heaven's ease.	

(pp. 210–211).

Khan often takes a unique approach towards love and beauty. There are poems where he turns love and beauty as emotive experiences. He describes the divine in terms of mercy and love towards creation, rather than cruelty. This humane perspective is evident in his poem “*Sparley*”

(*Spring*):

It's impossible to think that,	<i>Daa dimaagh zama chari na manee</i>
Anyone can still believe,	<i>Chi da gul khaliq ba saqar krree jurr</i>
That the God who fashioned hell-fire,	<i>Sanga khwagi ba pri zama kreeki lagee?</i>
Is the same who gave us these.	<i>Cha chi ma maa la nargas aw dilbar</i>
Why should He want us to suffer,	<i>krru jurr</i>
Or be happy when we grieve –	<i>Daa shinkey Chaman daa guloona srah</i>
He that gave us narcissi,	<i>Daa mast mast shaani mastaana</i>
Life and comfort, love and ease?	<i>makhaam</i>
This green floral garden and these red	<i>Daa sabot da saqi da mini dey</i>
flowers,	<i>Daa da sru sharabu barpoora jaam</i>
This rapturous ecstatic evening	<i>Da saqi chi stargi khumaari dee</i>
This is the proof of the cup-bearer's love,	<i>Daa khumar yi maa ta jurr karrey dey</i>
This red wine brimming chalice	
The cup-bearer's eyes that are drunken	
This drunkenness has been made for me]	

(pp. 188–192).

Love appears to take precedence over beauty. Beauty represents the physical objects, whereas love represents the idea and the spiritual aspect of reality. Humans are connected with the divine by carrying love within, where the divine resides. Thus, love is the reality, and beauty is the shadow of love. Khan sometimes depicts love in entirely divine and transcendental terms, through which the divine manifests itself, as Ibn Arabi suggests. This is evident in "*Love and Beauty*," where Khan interprets love as immortal and deathless. It links all creation into one knot, but physical beauty fades into insignificance after some time. Thus, love is divine, but physical beauty is the temporal manifestation of that divine self in earthly forms. Khan writes in his poem “*Meena aw Husan*” (*Love and Beauty*):

I heard the new moon whisper to a star:	<i>Sturee ta asmaan ki yawa wraaz wuwi hilaal</i>
“Allah has blessed us with unrivalled beauty;	<i>Khudai adam la mina warkrra moong la tash jamaal</i>
And man, ungrateful being,	<i>Zah ba war krram daa khpal Khaisht da</i>
He granted love.	<i>kamaal</i>
I would give way with laughter,	<i>Maa la ka yau saaskey raakrree suk pa swaal</i>
And without any regrets,	<i>Meena haqeeqat husan saaya da haqeeqat</i>
All this priceless beauty	<i>dah</i>
For a drop of love –	<i>Husan la zawaal shta meena na laree zawal</i>
For beauty must grow old and wane,	
But love is deathless, eternal!	

(pp. 220–221).

These lines conspicuously reflect that love is not influenced by any greed. It directs love towards some material or physical gain, but is entirely guided by the object of love and loyalty to the beloved’s command.

A true lover might have opted to be thrown into hell even if there had been any chance of seeing the beloved there. In his poem “*Chi Adam Khaawru ki Kini*” (**When Man Mingles with the Earth**), Khan feels no scruple in setting aside the material and worldly aggrandisements. He longs only for the unity with the divine through love. He thus reflects Ibn Arabi’s view that true love remains uninfluenced by material gains and is drawn towards the divine. Khan says:

Tempt me not with <i>houris, ghilman,</i>	<i>Maa ta houri ghilman ma sandawa bas dey</i>
They mean nothing to me, know,	<i>Pa wallah kah bi la taa na mi pa chaa kaar</i>
It’s Your friendship, love, I seek,	<i>shee</i>
And shall not be turned away!	

(pp. 225–227).

Khan’s poems present a reciprocal relationship between the human and the divine through the intercession of love and beauty. Khan holds a concept of beauty that serves as a conduit for

accessing the noumenal realms. It extends beyond empirical understanding. It is placed in the sublime and the subjective experience. Khan draws on his poems “*Yau Khub da Shaair da Saba da Ranrra*” (A Dream of a Poet) and “*Saaz aw Husan*” (Music and Beauty). Khan shows imagery related to light, colour and the transcendence of beauty. It is a kind of intangible and beyond rational comprehension that captivates the human soul through its alluring appeal.

Khan writes in “*Yau Khub da Shaair da Saba da Ranrra*” (A Dream of a Poet):

Beloved, my sweetheart	<i>Janaana dilbara janaana zama</i>
My heart-throb, my love!	
Was this just your glance,	<i>Daa sta wu yau khub ka qisa wa zama</i>
Or somebody’s story?	
Do tell me beloved,	<i>Khabar, ay khabar, ay khabar ka maa</i>
Do tell me my love!	

(pp. 214–215).

He also writes in another poem, “*Saaz aw Husan*” (Music and Beauty):

When music and beauty	<i>Saaz chi Khaisht sara jurra shee</i>
Their forms unite;	
Or when light and colour	<i>Ya chi noor pa rang ki yau shee</i>
Their souls combine;	
Then, even though I try to hide,	<i>Zah ka zar brakhu ki patt sham</i>
In a thousand parts divide,	
My life and soul they captivate,	<i>Zhwand mi patt krree zrra mi yawsee</i>
Transport the heart to unknown heights!	

(pp. 260–261).

Khan’s poem “*Sparley*” (Spring) rejects the notion that cruelty can be ascribed to the divine.

Khan rather questions the concept of divine justice. Khan describes this in his poem “*Qismat*”

(Fate):

[...I am a picture of someone else’s fingers,	<i>....zah yau tasweer yem da bal da gutu</i>
A tongueless clay in the potter’s hands,	<i>Bi zubaana khata laas da kulaal ki</i>
It will be either the fate or hellfire,	<i>Ya bah qismat wee ya bah dawzakh wee</i>
Moreover, if both exist, then You are the Merciful?	<i>Aw ka wee dwaarra nu ta Rahmaan yi?</i>
	<i>Na sham zghamaley na sham manaley</i>

I cannot bear, I can't accept

Chi ta jalaad yi aw hum janaan yi

That You are the executioner as well as
the Beloved.]

(pp. 216–217).

Khan thus becomes a philosopher through his inclination towards finding answers to the questions of being and becoming. Khan confesses that he lacks the insight and rational understanding to unveil the noumenal and the sublime.

The creation of humans is the manifestation of divine love. Khan describes in his poem “*Pa Awya Kaala Zhwandoon Ki*” (Of the Three Score Years and Ten) how humans have been transformed from the immaterial and spiritual. Khan writes:

For this little sod of earth,

Di zara taa jurr karee daryaboona da

You've created all the fire

uroonu

And the brimstone that can be!

Ay daryaba da Rehmat sta da meeni nakha

daa

.....

Ay da sturu spugmu khana pa nwarrey

dudai yi khars krri

.....

Dagha khalqu ki paida shum sta da husan

For a morsel of bread

kawm qisa

Is Your name sold for a pittance!

Ay zama jaana janaana ay da noor aw

husan khana

Your name is sold for bread to eat,

Charta pa khub ki di Ghani khu pa di mla

Within a people such as these...

wutapawa

(pp. 256–257).

Life without love is meaningless because it is love that connects humans with the divine. Having no dimension of love within oneself is like having only filth and waste. The Akbarian and the Kantian concept of leading a life of moral dignity and purpose is expressed in Khan's poem “*Zhwand*” (Life). Khan compares the temporal nature of life with the everlasting value of love and beauty. Khan writes:

When life's willingly been wagered,	<i>Chi pri sar pa khandaa daaw shee hala khug</i>
Only then dear to the heart,	
Becomes love and all its secrets,	<i>raazu niyaz shee</i>
All its amatory conceits.	
When the swords in all their sheen,	<i>Chi da spinu turu jang shee khkaara halta ki</i>
In the battle thirst for blood,	
Then it is <i>Ayyaz</i> is seen,	<i>ayaz shee</i>
In the thick of all the fray!	

(pp. 246–249).

5.7. Conclusion

This chapter explored the concept of the cosmic self in Khan's poetry through the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Khan's poetry presents a unique synthesis between the philosophical and mystical traditions. This synthesis added a layer of depth and complexity to his poetry, making it a rich field for exploration.

The succeeding chapter will examine convergence and divergence between Keats's and Khan's poetry regarding the concept of cosmic self as well as its cross-cultural and universal significance.

CHAPTER SIX

Keats and Khan: Unveiling Unity in Diversity

The stars, my friend, are far away,
Be content with flowers!
When the face is turned towards,
The beloved's lovely face,
Then undaunted, make your way,
Through ravines and steep passes.
His minarets, let others be,
You no more than trudge along,
Kiss the dust beside the feet!
Take your grief and take your laughter,
Step in step with life proceed;
Drunk with life and reason,
And with hopes, in hope proceed!

(Sahibzada, 2014, pp. 62–65).

6.1. Introduction

This chapter analyses convergence and divergence in Keats's and Khan's poetry concerning the cosmic self. It also analyses the cross-cultural and universal appeal of the cosmic self. The chapter is divided into the following three main headings:

- Cosmic Self – Convergence and Divergence in Keats's and Khan's poetry
- Cosmic Self – Cross-cultural and universal significance in Keats's and Khan's poetry

6.2. Cosmic Self – Convergence and Divergence in Keats's and Khan's Poetry

6.2.1. Freedom and Autonomy

6.2.1. A. Convergence

Both Keats and Khan appear to converge on the question of freedom as a dimension of the cosmic self through the employment of evocative imagery and philosophical contemplation.

Ibn Arabi and Kant view freedom through the lens of an ineffably noumenal source, directed towards moral dignity, which transcends the personal ego and desires, culminating in the realisation of one's true essence and moral responsibility (Ibn Arabi, 1980; Kant, 1788).

Keats's poetry frequently hints at and provides evidence of this concept of freedom through transcendence, liberating the self from the mortal and corporeal constraints of existence in pursuit of spiritual and aesthetic beauty. Keats juxtaposes the immortality of the nightingale as symbolic of poetry and music with the hungry generation of humanity, who are led by the material pursuits, to convey the theme of freedom which the nightingale enjoys in the forest in "Ode to a Nightingale," "Thou wast not born for death, immortal Bird! / No hungry generations tread thee down..." (lines 61–62). It is through the imaginal existence of the mythic nightingale and its song that Keats will find escape from corporeal existence. This fascination with the creative art is not without purpose. A similar sentiment is expressed in another poem, "Ode on a Grecian Urn," where the vase carrying traces from the ancient past becomes a symbol of true beauty. After all, it is a truth expressed in paradoxical terms, which is the most significant lesson that everybody must be familiar with on earth (lines 49–50). The urn then symbolises freedom, being uninfluenced by the passage of time. However, both the nightingale and the urn have one end tethered to the physical world, which Keats finds rather attractive towards the end of the odes.

Khan is also inspired by the theme of freedom and, like Keats, places it in the struggle for existence against the deterministic constraints presented by the cosmically divine force. Khan's poem "Badiwa" (The Kite) represents the human yearning for freedom due to the limitations of being tied to physical existence:

You are a transparency	<i>Baad da Aashiq pa shaani khaandi khushaligi</i>
Of man's fate – continuous flight,	<i>tah</i>
Drunkenness of many hues,	<i>Masta sulee maara ta taawus hasi gadigi tah</i>

Tethered to the stake of fate.

(pp. 70–71).

In the above-quoted lines, the kite becomes the Keatsian nightingale for Khan, an embodiment of the soul's longing for freedom. Just as Keats, Khan also acknowledges the constraints of physical existence as obstructions in the way of achieving freedom.

The cosmic realisation is not always attainable. No matter how hard one tries to achieve freedom from the bondage of different confinements, the human self will fall short of attaining full cosmic realisation, mainly due to its intrinsic limitations of being a mortal existence. Keats's "Ode to a Nightingale," says the same through, "What thou among the leaves hast never known, / The weariness, the fever, and the fret..." (lines 22–23). It can be paralleled with Khan's "*Da Khapiru Shahzadgai*" (*The Fairy Princess*), where the princess laments over her captivity:

.....I am a captive, *Wi rang ranrra newwaley yem, maa dartlu ta*
Of both colour and the light, *nah pregdee*
And much as I would like to go, *Aw maa khpali wazari alwatu tah nah prigdee*
They won't let go of me.

(pp. 50–51).

Both Keats and Khan adopt a paradoxical approach to time. It can either restrain or emancipate, serving as a motivation for the self to set itself free. Keats reconciles to the conditions imposed by time through accepting the cyclical process and flow of time, with each moment carrying its charm. In "Ode to Autumn," he elaborates this as "Where are the songs of Spring? / Ay, where are they? / Think not of them, thou hast thy music too..." (lines 23–24). Khan also acknowledges the overwhelming influence of time, as in his poem "*Jannat aw Dunya*" (*The World and Heaven*), by connecting it with the divine and also reconciling to what each moment offers to the human self in its wake:

Every moment, hue of life	<i>Har saa'at har rang da zhwand staa da</i>
Is a helpless slave of time;	<i>wakht bi kas ghulam</i>
And, in Heaven, says the priest,	<i>Aw jannat ki mullah waayi wakht bah wee</i>
Time, my slave is bound to be.	<i>zamaa ghulam</i>

(pp. 56–57).

Love serves as a medium that can provide a way out of bondage. Keats and Khan make love a conduit for freedom. Keats's quote in "[Ode to a Nightingale](#)," "I have been half in love with easeful Death," explores the same theme of accepting death as a means to achieve true freedom by attaining unity with the divine and transcending temporal restraints (line 52). Khan also emphasises the same idea through engagement with metaphysical questions in "[Wali](#)" ([Why?](#)). The beloved's eyes force him to accept freedom through surrender, "Why does one's heart surrender? / How is it one falls in love?" (pp. 6–7).

Freedom is an inseparable part of the cosmic self. It is evident from Keats's and Khan's poetry, as well as the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant, that freedom is not only a subject of aesthetic experience but also a quest for self-recognition in the existential struggles to attain cosmic heights.

6.2.1. B. Divergence

Divergence can be traced back to the constraints and requirements of the cultural and historical contexts, as well as to the philosophical and mystical proclivities. Freedom lies either in self-realisation (Ibn Arabi) or in rational autonomy (Kant). It is also either merging into one with the divine (Ibn Arabi) or enjoying autonomy (Kant) (Ibn Arabi, 2004; Kant, 1785/1997).

Keats's poetry often displays a passive acceptance of life's pains and thorns. He tries to gain freedom through imaginative escape from life's rough and challenging circumstances. He touches upon the same theme in his "[Ode to a Nightingale](#)," where poetry helps him win escape, "Away! away! for I will fly to thee, / Not charioted by Bacchus and his pards, / But on the

viewless wings of Poesy...” and so transcend the corporeal constraints (lines 31–33). The aesthetic arts and beauty help in achieving freedom. On the contrary, Khan’s poetry unmistakably bears the influence of *Pashtoon* culture, which emphasises achieving freedom forcefully. His poem “*Shaheed*” (*The Martyr*) exalts the struggle for freedom in the following words:

Oh martyr! and oh lover!	<i>Ay shaheedah ay aashiqah! Ay bachiya da</i>
Oh offspring of <i>Mansoor</i> !	<i>Mansoor</i>
In laughter, you departed,	<i>Pa khandaa janaan la laarri doob daryab ki</i>
This earthly life and state.	
To meet with your beloved,	<i>shwi da noor</i>
And to drown yourself within	
The sea of radiant light!	

(pp. 276–277).

Unlike Keats, who finds comfort and peace in the fanciful and supra-sensory realm, Khan confronts the physical world head-on with all its hardships. His poem “*Ay Zamaa Watana*” (*Oh Motherland!*) extols an anti-colonial attitude, “Every valley, gorge of yours, / Witness to my feat of arms!” (pp. 280–281).

Keats adopts a paradoxical approach towards eternity and transience as in “*Ode on a Grecian Urn*,” carrying forms that defeat the ravages of time but are also defeated by the frozenness of time. Keats thus holds an undecided and ambiguous approach towards complete freedom. Khan does not hesitate to challenge aggressively the dictators who might deprive him of autonomy and freedom. He writes in his poem, “*Wasiyat*” (*The Will*):

But if I were to have died an	<i>Kah Khaazi shni mi pa qabar wi walaarri</i>
enslaved person,	<i>Kah ghulam marr wum raazai tukey pri laarri</i>
Come, spit on and defile them!	<i>Ka pa khpalu winu na wum lambeedaley</i>
If my body were not bathed,	<i>Pa maa ma paleetawai da jumaat ghaarri</i>

In my blood and sanctified.

(pp. 288–289).

Keats and Khan thus stand in sharp contrast to each other, concerning their handling of freedom. It is assertive and self-defining (Khan) but somewhat docile, with an inclination to find shelter in eternity (Keats). Khan's realistic standpoint is explicitly stated in his poem "*Da Bachu Taraana*" (*The Children's Anthem*), where he writes, "I shall now my name disown / Or I shall the world transform! / I shall for my people fight..." (pp. 292–293). On the contrary, Keats writes in "*Ode to Autumn*" "Season of mists and mellow fruitfulness," where Keats appears to find solace and contentment in being bound by the seasonal cycle of nature.

It is thus evident that, like Ibn Arabi and Kant, Keats and Khan also hold sometimes divergent ideas about freedom. It is influenced to varying degrees by its respective cultural and historical contexts. For Keats, freedom is more an imaginative and poetic release from temporal existence to the permanent. On the contrary, Khan views freedom as self-recognition and a collective struggle for gaining autonomy.

6.2.2. Cosmic Self as Annihilation and Oneness

6.2.2. A. Convergence

This is also evident in the poetry of Keats and Khan, who hold annihilation and oneness as a means to access the cosmic self. Ibn Arabi and Kant also have sometimes overlapping approaches towards these dimensions, arguing for unity in diversity (Ibn Arabi) and the categories of understanding (Kant) (Chittick, 1989; Kant, 1781/1998).

Oneness through the annihilation of the individual self into the divine is derived from the mystical tradition. Khan expresses this oneness through becoming both the guide and the path in "*Da Faridoon Da Mur Khat*" (*Letter from Faridoon's Mother*):

When you became a spark of the fire as *Tah chi shwi da ur basarey zah hum srah*
it burned, *lamba da ur shum*

I became the raging flame. *Chi sta zrra pa talaash sar shu za shum laara*

When your heart went out a searching, *za imaam*

I became the path and guide...

(pp. 14–19).

This act of becoming the means and the end is very much in line with Keats's idealisation of love and beauty. It is reflected in his approach towards love and beauty and his longing for transcendence.

The obliteration of the self through love and beauty is reflected in several of Keats's poems, like "Ode to a Nightingale," "Endymion," and "Lamia," to mention a few. In "Ode to a Nightingale," he dissolves sorrow and becomes one with the divinely inspired song of the nightingale when he says, "Fade far away, dissolve, and quite forget / What thou among the leaves hast never known..." (lines 21–22). Khan's poem "Masti" (Ecstasy) also touches the same theme as he writes, "When the lover's ecstatic, / He becomes a drop / Of beauty and light..." (pp. 92–95). Thus, both poets transcend and achieve union through annihilation.

Keats and Khan have a characteristic approach towards nature. Keats's longing to be one with the object of beauty in nature to secure universality and immortality like beauty. It is evident in "Endymion," "A thing of beauty is a joy for ever: / Its loveliness increases; it will never / Pass unto nothingness..." (lines 1–3).

Khan approaches nature with the same attitude of finding the divine being one with nature. Khan describes this in his poem "Sparley" (Spring), "What is Spring but the Beloved is actually in ecstasy / Who is spreading His effulgence in every particle and every breath..." (pp. 188–192).

The annihilation and oneness take painful form. Khan portrays this painful side of longing for annihilation and oneness in his titular poem "Mansoor," when he says, "You are love and so am I, / Why should then between us be, / This obscuring veil?" (pp. 204–205).

Khan thus strikes a connection with *Al-Hallaj*, who suffered persecution on account of calling himself the Real Truth (*Al-Haqq*) and ultimately a painful death.

Keats's poem "*Lamia*," describes the effect of the divine. It transcends the individual self just like nature. Keats strikes a note of oneness through the intermediary of the divine as described symbolically in the following words:

But the God fostering her chilled hand,
She felt the warmth, her eyelids open'd bland,
And, like new flowers at morning song of bees,
Bloom'd, and gave up her honey to the lees. (lines 140–143).

Keats's and Khan's poetry thus shares a concept of oneness and annihilation of the individual self in the cosmic whole. It is often achieved through the intervention of natural phenomena, which connects the earthly to the heavenly.

6.2.2. B. Divergence

Keats accepts the concept of oneness and annihilation being associated with love. For example, Keats invokes death in "*Ode to a Nightingale*," "Now more than ever seems it rich to die, / To cease upon the midnight with no pain..." (lines 55–56).

On the contrary, despite his desire for annihilation in his beloved's feet, Khan longs to annihilate himself in love of his motherland only to re-emerge as a hero after sacrifice. Khan's poetry thus leads to a transcendental unity with the divine, which he elaborates through a dialogue in his poem "*Sawaal jawaab da Liwane aw da Mullah*" (*Pious Priest and Madman*):

And, what is prostration, madman?	<i>Liwaniya! sajda sa dah?</i>
Pious priest, it's the reduction	<i>Mullah! zaan khaawri kawal dee</i>
Of one's self to dust, and placing	<i>Da mastee da gulu haar</i>
At beloved's feet the necklace	<i>Da yaar pkhu ki achawul dee</i>
Of the flowers of ecstasy!	

(pp. 116–119).

Like a *Sufi*, Khan defines self-annihilation as a complete effacement to achieve oneness with the divine symbolised by the beloved.

Keats often offers annihilation either entirely or not, but Khan annihilates only to regenerate. Keats tries to come to terms with the impermanence of life and beauty that has to face decay as “*Ode to Autumn*,” describes, “Where are the songs of Spring? Ay, where are they? / Think not of them, thou hast thy music too...” (lines 23–24). Keats’s “*The Eve of St. Agnes*,” also shows Madeline imploring Porphyro, “Oh leave me not in this eternal woe, / For if thou diest, my Love, I know not where to go...” (lines 314–315).

On the contrary, Khan sees permanence in the impermanence and a spiritual regeneration in the annihilation. He writes in his poem “*Meena*” (Love):

She said, “Love is a flower,	<i>Haghi wi meena yau gul dey us taaza wee us</i>
Fresh and lovely for a while,	<i>fanaa shee</i>
And in a while no more.”	<i>Maa wi yau gul chi shee mrrawey sal</i>
I said, “when a flower wilts,	<i>guloona tri paida shee</i>
It gives birth to many more.”	

(pp. 152–153).

Thus, both Keats and Khan treat annihilation and the oneness in their poetry. Keats is more personal and driven towards melancholy, contemplating the transitory nature of beauty and love. Khan is more driven towards mysticism, considering self-annihilation and oneness as a means of opening the door to unity with the divine.

6.2.3. Immaterial and Material – Paradoxical Components of Cosmic Self

6.2.3. A. Convergence

Despite being separated by time and space, Keats and Khan hold similar views on material (physical, phenomenal, tangible) versus immaterial (spiritual, noumenal, intangible). Ibn Arabi

and Kant accept the material and the immaterial, as both being aligned with the divine will (Ibn Arabi) and directed towards a universal moral principle (Kant) (Ibn Arabi, 1980; Kant, 1781/1998).

Keats often longs for the immaterial world. His negative capability releases him from the material self to become a part of the ineffable with no desire for empirical or scientific truths. Almost every poem by Keats uses material as a threshold to the immaterial, though it usually becomes an obstacle as well. This paradoxical approach towards material and immaterial is evident in “*Endymion*,” through Cyntha (the moon goddess, immaterial) and the Indian Maid (material). In the “*Ode on a Grecian Urn*,” the material vase from antiquity presents an example of the immaterial as well, on account of its being untouched like a virgin and timeless, “Thou still unravish'd bride of quietness” (line 1). Its beauty outshines any material entity through transcendence, serving as a cosmic whole, holding all humanity upon its surface.

Khan’s poetry also covers themes of the material and the immaterial. Mostly, he connects both into one, with the root being hidden in the immaterial. For instance, in “*Khayal*” (*Fancy*), Khan makes this connection explicit when he writes:

All that’s beautiful and perfect,	<i>Yau yi khaisht yau yi Jamaal dey da Isa</i>
Have the same perfection, beauty –	<i>ghamgeeni stargi</i>
The sad eyes of Jesus Christ,	<i>Da Suqrat pa jaam ki zahar da Mansoor</i>
Poisoned cup of Socrates,	<i>mastee bi khuda</i>
<i>Mansoor’s</i> ecstasy supreme,	<i>Aw ranrra spina la khudah pah har laas pah</i>
And the radiance of the self.	<i>har mashaal ki</i>

(pp. 62–65).

Through a juxtaposition in the above excerpt between material (eyes, poison, candle) and immaterial (beauty, ecstasy, radiance), Khan emphasises the connection between the material and the immaterial. One reaches the immaterial through sensory perceptions (material).

Keats and Khan consider finitude (material) as a passage to the divine (immaterial). Keats compares the immortal song by the nightingale with the finite material world in “**Ode to a Nightingale**,” and concludes, “Thou wast not born for death, immortal Bird! / No hungry generations tread thee down...” (lines 61–62). Khan’s poem “*Khaawri*” (Dust) also deals with the same theme when, despite being dissolved in dust, humans remain alive in immaterial form:

In the grave lies buried deep,	<i>Pa qabroonu ki prati dee laas aw pkhi</i>
Hands and feet, fingers and lips;	<i>shoondi aw guti</i>
Who can dig a grave and bury,	<i>Suk shee qabar jurrawuley da di sru stargu</i>
Drunken glory of the eyes.	<i>khumaar la</i>

(pp. 72–75).

Only material pursuits in the negative sense lower the status of humans. Keats and Khan adopt a hateful attitude towards such degeneration. This kind of despicable approach in humans does not let them go beyond the superficial and achieve true self-realisation. Keats highlights this in one of his most scathing portrayals of superficial and cruel humans. He writes in “**Isabella; or, The Pot of Basil**” about Isabella’s brothers:

For them, the Ceylon diver held his breath,
 And went all naked to the hungry shark;
 For them his ears gushed blood; for them in death
 The seal on the cold ice with piteous bark
 Lay full of darts... (lines 115–118).

Not only Keats, but also Khan becomes hateful towards such a superficial approach towards material obsessions. He feels for such people in his poem, “*Deodasi*,” when he says, “If it cannot see your beauty, / Then the world has become blind...” (pp. 104–111). At another place, he becomes even more bitter and scathing when he says in “*Sawaal Jawaab da Liwaneer aw da Mullah*” (Pious Priest and Madman):

What is Heaven, madman tell me?	<i>Lewaniya! Jannat sa dey?</i>
Pious priest, our concepts differ –	<i>Mulla! staa jannat piti dey</i>
For you Heaven is no more	<i>Ao zamaa jannat wisaal dey</i>
Than a gourmet’s spread, for me	<i>Yau khumaar yau mastee dey</i>
It’s communion and being drunk	
With the wine of ecstasy.	

(pp. 116–119).

Keats and Khan often develop a connection between the material and immaterial through the intermediary of nature and love. In "Ode to Autumn," Keats builds a material world out of the immaterial season of Autumn, being personified. However, this material world suffers from the cyclical process of life as described, “Where are the songs of Spring? / Ay, where are they? / Think not of them, thou hast thy music too...” (lines 123–125). Material existence is transient and temporary.

Khan idealises a self that is uninfluenced by the material. It remains ecstatic and jubilant even in a state of solitude because that symbolises uniqueness and philosophic contemplation after the immaterial. Khan describes this in his poem “*Reedi Gul*” (The Flower):

I shall not exchange this wasteland,	<i>Zah ba daa sahraa war na krram da Iran pa</i>
For the <i>Persian</i> garden green.	<i>gulistaan</i>
Here I am one of a kind,	<i>Delta za yau aw yaktaa yem halta zar zamaa</i>
There are thousands there like me.	<i>pa shaan</i>

(pp. 76–77).

The same longing for loneliness and contemplation is found in Keats’s poetry. For instance, in “Ode to Autumn,” he visualises autumn “sitting careless on a granary floor,” or in “The Eve of St. Agnes,” Madeline is portrayed worshipping in solitude, “She knelt, so pure a thing, so free from mortal taint” (Stanza XXXIV). This state of philosophic contemplation to regain the lost status of a god (immaterial, intangible, noumenal) is explicitly stated in “Hyperion”:

Deep in the shady sadness of a vale

Far sunken from the healthy breath of morn,
Far from the fiery noon, and eve's one star,
Sat grey-hair'd Saturn, quiet as a stone,
Still as the silence round about his lair;

Forest on forest hung about his head... (Book I, lines 1–6).

Keats and Khan thus write on almost the same themes regarding the material and immaterial as dimensions of the cosmic self. Despite belonging to entirely different cultures, languages, and ages, both these poets try to reconcile the realms of the material and the immaterial in their poetry.

6.2.3. B. Divergence

Keats and Khan are influenced by their own unique philosophical and mystical leanings when they approach the material and immaterial. Sometimes Keats sees transience and change in the material, but Khan examines the material and immaterial from the perspective of exploring the connection between the sensory and supra-sensory realms. The material and immaterial are either two faces of the same coin (Ibn Arabi) or exist independently of each other (Kant) (Chittick, 1998; Kant, 1781/1998).

Keats's poetry highlights the dual aspects of pleasure and grief related to existential issues. Sometimes Keats idealises the beauty of material existence as immortal, such as in "Ode on a Grecian Urn" he says, "Beauty is truth, truth beauty" (line 49). However, he also acknowledges the material beauty in "Ode on Melancholy," where death emerges as in pursuit of this beauty, "Beauty that must die; / And Joy, whose hand is ever at his lips..." (lines 21–22). Keats's "Ode to a Nightingale," accentuates this further, where the material and the immaterial are juxtaposed through the symbolic representation of the material "weariness, the fever, and the fret" (line 23) and the immaterial nightingale "not born for death, immortal Bird!" (line 61).

Khan's poetry has several examples of preferring the immaterial over the material. The corporeal may obstruct one's journey towards attaining unity with the immaterial. Khan highlights the same in his poem "*Dua*" (Prayer):

In my beloved's lovely eyes, *Stargu da janaan ki zamaa khkulee*
A universe of beauty lies; *jahanoona dee*
Take Your world, it's Yours to keep, *Waa di khla duniya zah wurrey staa da*
I am not in need of it! *duniya na yema*

(pp. 200–201).

Khan thus rejects the material world and selects the divine beloved. Another example from Khan's poetry amplifies this anti-worldly attitude. In "*Chi Adam Khaawru Ki Kini*" (When Man Mingles with the Earth), he says how worldly pursuits may risk human dignity:

When man mingles with the earth, *Chi adam khaawru ki kinee sa zarghun krree*
Crops so green of worth emerge; *Manjeela chi pa daulat shee nu khamaar*
When coiled upon his wealth he sits, *shee*
Then like a viper venom spits!

(pp. 225–227).

Keats and Khan both idealise suffering but with some difference in their approaches. Keats unveils the romantic side of suffering as an inseparable part of the material, adding to the in-depth understanding as in "*Ode on Melancholy*," he writes, "Ay, in the very temple of Delight / Veil'd Melancholy has her sovran shrine..." (lines 25–26). However, Khan finds mystical undercurrents in suffering. He strikes a divine connection through these, as in "*Ajaba Falsafa*" (Strange Philosophy):

Oh one bereft of reason! *Liwaniya! Liwaniya! daa tul aqal zamaa*
Come! take my reason away! *waakhla*
But in exchange provide,

Of your longing just a drop!

Khu badal ki raata raakrra yau qatra da

(pp. 132–143). *khpal armaan*

Suffering then becomes, for Khan, a source of soul-purification for the soul, drawing it closer in harmony to the divine.

Khan derives the message of impermanence and illusion from the exact nature of things, but Keats sees a connection with the eternity. For example, Keats idealises the nightingale’s song and yearns to be one with that immaterial existence. In “Ode on the Grecian Urn,” Keats highlights the merging of material and immaterial by the very nature of the urn being a relic from the past. Khan finds illusion, impermanence and decay in nature, which he describes in “*Laka Wakhli Chi Maashoom*” (Like a Child Who Plays):

And my garden and my flowers,

Baagh da gulu mi taalaa shu

Have been trampled on, despoiled;

Da laaloonu shkur mi tash shu

And my basket of bright rubies,

Daa laa waawra! mulla jaan

To the bottom has been scrapped.

Kai tang tang da hisaboonu

Yet on top of this I hear,

The insistent priest declared,

The impending day of doom,

And the calling to account!

(pp. 96–99).

In short, Keats brings synthesis between the dual aspects material and immaterial, accepting the hardships of the material world, but Khan makes the material and immaterial as the same aspects of a single reality.

6.2.4. Cosmic Self – Essence and Existence

6.2.4. A. Convergence

Despite belonging to different traditions and cultures, Keats and Khan display similar interests in exploring the ontological and metaphysical questions about the essence and existence. Reality exists at the existential (roughly Kant's phenomenal) and essential (roughly Kant's noumenal) levels, with the essence and existence being bridged through the individual (Chittick, 1989; Izutsu, 1983; Kant, 1781/1998).

Keats and Khan often adopt a mystical approach towards death, viewing it not as a terminal point, but as the end of corporeal existence and the beginning of the incorporeal by merging back into the essence. Keats's "Ode to a Nightingale," displays the same theme when he writes, "Thou wast not born for death, immortal Bird! / No hungry generations tread thee down..." (lines 61–62). The nightingale thus becomes a symbol of eternity. However, in another poem, "Lamia," Keats makes Lamia immortal through a combination of both the essence and existence as one:

Sure some sweet name thou hast, though, by my truth,
I have not ask'd it, ever thinking thee
Not mortal, but of heavenly progeny,
As still I do. Hast any mortal name,
Fan appellation for this dazzling frame? (lines 86–90).

The nightingale and Lamia are symbols of the essence which, despite being confined to their physical form, carries immortal attributes within themselves. The same theme of the essence being universal is repeated in Khan's poem "Zama Da Bachu Mur Ta" (The Mother of My Children), where he explicitly traces the human self back to its essence. In contrast, the apparent form of humans is only in the state of existence:

In human form a poet's dream;	<i>Yau khub da shaair pa jaama insanee</i>
A heavenly melody, ambient, serene;	<i>Yau saaz door daraz khkuley khug</i>
A flower from heaven by nature divine;	<i>asmanee</i>

A form pure, ethereal, the heart saintly *Yaw gul da jannat pa khaslat Rehmanee*
light... *Yaw jism naarey yau zarrgey nuraanee*

(pp. 4–5).

In another poem, “*Khaawri*” (Dust) Khan juxtaposes the permanent and impermanent in words such as “Death is not the end of life, / As if draining dry a wine cup, / Is the end of drunken strife...” (lines 72–75). This theme gets echoed not only in Keats’s poem, “Ode to a Nightingale,” but also in “Endymion,” where he says:

When from this wreathed tomb shall I awake!
When move in a sweet body fit for life,
And love, and pleasure, and the ruddy strife
Of hearts and lips! Ah, miserable me! (lines 38–41).

Keats and Khan acknowledge the ambiguities and internal conflicts within one’s own self. These are essential parts of existence. Keats’s negative capability aligns with Khan’s lines in his poem “*Talaash*” (Search), “What if life is a lost moment of our consciousness, / It has, at least, a Loved One in Eternity...” (pp. 82–89). Thus, both accept the transitory nature of existence in the physical world with an intrinsic belief in the divine essence.

Keats and Khan also compare essence and existence with the arts, especially poetry, which exists as eternal due to its essence in beauty. Keats describes this same concept through famous lines in “Ode on a Grecian Urn,” where he writes, “Beauty is truth, truth beauty—that is all / Ye know on earth, and all ye need to know...” (lines 49–50). Khan also treats existence on the same lines in his poem “*Saakht*” (Creation), where the human self is considered holding a close connection with the cosmic order:

Clear and sweet the water of hope, *Speeni khwagi da umeed ubah*
For life, a path is created in the flowers. *Zhwand la guloonu ki laar jurrai*
In everything form, weight, and count, *Har shai ki saakht aw tul aw shumaar*

Shape and colour, function and strength.

Shikl aw rang aw zur aw kaar

(pp. 34–35).

Keats and Khan strike a connection with nature through uniting the human with the nature. For instance, Keats’s “*Ode to Autumn*,” personifies the autumn that is engaged in a conspiratorial relationship with the sun, such as “Season of mists and mellow fruitfulness, / Close bosom-friend of the maturing sun...” (lines 1–2). Khan develops a similar relationship with a flying kite in his poem “*The Kite*,” where he writes, “You are a transparency / Of man’s fate—continuous light, / Drunkenness of many hues...” projecting self into a flying kite (pp. 70–71).

Not only do Keats and Khan believe in the duality of existence, but they also uphold the simultaneous existence of pleasure and pain. It adds to the complexity of the human self. Beauty coexists with melancholy due to its impermanence, as in “*Ode on Melancholy*,” Keats writes, “Ay, in the very temple of Delight / Veiled Melancholy has her sovran shrine...” (lines 26–27). Khan repeats similar themes in his poem, “*Laka Waakhli Chi Mashoom*” (*Like a Child Who Plays*), where the duality of experience holds both pain and pleasure in conformity “Was this life, or but a snare / Of raging flame and grief?” (pp. 96–99).

All these examples demonstrate that there is close affinity in Keats’s and Khan’s poetry regarding the essence and existence as facets of the cosmic self.

6.2.4. B. Divergence

Keats and Khan explore the essence and existence from their unique perspectives, diverging significantly. Keats is more influenced by the impermanent aspect of existence, but Khan is more interested in examining the permanent aspect of existence through impermanence and essence.

Keats makes beauty and art immortal in “*Ode on a Grecian Urn*,” that “Beauty is truth, truth beauty,” reflecting an enduring aspect of existence when combined with essence (line 49). A poem or a piece of art is the existential state of creative genius or essence.

Khan considers the divine essence as the ultimate beauty being manifested through existence, as in “*Shpa Wa Da Sparlee*” (*It Was a Night in Early Spring*), he writes, “Beauty, only beauty, is, / Both God and the beloved...” (pp. 194–197). Khan is more attracted towards mystic philosophy, which argues for the sameness of the essential and existential.

On the contrary, despite connecting essence and existence in the “*Ode to Autumn*,” Keats reconciles with accepting impermanence being an inseparable dimension of existence. Keats describes this impending doom symbolically through, “Where are the songs of Spring? Ay, where are they? / Think not of them, thou hast thy music too...” and thus conveys the imponderable reality of impermanence and transitoriness of the physical existence (lines 20–21).

Khan accepts the little agentive role that humans play in determining their existence. They mostly surrender to the dominant role being played by the divine essence, as in his poem “*Qismat*” (*Fate*), Khan says, “Little matter, but being pliant clay, / In unknown hands, that mould me as they will...,” and thus that shapes the existence (pp. 216–217). So, Khan views essence and existence as two sides of the same coin, but Keats sees them as distinct from each other.

Khan’s poetry interweaves the existence and the divine essence into a cosmic whole, as in his poem “*Seendah Za Seendah Bahiga*” (*Flow Oh River, Flow Along!*), where the river of life symbolises existence that gets dissolved in the essence. It is the same mystical concept of union between the essence and existence, “Every man is like a river, / And forever on the go...” (pp. 169–173).

On the other hand, Keats demonstrates an ambiguous approach towards essence and existence. Sometimes, existence becomes everlasting when it gets combined with the essence, as in “*Ode to a Nightingale*,” where he invokes, “Thou wast not born for death, immortal Bird!”

(line 61). But Keats also accepts the impermanence of existence as in “*Endymion*” when he writes:

Therefore, on every morrow, are we wreathing
A flowery band to bind us to the earth,
Spite of despondency, of the inhuman dearth
Of noble natures, of the gloomy days... (lines 6–9).

A middle could have been to accept the earthly existence, along with all its temporal and spatial limitations.

The above analysis reflects that Keats is ambiguous in his approach towards essence and existence, but Khan displays a somewhat definable stance towards essence and existence.

6.2.5. Cosmic Self through the Intercession of Love and Beauty

6.2.5. A. Convergence

Keats and Khan come from two distinct cultures, but there is a metaphysical connection between them. In their poetic treatment of love and beauty, Keats and Khan display striking similarities.

Keats writes in a letter, “I have lov'd the principle of beauty in all things” (*Letters, II, 263*). His oft-quoted maxim from “*Ode on a Grecian Urn*,” that “Beauty is truth, truth beauty,” is reiterated in another narrative poem, “*Endymion*,” when he says:

A thing of beauty is a joy for ever:
Its loveliness increases; it will never
Pass into nothingness; but still will keep
A bower quiet for us, and a sleep
Full of sweet dreams, and health, and quiet breathing. (lines 1–4).

Khan also displays a worshipful attitude towards love and beauty, which, like Keats, transcends an aesthetic experience. For instance, Khan’s reverence for beauty finds expression in one of

his poems titled “*Saakht*” (*Creation*), where he writes, “In beauty there lies, Your ultimate proof, / Enlightening the eyes of the heart and the soul...” (pp. 34–35). It thus strikes a connection between the individual and the divine through beauty.

An essential part of achieving unity with the divine self is love. It is both a transforming and transcending experience. Through pain and pleasure, it takes the individual self to the cosmic self. For instance, Keats combines the form of beauty with pain and pleasure in “*Hyperion*,” when he says, “But oh! how unlike marble was that face: / How beautiful, if sorrow had not made / Sorrow more beautiful than Beauty’s self...” (lines 34–36). Keats also considers love a manifestation of the divine and the cause of all creation. In “*Hyperion*,” the character of Saturn is described in the words, “Manifestations of that beauteous life / Diffus’d unseen throughout eternal space: / Of these new-form’d art thou, oh brightest child!” (lines 317–320). Khan takes this love beyond the physical into the spiritual on account of its capacity to connect the individual self with the cosmic whole. He highlights the dual nature of love in his poem “*Bachey Chi Lui Shi*” (*My Child When You Grow Older*):

When in love you are entwined,	<i>Hala ba mast shi chi bandiwan shi</i>
You will ecstasy imbibe;	<i>Hala ba khur shi chi aswiley shi</i>
You shall wait upon the wind,	<i>Bachiya! lui shi bachiya! Lui shi</i>
When you suffer and sigh.	

(pp. 32–33).

The association of beauty and love being linked with the ephemeral is expressed in Keats’s “*Ode to Autumn*,” where the season becomes a symbol of transitoriness and temporality. It echoes in Khan’s “*Jannat aw Duniya*” (*The World and Heaven*), where he says:

If forever I were young,	<i>Chi za tul umar zalmey yem zalmitub ba yau</i>
Youth would surely be a curse;	<i>azaab shee</i>
It is now so loved, endearing	

As its beauty is like the morn, *Zaka us ra baandi graan dey chi yi khaisht*
 Like a dream that quickly fades. *shee zar tamaam*

(pp. 56–61).

Reason cannot access the divine beauty, nor can it understand love. This acceptance of the limitations of reason is evident in "Ode to a Nightingale," where Keats surrenders to the mesmerising beauty of the nightingale's song. Khan's poem "Saakht" (Creation) highlights the same attitude towards reason "Reason no more than two paces can take, / Thereafter loses itself in the maze..." (pp. 34–35). In another poem, "Fancy," Khan writes "when reason exhausts itself, / Step in step with love proceed!" (pp. 62–65).

Keats begins "Endymion," with "A thing of beauty is a joy forever," trying to prove that beauty is part of eternity, connecting all beings (line 1). Khan also shows this in his poem "Arinee" (Show Me), where he writes:

For the night, a hope of dawn, *Shpi la da saba ziarey aw meeni la janaan*
 And for lover, a lover seeks; *latom*
 That is why, at times I go, *Zaka kala gul kala sparlee kala hilal la zam*
 To meet the spring, accost the flower, *Puri tri ranrra latom pa waazu stargu jaal*
 Ascend the crescent, greet the star. *la zam*

(pp. 52–55).

Keats and Khan thus consider love and beauty as an overarching dimension connecting all the remaining dimensions into one cosmic whole,

6.2.5. B. Divergence

Keats's attitude towards love and beauty is worshipful but mostly abstract. Keats's quotes demonstrate his concept of beauty, such as "Beauty is truth, truth beauty" (line 49) in "Ode on

a Grecian Urn,” then “A thing of beauty is a joy for ever” (line 1) in “Endymion” and “Some shape of beauty moves away the pall / From our dark spirits...” (lines 12–13). These lines display how Keats considers beauty both temporal and transcending experience, such as in his “Ode to a Nightingale,” he juxtaposes on the one hand the ethereally and immortally beautiful song of the nightingale and on the other hand the ephemerality and mortality of an individual self.

Khan, however, defines beauty, highlighting its different dimensions. Khan explicitly describes love and beauty being manifested through material objects. Love and beauty thus go into the composition of everything. Khan defines beauty through a dialogue in “*Sawaal Jawaab Da Liwane Aw Da Mullah*” (Pious Priest and Madman):

What is beauty and its essence?	<i>Liوانيya! husan sa dey?</i>
Pious priest, it is a wave.	<i>Mulla leher da khumar dey</i>
Of our drunkenness intense	<i>Yau muskey muskey shaan khiyal dey</i>
And a faintly smiling thought,	<i>Yau narey da ranrra taar dey</i>
And a slender thread of light!	

(pp. 116–119).

Keats looks at either the temporal or permanent aspect of beauty like philosophers. Keats mostly keeps his expressions of love and beauty implicit instead of explicit, like Khan. For instance, “Where youth grows pale, and spectre-thin, and dies” implicitly describes the death of his brother Tom in “Ode to a Nightingale” (line 26). He also shares his secret love for Fanny in “The Eve of St. Agnes,” when he says, “And they are gone: ay, ages long ago / These lovers fled away into the storm” (lines 370–371).

On the contrary, Khan is quite explicit about love and beauty in his poetry. He divides love or even beauty into different types, such as that related to close family members, the individual self and the *Pashtun* nation. In “*Ajaba Falsafa*” (Strange Philosophy) Khan writes:

Beauty does not have a form,	<i>Khaisht Wajood laree na surey</i>
Nor a shadow one can see,	<i>Da dah noor ba hala guri chi pah patu</i>
Its existence is apparent	<i>stargu guri</i>
To closed eyes, which do not see!	

(pp. 132–143).

His love for the nation becomes quite aggressive. He even forbade people from offering prayers on his grave if he suffered a useless death. He writes in his poem, “*Wasiyat*” (*The Will*):

But if I were to have died an	<i>Kah Khaazi shni mi pa qabar wi walaarri</i>
enslaved person,	<i>Kah ghulam marr wum raazai tukey pri laarri</i>
Come, spit on and defile them!	<i>Ka pa khpalu winu na wum lambeedaley</i>
If my body were not bathed,	<i>Pa maa ma paleetawai da jumaat ghaarri</i>
In my blood and sanctified.	

(pp. 288–289).

Both Keats and Khan write on the theme of love and beauty as dimensions of the cosmic self. However, they also diverge significantly, as Keats views beauty as a means of escaping mortal existence. In contrast, Khan connects the individual and the cosmic self into a unified whole, representing the true essence of reality (Ibn Arabi).

6.3. Cosmic Self – Cross-Cultural and Universal Significance in Keats’s and Khan’s Poetry

6.3.1. Significance of Freedom and Autonomy

Keats's and Khan's poetry displays strong traces of exploration into the significance of freedom as a dimension of the cosmic self. Ibn Arabi and Kant consider freedom and autonomy as both cosmic unity and rational self-governance, respectively (Ibn Arabi, 2002; Kant, 1997).

Keats's poetry connects with the sublime that enables the human to either escape or bravely face the "weariness, the fever, and the fret" that Keats longs to achieve in "Ode to a Nightingale" (line 23). The nightingale's song is not just a simple warbling but a representation of freedom of art and music that is unfettered by any restraint, which has the power to turn one into an immortal.

A constant struggle for freedom persists within the individual. This also reflects a paradoxical duality of the human, which binds itself to either the spiritual or the physical side to set itself free. This equation can be resolved by no better example than the phenomena of "*Badiwa*," "*The Kite*." The kite may fly in the open sky, but it will remain fastened by a delicate thread. It risks losing itself in the unknown land if driven by the unfettered freedom "You are a transparency / Of man's fate – continuous flight, / Drunkenness of many hues... (pp. 70–71).

The desire to attain freedom never dies. It is in the pursuit of the existential goals. Keats and Khan offer rich examples of the idealisation of beauty, whether in its eternity or its temporality. Khan reflects this approach towards achieving existential autonomy in "*Da Khapiru Shahzagai*" (*The Fairy Princess*) "I am weary of the world outside, / Afraid of pain in store..." (pp. 48–49). Keats parallels this yearning for out-of-the-world freedom through art, music and poetry, which he symbolically presents in almost every poem, such as in "*Lamia*":

Free as the air, invisibly, she strays

About these thornless wilds, her pleasant days

She tastes unseen; unseen her nimble feet

Leave traces in the grass and flowers sweet... (Part II, lines 94–97).

Khan accepts this duality of the self. Despite “Sometimes laughter, often pain,” the longing for freedom is indomitable even under these adverse circumstances. He says in, “*Da Faridoon Da Moor Khat*” (*Letter from Faridoon's Mother*) that the human self either soars high in heaven like an eagle and loses itself in the melodious song of a nightingale or becomes the mercy of an emperor who is approached by an enslaved person for emancipation. It is the longing to be lost entirely in the heavenly effulgence, as “When my soul absorbed the light, / Both his eyes commenced to glow...” (pp. 14–15).

The magnetic pull by the duality of the self and its cosmic association with freedom in Khan, as well as in Keats, reflects its universal appeal as in Keats’s “*Ode on a Grecian Urn.*” The urn establishes a connection along a continuum between the past, the present and along a vertical line between the earthly and the divine. Achieving absolute freedom will instead be facilitated by a belief as powerful as in Keats's “*Ode to a Nightingale,*” where “beauty is truth, truth beauty” through the transcendence of earthly and temporal limitations (line 49).

It is also universally acknowledged that individual, familial and societal structures limit the human’s ability to achieve freedom under numerous constraints. Khan is vociferous in rejecting these obstacles in his poem “*Waaya Waaya Mullah Jaana*” (*Come and Tell Me Pious Priest*) because the human self soars high in heaven like a falcon only to become a slave of desire to keep flying high:

Pious priest! Oh come and tell me,	<i>Waaya waaya mullah jaana!</i>
Is to search for a means of worship,	<i>Moondal wasl dey kah bigaar dey</i>
Or just forced-labour, exacting?
.....	
Or a snare the falcon’s knotted	<i>Daa yau jaam shahbaaz jurr karrey</i>
To entrap its powerful wing?	<i>Chi pri khpal wazar raagir krree</i>

(pp. 120–121).

Freedom, being an intrinsically universal aspiration of the human self, can be attained through various means, such as nature, beauty and art, as well as through human resilience to withstand

individual, familial, societal and even heavenly constraints. Ultimately, it is the transcendence of the earthly boundaries and limitations.

6.3.2. Significance of Annihilation and Oneness

When the self is surrendered to the divinely real, it becomes genuine in both sensory and supra-sensory perceptions (Ibn Arabi, 2002). Similarly, Kant asserts that humans exist in the sensible world as a phenomenon and in the intelligible world as pure reason (Kant, 1997).

Despite their differing cultural and historical backgrounds, the similarities in annihilation and oneness demonstrate the cross-cultural and universal significance of these dimensions. Questions about life, death, mortality and immortality have always captured the attention of thinkers. Keats also displays meditative characteristics by contemplating mortality and sublimity to be attained through transitoriness and eternity. Keats's "Ode to a Nightingale," offers an example of how significant it is to set one's free from suffering in earthly existence and merge with the immortal song of the nightingale. It becomes immortal itself, "Now more than ever seems it rich to die, / To cease upon the midnight with no pain..." (lines 55–56).

Art and poetry also represent characteristics founded on the principles of annihilation and oneness. This characteristic is also evident in "Ode on a Grecian Urn," where the permanence and impermanence of beauty are considered the undeniable truths related to the concept of beauty. Death and regeneration go hand in hand, "Beauty is truth, truth beauty, — that is all / Ye know on earth, and all ye need to know..." (lines 49–50). Similarly, the dissolution of the self through annihilation or oneness is significant because there is a dire need to develop a humane and benevolent attitude towards fellow humans and the rest of creation.

Egoistic tendencies only damage both the internal and external peace, which the *Sufi* practices explore. Khan's approach to achieve annihilation and oneness within the *Sufi* tradition is described in "*Da Faridoon Da Moor Khat*" (Letter from Faridoon's Mother):

When your heart went out a searching, *Chi staa zrrah pah taalaash sar shu zah*
 I became the path and guide; *shum laara zah imaam*
 When your lips thirsted for wine, *Daa chi staa shundi shwi tagi da masti da sru*
 The red wine of ecstasy, *sharabu*
 Then my own dear beloved, *Daa khu zaka za janaana! Hum sharaab*
 I became the cup and the wine. *shuma hum jaam*

(pp. 14–19).

As the above lines from Khan illustrate, when the human self is entirely obliterated through annihilation and oneness, it becomes both the means and the end.

There is no reason why there should be insurmountable boundaries between humans if all have derived their existence from one cosmic whole. This shared belief in the interconnectedness and dissolution of egoistic preferences only ushers in a world of peaceful co-existence. Both Keats and Khan use almost similar imagery to highlight this theme of annihilation and oneness, such as metaphors from nature and celestial entities, as Khan says in “*Mastee*” (Ecstasy):

When light is ecstatic, *Ranrra chi masta shee ranga rangoona shee*
 It turns into colours. *Khaawra shi masta shee srah srah guloona shee*
 When the Earth is ecstatic,
 It produces red flowers.

(pp. 92–95).

This element of shared essence takes multifarious forms as a result of transformation. The transformation of the human self from an almost annihilating state, marked by a tiny drop of light and beauty, offers an example of self-annihilation as well as re-emergence in the form of light and beauty.

Humans of all cultures and ages yearn for the desire of immortality through transcendence, despite accepting the reality of suffering in earthly existence. Keats reflects this approach in his “Ode to Autumn,” where he agrees with the cyclical nature of temporal existence and the re-emergence through transcendence after annihilation and oneness with own characteristics, “Where are the songs of Spring? Ay, where are they? / Think not of them, thou hast thy music too...” (lines 21–22). The cross-cultural characteristic of annihilation and oneness, as dimensions of the cosmic self, is also displayed by Khan in his poetry, where he paradoxically uses longing and loss as a medium to access the sublime and spiritual heights. In his poem “*Wruk Khayal*” (Longing) Khan writes:

In the darkness of the surrounding light	<i>Tura tiarah ki warra spina shama</i>
A little candle, but so full of light;	<i>Da ranrra dakka khu ghamgeena</i>
Inwardly grieving, searching feverishly	<i>shama</i>
To augment the grief of the beloved.	<i>Chapira stargi da sanam guri</i>
	<i>Pa khpalu stargu zaan la gham guri</i>

(pp. 90–91).

In the above lines, the candle’s light also symbolically represents, like the Autumn of Keats, its attributes of flickering but divine and enduring love. These excerpts provide rich evidence of Keats’s and Khan’s poetry as manifesting a cosmic self through annihilation and oneness, reflecting its cross-cultural and universal significance.

6.3.3. Significance of Immaterial and Material

The pursuit of both material and immaterial aspects has always played a defining role in shaping the movement and direction of history. Often, the conflict between these two dimensions has driven humans to either heights or depths. Keats and Khan display an urge to explore and unveil the relationship between the material and immaterial as significant dimensions of the cosmic self. In Keats’s and Khan’s poetry, this exploration delves symbolically into the finite and the infinite, the concrete and the abstract, the phenomena and

the noumena. Their poetry shows a blurring of the boundaries between temporal and spatial divisions. The perceptions associated with these images endure across human distributions, cultures, traditions, geographies and ages.

Ibn Arabi views the cosmos as the spirit of the divine, existing in everything, as both the seeker and the sought (Ibn Arabi, 2004). Kant also sounds somewhat similar to Ibn Arabi when he argues that the sensible world only contains appearances. In contrast, the world that stands independently is the world beyond sensory perceptions (Kant, 1998).

Many philosophies and religions of the world are unanimous in holding eternal within the temporal. Keats's "Ode on a Grecian Urn" accentuates this point by presenting an analogy from the routine. It suggests that the urn is not merely a piece of art, but a sample of the immaterial within the mortal world that has endured since ancient times. Even the images on its surface convey the message of eternity shrouded in their frozen state. Slow time cannot be perceived through the normal senses. It needs a more profound imaginative vision for this perception as the Grecian urn "Thou still unravish'd bride of quietness, / Thou foster-child of Silence and slow Time..." (lines 1–2). The material world is also significant because it serves as a conduit for the self to be transported to the immaterial world, as exemplified by the urn or the nightingale. When Keats says that "Beauty is truth, truth beauty," he acknowledges the truth of material, earthly existence (lines 49–50).

Khan also explores the connection between the material and the immaterial in his poetry. He displays an inclination to access the immaterial world beyond the material. Khan's concept of the beautiful is expressed in his poem "*Khayal*" (Fancy), "All that is beautiful and perfect / Have the same perfection, beauty." In the same verse, he acknowledges the role of the human senses in their contact with the material world to unveil the immaterial beauty:

In each hand, in every torch,	<i>Aw ranrra speena la khuda</i>
It is the same beauty and light;	<i>Pa har laas pa har mashaal ki</i>

in his poem “*Meena*” (*Love*), where he makes love comprise both the material and immaterial experience:

She said, ‘love is a scourge,	<i>Haghi wi meena ghazab dey sarrey rroond</i>
One gets blinded, sees no more.’	<i>shee naabeena shee</i>
I said, ‘eyes aware of God,	<i>Maa wi khudai ta naabeena stargi tal jahaan</i>
To the world, they are without sight...	<i>ta naa beena shee</i>

(pp. 152–153).

Keats and Khan make no scruples in displaying the material and immaterial as inseparable dimensions of the cosmic self. Keats explores the relationship between the material and the immaterial by offering images of love and beauty that exist in the material world, with a longing to transcend the material. Khan appears to be more fascinated with linking the material and immaterial as manifestations or even emanations of the divinely cosmic essence through beauty and love. Both poets thus share a relationship that closely connects them despite the cross-cultural, geographical and historical gaps between them.

6.3.4. Significance of Essence and Existence

The question of essence and existence holds a significant position in mysticism, philosophy and literature at trans-cultural and universal levels. Keats and Khan, like Ibn Arabi and Kant, are driven by the desire to explore the relation between essence and existence. Their approach is more existential because they consider essence and existence as intermingled and spanning the whole of existence on earth.

According to Ibn Arabi, all that exists emanates from the divine essence (Ibn Arabi, 1980). In a similar vein, Kant argues that without making any effort to connect the essence and existence, all externally visible objects are mere appearances. In contrast, the real thing-in-itself is always hidden from us (Kant, 1998).

Keats finds it challenging to come to terms with his mortal status. Not only has he been pushed into the testing circumstances of life, but also been pulled away from his beloved Fanny Brawne. The only course left with him is to set himself free from the constraints of the temporal and spatial existence through transcendence to the real essence. The timeless beauty, as manifested through nature, where the nightingale warbles out its immortal song, is juxtaposed with his existence, seeking after the essence, like a nightingale, in the woods. The nightingale thus becomes a symbol of human existence. In contrast, its song symbolises eternity and infinity when Keats writes, “Thou wast not born for death, immortal Bird! / No hungry generations tread thee down!” (lines 61–62). These lines contrast the temporality of the physical world of existence, where, despite the hunger for immortality, none has been able to attain unity with the essence.

The journey from existence to essence continues in Khan as well, but with some differences. His speaker in the poems is either one in essence and existence or successfully achieves this state of oneness. Khan’s poem “*Badiwa*” (*The Kite*) reflects on the same journey from essence to existence:

In a wide expanse of sky,	<i>Dumra weerr asmaan ki da khpal rang</i>
Streaks of colour you display,	<i>saaskee khkaara krri tah</i>
Mounted on the steed of wind,	<i>Choong khaawra wajood yau liwantub yau</i>
You observe the static form,	<i>nazaara krri tah</i>
Of the earth stretched out below	

(pp. 70–71).

The flight of the kite in heaven symbolically represents a universal human desire for freedom and the quest for the divine essence.

Despite considerable progress, corporeal existence has been unable to reveal the mysterious and ineffable essence. Khan describes this conflict in a sequential order in his poem

“*Jannat aw Duniya*” (The World and Heaven):

When a thing becomes eternal,	<i>Har yau shey chi abadee shee yuu afat shee yau</i>
It becomes a scourge, infernal.	
The unending aeons of time,	<i>azaab shee</i>
From the dawn of all creation,	
The eternal existence,	<i>Bas yau taa sara maza kah daa azal abad</i>
Can suit You and You alone.	<i>dawaam</i>

(pp. 56–61).

The permanence and impermanence thus work as a paradox, with essence being rooted in the divine.

Keats and Khan consider the essence as timeless and existence as transitory, but both are bound together tightly by cosmic unity and order. Keats illustrates this through the urn in his ode, which, despite its existence in the physical and fleeting world, represents the indomitable permanence of the essence that holds all the images upon its surface. Thus, the urn paradoxically symbolises the world in its existence and the world in its essence, where the images have attained immortality because they have become one with the essence that is the urn, just as Keats’s urn has captured the frozen moments within itself. Khan represents a realistic self and hates giving it eternity. This state of eternity may also turn out to be a curse, where nobody can escape or change, thus enduring the restraints of inescapability eternally.

Keats and Khan thus present a universally cherished human yearning to transcend the self in its state of existence and unite with the cosmic essence. Despite living on widely different continents and in different periods, both poets acknowledge the dual aspects of reality as eternal and temporal. They derive interpretations from the essence and existence, reflecting the transcultural and universal appeal of the questions related to essence and existence. Like the mystical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and the philosophical ideas of Kant, both Keats and Khan also display metaphysical underpinnings that view essence and existence as aspects of

the cosmic self. These ideas have influenced both Eastern and Western mysticism and philosophy.

6.3.5. Significance of Love and Beauty

It is the divine to create a universe to know the divine self. Otherwise, the treasure would have remained unacknowledged (Ibn Arabi, 1980). The beautiful not only gives us a concept, but also produces a universal pleasure (Kant, 1790/1998).

The ephemerality of corporeal existence has attracted thoughtful poets, such as Keats and Khan, particularly in association with beauty and love. These aspects are acknowledged transculturally and universally for their significance. The transcending and elevating influence of these experiences relieves one from the miseries of physical existence. However, these also inflict pain and agony due to their paradoxical relation with life and death. Keats's famous quote in "*Ode to a Nightingale*," rejecting any notion of death associated with the nightingale, suggests that beauty is immortal. Keats acknowledges the transitoriness of beauty as well in another "*Ode on Melancholy*," where beauty is shown as suffering death towards the end. Beauty has been seen as a combination of both pain and pleasure. Khan considers love and beauty as timeless experiences of life that bind the immediate as well as the remote in an unbreakable chain. Khan says in his poem "*Da Khaapiru Shazadgai*" (*The Fairy Princess*):

I am your servitor;	<i>Maa wi ay da jannat bibi zah staa da dar</i>
And will as a devotee,	<i>malang yema</i>
Sit beside your palace door.	<i>Dir tang da di jahaana da ghamoonu na yi</i>
I'm weary of the world outside,	<i>tang yema</i>
Afraid of pain and store...	

(pp. 48–51).

This sentiment shows a retreat within, as it is scared of the painful physical existence without. It also highlights the importance of the individual self.

Keats and Khan offer a transcendental association of love and beauty in their poetry. They also consider love as a temporary experience that transcends the individual and connects to the cosmic. Keats also shows that a creative masterpiece gives pleasure. It is the harmonious nature of art that carries attraction. An imbalanced piece always has a repelling effect. Keats describes this in "**Ode on a Grecian Urn**," which exemplifies the paradoxical nature of beauty and truth. Khan mirrors this reciprocity of beauty and truth in his poem "**Saakht**" (**Creation**):

Reason: no more than two paces can be taken.	<i>Aqal khu dwa gaama laarr shee bas akhwa tah wruk aw hairaana shee</i>
Thereafter, it loses itself in the maze;	
In beauty there lies, Your ultimate proof,	<i>Husan ki hagma daleel dey staa stargi da zrra pri rukhaana shee</i>
Enlightening the eyes of the heart and the soul.	

(pp. 34–35).

The above-quoted excerpt from Khan validates a close affinity between love and beauty as intrinsic to the human self.

Physical beauty cannot withstand the test of time due to its transience; therefore, it is often associated with pain and loss. Keats and Khan also acknowledge the impermanence that such beauty always leads to pain. The only way out is to achieve transcendence through seeking the eternal beauty which Keats does portray in "**Ode to Autumn**," in words, "And still more, later flowers for the bees, / Until they think warm days will never cease, / For summer has o'erbrimmed their clammy cells..." (lines 8–10). Khan also reiterates this theme related to beauty, and its transitory nature in "**Jannat Aw Duniya**" (**The World and Heaven**) when he says, "Beauty lies in the impermanence and transitoriness / If forever I were young, / Youth would surely be a curse..." (pp. 56–61). This characteristic of fragility or impermanence in beauty is an essential part of human experience.

Keats and Khan also share a yearning to unite and bring synthesis to the material and immaterial worlds through love and beauty. The connection between the material and the divine through love and beauty is manifest in Keats’s “*Endymion*.” It begins with praise to honour beauty by making it something that never fades but increases in beauty with every passing day, without ever entering a non-existent state. Khan displays the same sentiment in his poem “*Badiwa*” (*The Kite*) when he says, “Like a rose without its roots / You adorn the sky...” which reflects the divine connection (pp. 70–71). Love and beauty are indispensable for transformation in the world. Khan’s poem “*Yaw Jaam*” (*A Goblet of Wine*) demonstrates the same theme:

Raving mad, my dreams ignite,	<i>Mast mast raakrra khuboona chi patt krram</i>
Overcome my maddening grief;	<i>pri ghammona</i>
To the rhythmic beat of life,	<i>Shuroo krra da zhwand taal tah naazuk da</i>
Strike the notes of beauty’s strains,	<i>Khaisht suroona</i>
Lover and beloved be,	<i>Dilbar sha dilruba sha yau jaam jaam</i>
Bring a goblet full for me!	<i>raawrra</i>

(pp. 42–45).

6.4. Conclusion

This chapter examined convergence and divergence regarding the cosmic self in Keats’s and Khan’s poetry, as well as its cross-cultural and universal significance. Despite the geographical, historical and linguistic differences between Keats and Khan, they developed a bridge through their themes regarding the concept of the cosmic self between the East and the West. The cosmic self as transcending experiences and egoistic tendencies, leads to self-realisation. Keats and Khan also demonstrate the significance accorded to the cosmic self in their poetry. Keats and Khan are thus part of a tradition that sought to explore the true essence of the cosmic self.

This study culminates in the succeeding chapter, which will synthesise all the data analysed regarding the cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's poetry concerning the frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant.

CHAPTER SEVEN

Postlude:

A Wandering Keats from a far-off Place like Wretched Khan

My heart has become capable of every form:
It is a pasture for gazelles and a convent for Christian monks,
A temple for idols and the pilgrim's Kaaba,
The tables of the Torah and the book of the Quran.
I follow the religion of Love; whatever way Love's camels take,
That is my religion and my faith.

(Ibn Arabi, 1911, p. 67).

7.1. Introduction

This study culminates in this final chapter that synthesises findings from the data analysis. The study was inspired by the goal of conducting a comparative analysis of the dissolution phenomenon in the closure of many of Keats's poems and addressing existential questions in the *Pashto* poetry of Khan. In line with the comparative study, a conceptual framework regarding the cosmic self was developed from the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Despite the concept of self having taken place mysteriously at different levels, the cosmic self is the one that unites the cosmos, the egoistic self and the divinely infinite (Nasr, 2007). So, it becomes a magnification and expansion of the individual self by merging it with all creation and the divine essence, which is universally found in the ascetic and mystic traditions across the East and West.

The research questions that guided this study throughout the data analysis were directed towards the objectives of finding the attributes of self and its cosmic association in Keats's and Khan's poetry from the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. These are followed by how Keats and Khan demonstrated convergence and divergence in their poetry regarding the concept of the cosmic self. The study concludes on the synthesis and significance in cross-cultural and

universal terms accorded to the cosmic self by Keats and Khan in their poetic compositions.

This chapter comprises the following main sections:

- Synthesis of Findings
- Recommendations
- Theoretical Implications of the Study
- Limitations of the Study

7.2. Synthesis of Findings

This study has revealed a deep mystical and philosophical connection regarding the cosmic self between Keats's and Khan's poetry after exploring them through the frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. Despite the spatial, temporal, cultural and intellectual disparity in the background of Keats and Khan, they try to negotiate between the dialectical concepts like material-immaterial, finite-infinite, essence-existence. Both Keats and Khan have an ambiguous attitude towards the self.

They often develop a concept of the self that is rooted in being finite but secures transcendence. This section comprises a synthesis of the data analysis by locating the self along with all its dimensions.

7.2.1. Bridging the Material and Immaterial

This research finds that the self is a central entity that provides an *isthmus*, an intermediary and a *barzakh* (Ibn Arabi) between the sensory (phenomenal, material, existence) realm and the supra-sensory (noumenal, intangible, essence) realm in Keats's and Khan's poetry. Keats often presents the self as existing and processing experiences from the tangible as well as intangible world. It is besides the fact that the tangible or material world is impermanent, but the intangible or immaterial one is permanent. Despite living in a transitory world of change, the beauty of art assumes a universal and everlasting form in "Ode on a Grecian Urn," when Keats presents

the urn as both communicating with the sensory and supra-sensory realms by pulling him out of his reveries.

Khan's protagonist, like Keats's, hovers between different phenomenal levels from the earth to the sky while employing natural images. Khan frequently uses images like stars, moon, sun, flowers and rivers. Khan uses the image of a flying kite, which is neither connected to heaven nor the earth (only with a delicate thread) but remains suspended between both. Similarly, Keats emphasises the continuity and flow of life through these images. For example, he uses adjectives like swift (*Hyperion*), wide (*Ode to Autumn*), lucent (*The Eve of St. Agnes*) and slumberous (*Endymion*) for rivers and liquids.

Kant pictures the self as being constrained by the physical or phenomenal self, but it is noumenal, having agentive capacity to abide by the moral law with an idea of intrinsic dignity. This noumenally moral-agentive self aligns with Ibn Arabi's Perfect Being that mirrors and reflects the divine. However, it is restrained by the compulsions of creation. Both Ibn Arabi and Kant agree that a poet mediates between the physical and the spiritual, with neither being passive nor impermanent. The poet mediates between the phenomenal and noumenal. Keats makes the poet a dreamer and a mediator between heaven and earth (*Endymion*) or a god whose enormous knowledge and poetic skills can bring order in heaven and earth (*Apollo in Hyperion*) or a priest who can build a temple in the imaginal realm to look completely real (*Ode to Psyche*). Khan's poet is also not different from Keats's, because Khan also makes the poet an intermediary between heaven and earth on account of his imaginative power. The poet lives in the physical realm but has insight into the heavenly realms (*The Mother of My Children*) or can see heavenly light in the earthly beauty (*A Dream of A Poet*).

7.2.2. Transcendence through Annihilation and Oneness

Another recurring theme in both Keats's and Khan's poetry is self-annihilation. Kant looks at unity as transcendence through cognition, while Ibn Arabi sees it through self-effacement. This

dimension varies according to whether it is being viewed in a mystical or in a philosophical perspective. Keats and Khan follow a dialectical approach in their poetry that engages the protagonists in a relationship of thesis, anti-thesis and synthesis. This dialectical process also emphasises the existence of a consoler or advisor in Keats's and Khan's poetry. Keats initially dissolves himself entirely in love and beauty (*Lamia*, *The Eve of St. Agnes*, *Endymion*). However, in his longer narrative poems, where Keats appears to lose himself entirely and slowly fade away from sight towards the end of the poems, Keats's lyrical poems, such as odes, develop from a desire of escape or disappearance through fading away. He is pulled back towards the end. He accepts a reconciliation between the physical and spiritual. For instance, Keats rejects the world of imagination (*Ode to a Nightingale*) and accepts the impermanence associated with earthly life (beauty's decay in *Ode on Melancholy*). Keats thus rejects nihilistic tendencies while accepting a more participatory and reconciliatory approach (Kant's acceptance of the sublime due to limitations of reason).

Khan's poetry is more in line with Ibn Arab's concept of self-annihilation, which recommends dissolution of the entire self (ego) and winning unity with the beloved (the divine). For instance, Khan either entirely fuses himself to the extent of leaving behind nothing known as an entity (the poet being spread all over the platter or *Majnoon* in "Strange Philosophy") or he idealises icons of self-annihilation like *Mansoor*, whose heart is beloved in itself.

Keats dissolves into an aesthetic and philosophical experience, but Khan's dissolution is mystical in the *Sufi* tradition. Keats is more an *Akbarian* with respect to the question of essence than a Kantian. Peace comes only through a reconciliation between the different component dimensions of the human self. Keats's poetry also highlights a movement from a longing for annihilation to affirmation and reconciliation in the end. Almost every poem of Keats is designed on a super and sub-structure. It is in both Keats and Khan to present the concept of *barzakh* or intermediary in their poetry, reflecting their ambiguous approach towards life. This

approach of looking for intermediaries in both Keats and Khan reflects their inner desire for search. Keats and Khan also show through their verses that a cosmic self is always about synthesis.

7.2.3. Nature as a Source of Self-Projection

Nature is the best companion of the companionless. The world of nature carries symbolic connotations. Both Keats and Khan envision their inner projection into the external nature. Keats portrays this projection through a transformation of seasons, natural surroundings and heavenly bodies (Odes to Autumn and Nightingale, Hyperion and Endymion). The symbolic association of these natural phenomena aligns with Kant, who sees in this freedom and purpose. For example, nature is elevating, carrying a spiritual force behind it (Ode to a Nightingale), the grandeur of cosmos (Hyperion) and nature being appreciated for its own sake (Ode to Autumn).

As in Ibn Arabi's mystical philosophy, nature manifests the divine. It reflects the divine attributes in humans and external nature. Keats expresses an attitude that reflects a longing and transcendence, but Khan strikes a connection and sees himself in nature. Khan assumes several forms of nature in his poetry. He becomes a tulip (Prayer), or a poppy flower (The Flower) or holds an entire field of flowers within his own heart (*Mansoor*).

7.2.4. Connecting All through Love

The study also confirms that it is love that holds all the dimensions of the cosmic self together. It is only love that has the capacity to overpower other dimensions and their limitations. Every creative act, such as poetry and other arts, is subject to love and cannot create any piece without love, or if at all it does, the created thing will lose its credibility after some time. The immaterial self cannot be reconciled until it accepts the immaterial or love within the human self. Love pulls together the opposites, such as finite and infinite, mortal and immortal, essence and existence, divine and earthly, material and immaterial. Kant divides the metaphysical principles into regulative and constitutive. Love is a regulative principle because it structures the human

self towards moral and aesthetic goals. Love is a source of eternal pleasure (Endymion), a connection between material and immaterial (Ode to a Nightingale), pain and pleasure (Isabella; or, The Pot of Basil).

Khan believes in love being divine. Even earthly and physical entities take divine status. These become manifestations of the divine. Khan is in the tradition of Ibn Arabi and argues that the whole creation manifests the divine love, because it is created out of love by the divine. He thus holds a concept of the cosmic self that aligns with both Ibn Arabi and Kant. Khan is willing to give up even beauty for love because it is immortal (Love and Beauty), it is regenerative after death (Love), and it brings grief (*Deodasi*).

7.2.5. Teleological Underpinnings

Keats and Khan are driven towards different teleological ends. The Kantian teleology sees purposiveness without purpose, which cannot be logically or scientifically explained. Keats's negative capability completely aligns with Kant's teleology. Keats is happy in the very experience of either being in the company of nature or in the aesthetics (Ode to a Nightingale), or the natural life cycle that moves towards fruition (Ode to Autumn), or beauty becomes a source of eternal pleasure (Endymion).

Khan founds his teleology on the principles of metaphysics. Like mystics, Khan often aims at attaining unity and oneness with the divine. Khan is thus more in line with Ibn Arabi, who finds all creation moving towards divine unity and essence. Unlike Keats, who remains between the two realms of the physical and metaphysical and then ultimately either accepts the physical or the metaphysical, Khan accepts the merging with the One in the end. For example, Khan keeps thinking about the noumenal world of abstraction (Swing), or being one with the one (Longing), or it appears in material form like a summit on some far-off location (Summit).

7.2.6. Unified Framework

Keats and Khan can be placed in a unified framework as follows:

- Both engage in a dynamic relationship with the material and immaterial, essence and existence, beauty and pleasure, earthly and divine.
- They live between the two realms of physical and spiritual, permanent and impermanent.
- Their dissolution of the self results in transcendence and transformation.
- Both use love and beauty as sources for connecting all the dimensions of a cosmic self.
- Keats and Khan emphasise that a cosmic self exists beyond the material, representing two modalities of the physical and spiritual that belong wholly to neither this realm nor the other.

7.2.7. Implications for Comparative Poetics

- This comparative study reveals that, having read Keats's Romantic poetry, it achieves an entirely mystical interpretation, but when read through Kant, it acquires philosophical underpinnings. Similarly, when Khan is read through Ibn Arabi, he emerges as a mystic but a philosopher when read through Kant. Such a cross-cultural, mystical and philosophical background highlights a better interpretation.
- This shows that cross-cultural frameworks provide ample room for a richer and versatile interpretation. It emphasises that the self is much greater than what it usually appears to be. Humans combine in them both the macro and micro cosmos while themselves becoming a mirror of the divine. Humans use imagery and symbols, as highlighted through this study, in order to understand and articulate the cosmic connection in the universe.
- Once having developed this cosmic belongingness, humans develop a sense of humility, companionship and care. Textual and phenomenological pairing of poems

with selective philosophical exegesis show how images instantiate metaphysical claims and how philosophical concepts illuminate poetic strategies.

- The study emphasises that the cosmic self and its association with the finite and infinite show a rich source of addressing contrasting frameworks in the philosophical and mystical traditions.
- The study also highlights why some images attract the poets universally, such as stars, night, mountains and rivers, etc. The concept of cosmic self that associates the universe into a single whole drives our ethical considerations, thus linking metaphysics to the demands of social aspects.

7.3. Recommendations

Keats's approach to realising the cosmic self is through negative capability, which involves accepting the existence of mysteries and doubt, much like Kant. In contrast, Khan's approach is more mystical, emphasising the entire surrender through self-effacement, as seen in Ibn Arabi. Thus, self-realisation not only requires complete surrender, as in mystical unity, but also accepting the agentive role of the individual self through moral and creative autonomy.

Keats, like Ibn Arabi, adopts a passive attitude towards beauty, love and the arts, but Khan has an active approach, with a greater emphasis on the realisation of divine love through both rebellion and contemplation, similar to Kant. It requires humans to develop a sense of understanding of the arts and beauty through their aesthetic sense, thereby establishing a connection between the finite and the infinite, or the cosmic whole.

Keats and Khan agree on the role of contradictions and paradoxes in human life, a perspective similar to that of Ibn Arabi and Kant in their metaphysical and philosophical frameworks. Therefore, the essence of a genuinely cosmic self is not in eliminating contradictions but in accepting these opposites in life.

There exists an affinity between Keats and Khan regarding an inseparable connection between the past, present and future, similar to that of Ibn Arabi and Kant, who transcend these spatiotemporal constraints and divisions. Therefore, it is suggested that a more profound sense of communion between the individual self and an ineffable, cosmic and noumenal self be developed through contemplation and meditation.

Keats's concept of freedom is more in line with Kant's, who advocates imaginative flight through aesthetic experience in the face of the sublime. Khan is more in line with Ibn Arabi, who seeks freedom through surrendering the self and self-annihilation in the face of love and beauty. Freedom thus requires acceptance of contradictory demands, which means either gaining freedom through self-negation or autonomy. Therefore, freedom can be achieved through both self-negation and self-affirmation, as espoused by Keats and Khan, aligning with Ibn Arabi and Kant.

Neither Keats nor Khan rejects the material world. However, Keats, much like Kant, considers the material world to exist separately from the immaterial realm, and Khan, similarly to Ibn Arabi, views the material world as a mere illusion, with the divine being immanent in all creation. It thus requires that instead of rejecting material existence like hermits, it should be accepted with all its pitfalls and realities as a gateway to unveiling the cosmic self.

Keats and Khan worship beauty and love, and Keats is more in line with Kant, who holds beauty as an aspect of the ineffable sublime in nature, art and music. However, Khan lays more emphasis on love, similar to Ibn Arabi, who views it as an inseparable part of the First Cause when the universe was created by the divine out of love. Humans must develop a sense of understanding for love and beauty in nature, art and even in human relationships to attain oneness with the cosmic whole.

Keats and Khan project a fluid sense of the cosmic self. Keats is both *Akbarian* and Kantian because he oscillates between autonomy and self-negation, whereas Khan is also both

Akbarian and Kantian. After all, he oscillates between autonomy and self-effacement. Humans thus need to develop an inclusive approach by accommodating a fluid sense of the self and encouraging both the mystical union and individual creativity.

Keats and Khan hold art, poetry and creativity in high esteem, channelling them to gain access to the cosmic self. If Kant sees the sublime in the arts, Ibn Arabi finds a divine connection in poetic creativity. Therefore, we should encourage the pursuit of creative and artistic studies to fulfil the epistemological requirements of unveiling the cosmic self.

Keats and Khan encapsulate the mystical and philosophical frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant, allowing for both intuitive and rational understandings of the self. Thus, we should develop a wholesome approach that synthesises rational and mystical knowledge of the self and its cosmic significance.

7.4. Theoretical Implications of the Study

This study highlights a dialectical relationship between Ibn Arabi's concept of Unity of Being and Kant's transcendental idealism. These two traditions, rooted in contrasting philosophies, complement each other in their understanding of selfhood and self-recognition. They represent cross-cultural and universal implications of the concept of cosmic self. This study would yield rich dividends by encouraging a more significant number of integrative models to be developed along the lines of the conceptual framework established for this study.

This study fosters a more comprehensive framework, similar to those developed by combining the mystical framework of Ibn Arabi (Unity of Being and self-annihilation) with the philosophical framework of Kant (duality of existence). It demonstrates that the cosmic self represents a universal significance through dissolution and artistic expression. This juxtaposition of the *Akbarian* and Kantian perspectives through analysis of Keats and Khan also presents a model that explores both the self being dissolved in the cosmos and the self being autonomous through the retention of its agentive role.

The study challenges the long-held notion that the Romantic Movement is a Western phenomenon, which, however, can be paralleled with the *Sufi* tradition in the East. This study demonstrates that, despite being part of the Romantic Movement, Keats's poetry carries mystical and spiritual connotations similar to those found in *Sufi* literature. This also applies to Khan, whose poetry should be examined from Kant's political and philosophical perspective, rather than focusing solely on the mystical elements. Thus, the study inspires a reanalysis of Keats, Khan and many other poets across different cultures and periods.

Poetry provides Keats and Khan with the instrument to transcend the individual self by merging with the greater self represented by the cosmic whole. Thus, poetry aligns with Kant's emphasis on the aesthetic experience and the sublime, as well as Ibn Arabi's concept of viewing the creative process as a divine act. The study thus demonstrates that creative masterpieces of art, including poetry, transcend the boundaries between the material and the immaterial.

Despite the preference for individualism over cosmic significance that has emerged under the influence of modern intellectual development, this study addresses the issue by juxtaposing both perspectives. Both Keats and Khan suggest the dissolution of the self through philosophical and mystical means. However, it does not mean total self-effacement, but rather the integration of the individual self with the larger cosmic whole. This approach will inspire different branches of modern philosophy regarding their discussions of self-recognition and understanding.

Keats and Khan link the past, present and future through transcendence, like Ibn Arabi and Kant. They foster the idea that poetic compositions convey a concept of time that diverges from the conventional understanding of time.

The study also promotes a more widely accepted understanding of cultural nuances, emphasising that the pursuit of meaning, freedom and cosmic unity is a shared goal of humanity

by challenging ethnic, racial and religious polarisation. It develops a model based on inclusion to bring synthesis between intellectual and spiritual traditions.

This study also inspires autonomy and surrender to the cosmic whole, as espoused by Kant and Ibn Arabi, respectively. Thus, it will influence moral philosophy and existential psychology by reconciling the tension between autonomy and surrender.

This study develops an analytical framework by synthesising Ibn Arabi's mystical philosophy and Kant's transcendental idealism into a single whole. This encourages the development of models founded upon mysticism and philosophy. It will help future comparative literature researchers to contribute by exploring the concept of the cosmic self.

In this modern age of selfishness and individualism, which divides the world into several blocks, philosophical and mystical discussions assume great significance. Thus, the study offers reconciliation between the dichotomies and contradictions through poetic creativity.

7.5. Limitations of the Study

The study was conducted purely from philosophical, mystical and literary perspectives. This study cannot entirely encompass the vast significance and magnitude of the cosmic self. Therefore, a few dimensions, such as freedom, love and beauty, as well as the distinction between material and immaterial, essence and existence, were selected with particular reference to the frameworks of Ibn Arabi and Kant. However, since the study remained principally exploratory to analyse the poetic works of Keats and Khan through the philosophical perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant, the researcher ran the risk of over-intellectualising the poetic compositions. Thus, a deliberate effort was made to make poetic interpretations strictly objective by taking help from the available research work on Keats's and Khan's poetry. The arguments and examples to support points were unavoidably within the premises of the abstract and theoretical dimensions.

7.6. Future Directions

The conceptual framework developed for this study can be replicated for other literary works as well. Similarly, such studies can be conducted by combining other philosophers from the East and the West. Since the concept of self holds equal significance in psychology, it can be explored in poetic works from psychological perspectives.

7.7. Conclusion

This chapter presented the key findings in light of the analysis conducted in the previous chapters. The findings of the analysis were compiled under different headings, ranging from convergence to divergence and cross-cultural significance, regarding the concept of the cosmic self in Keats's and Khan's poetry, as viewed through the perspectives of Ibn Arabi and Kant. The study offered recommendations, followed by theoretical implications. In short, this study of Keats's and Khan's poetry, conducted through the lens of the *Akbarian* and Kantian frameworks, explored the concept of the cosmic self from mystical and philosophical perspectives. It was also revealed that Keats's and Khan's poetry shares profound similarities in themes such as love, beauty, freedom, essence and existence, as well as the material and immaterial dimensions of the cosmic self. Considering the cross-cultural and universal significance of the cosmic self, political and racial disparities between humans can be eliminated by acknowledging the universal and cosmic connectivity of the human self.

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